

**AGENT-BASED
SUPPORT TOOL FOR
THE DEVELOPMENT
OF AGRICULTURE POLICIES**

D1.5 Characterisation of national and regional data sources

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Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the methodology defined within the AGRICORE project to characterise national and regional data sources useful for performing agricultural research analysis. This methodology has been developed as part of the first of the work packages defined in the AGRICORE project. AGRICORE is a research project proposing an innovative way to apply agent-based modelling to improve the capacities of policymakers to evaluate the impact of agricultural-related measurements under and outside the framework of the Common Agricultural Policy. This project was funded by the European Commission as a result of the RUR-04-2018 call, part of the H2020 programme.

In the introduction, the basis on which the methodology has been developed is presented, i.e., the ARDIT tool and the AGRICORE DCAT-AP 2.0 ontology. Then, the proposed methodology is detailed including also the definition of all the fields to be filled while characterising a dataset in ARDIT. As part of this methodology, also all the main challenges encountered during the characterisation of the datasets have been explained, illustrating the proposed solutions. After that, also the methodology proposed to guarantee that the tool ARDIT remains efficiently working is described, relying on a continuous upgrade and maintenance of the data. Finally, some conclusions regarding the characterisation process and the need for a governance strategy to ensure the survival of the ARDIT after the project are provided.

It is important to remark that although this deliverable has been developed in the framework of the AGRICORE project, the participating partners have aimed for broader usage of the proposed methodology. As the final goal of this work package, the proposed EU Index Tool (now renamed as Agricultural Research Data Index Tool (ARDIT)) aims to serve as a central entry point for locating useful datasets useful for agricultural research.

Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Full name
ABM	Agent-Based Model
AP	Application Profile
API	Application Programming Interface
ARDIT	Agricultural Research Data Index Tool
CSV	comma-separated values
DCAT	Data Catalogue
DCAT-AP	Data Catalogue Application Profile
EEC	European Economic Commission
EC	European Commission
ELSTAT	Hellenic Statistical Authority
EU	European Union
FADN	Farm Accountancy Data Network
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organisation of the United Nations
GUI	Graphic User Interface
IACS	Integrated Administration and Control System
ISTAT	Istituto nazionale di statistica
LAU	Local administrative units
NUTS	Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
RDF	Resource Description Framework
UoA	Unit of Analysis
UC	User case
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
VOCAB-DQV	Data Quality Vocabulary
WP	Work Package

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1 Introduction

The goal of the Agricultural Research Data Index Tool (ARDIT) is to support agricultural researchers in the identification of the most suitable datasets to meet their model requirements and answer their research questions, without having to retrieve the complete datasets. This will represent a great help considering that generally even just obtaining preliminary access to some datasets can result in expending a significant effort by the researcher, which could be in vain especially in case the data is, upon retrieval and inspection, inadequate (e.g. due to an undesired unit of analysis of the dataset or the lack of one or more key variables). In addition, the amount of data necessary to use large-scale models, or combinations of multiple models, is likely to be significant. Therefore, properly organising the relevant datasets to be ready for use, by selecting or manipulating parts of them, could be a limiting factor for some researchers. Specifically, this activity has relied on having access to good and complete descriptions (i.e., metadata) of the contents of the dataset, especially on the characteristics of the variables contained in them. The methodology presented in the following sections has been developed to collect all the relevant information on datasets, such that this knowledge could be stored, manipulated and displayed employing the AGRICORE ontology. Lastly, this information will be gathered and hosted in the ARDIT, which will be then used to allow researchers to identify useful data sources for them.

The proposed methodology to characterise agricultural datasets is described through the three main elements that it is composed of:

1. The proposed ontology: The AGRICORE DCAT-AP 2.0 Extension
2. The ARDIT tool
3. The data governance process

This process has been applied within the project to characterise an extensive set of data sources covering EU-wide and local datasets (especially those relevant to the three use cases foreseen in the AGRICORE project). Moreover, this methodology also describes the process that should be followed after the project to add contents in ARDIT.

As already said, one of the goals of the AGRICORE project is to provide the ARDIT as a tool for agricultural researchers to facilitate the task of identifying relevant and useful data for performing agricultural policy analysis. To do so, the AGRICORE partners devised a characterisation methodology (detailed in the next sections) for describing the available data sources and their content to enable proper mapping and searching capabilities over the gathered information. To design such a methodology, one of the key elements is the definition and adoption of an ontology (or a set of them), which allows:

- To share a **common understanding** of the structure of information among people or software agents.
- To enable the **reuse** of domain knowledge.
- To make domain **assumptions explicit**.
- To **separate domain** knowledge from the **operational** knowledge
- To **analyse** domain knowledge
- To secure the interoperability of datasets

All these motivations are present in the AGRICORE project. Indeed, to ensure the long-term usefulness of the ARDIT platform well beyond the scope of the AGRICORE project, it has been critical to develop it in a way that it is easy to upgrade and maintain as well as user-friendly for the research community as a whole. Accordingly, during the first months of the project,

consortium partners performed an analysis of existing ontologies that could be used for developing the ARDIT.

In order to build the ontology used for characterising the datasets on the ARDIT, Protégé 5 ¹, was selected due to the large community deeming it a reliable and flexible collaborative tool available as an open-source product both in a desktop and web version. As reported by previous studies [1], it has a suite of tools to construct domain models and knowledge-based applications with ontologies. It implements a rich set of knowledge-modelling structures and actions that support the creation, visualisation and manipulation of ontologies in various representation formats. It can be customised to provide domain-friendly support to creating knowledge models and entering data. Also, it can be extended by a plug-in architecture and Java-based API for building knowledge-base tools and applications. Protégé allows the definition of classes, class hierarchy's variables, variable-value restrictions, and the relationships between classes and the properties of these relationships.

Within the next phases of the AGRICORE project, the ontology will allow the application of semantic queries in ARDIT for searching datasets information and characterisations. Likewise, it will allow a continuous enrichment of the number and quality of datasets characterisations through the ARDIT GUI tailored to fit the data model structure described by the ontology.

¹ <http://protegeproject.github.io/protege/getting-started>

2 National and regional datasets

An important aspect addressed by the AGRICORE project in characterising data sources is the distinction between national and regional datasets. This latter is not due to the level of geographical representativeness but in the specificity and uniqueness of the databases. National datasets, in their definition, refer to rules that are valid on a national or supranational scale and are usually defined and managed by national statistical offices (e.g.: ISTAT for Italy). These datasets are organised by successive aggregations, from the Local Administrative Units up to the size of NUTS 1. Moreover, to meet the demand for statistics at a local level, Eurostat maintains a system of Local Administrative Units (LAUs) compatible with NUTS. These LAUs are the building blocks of the NUTS and comprise the municipalities and communes of the European Union. The LAUs are administrative units responsible for the availability of data and policy implementation. They are a subdivision of the NUTS 3 regions covering the whole economic territory of the Member States. It follows that the information in the national databases, referred to the regional level (NUTS 2), or even to the LAU level, are comparable with each other.

On the other hand, when talking about regional datasets we refer to two conditions: the focus on the regions and the regional uniqueness of some information. In the first case, the regional datasets allow a concise and efficient reading of statistical information with the aim of characterising a certain region by allowing it to be compared with other regions of the planet. A significant example of this is the regional statistics provided by the OECD² and the databases built in compliance with the procedures established by the IACS administrative databases. In the second case, the datasets are specific to a certain region, they are not reproducible or do not allow the comparison between regional datasets. These datasets usually present information that is relevant to regional policymakers and they were mainly developed in the past when datasets were not harmonised. An example in the agricultural field is the IACS databases that report information on farm holdings that have applied for payments under the Rural Development Plans. Very often these databases are written in the national language and are difficult to use.

² <https://www.oecd.org/regional/regional-statistics>

3 Methodology for the selection and characterisation

Selected datasets

The data sources characterised in the ARDIT tool have been selected to meet the needs of the agent-based model (ABM). In the AGRICORE project, specific attention has been dedicated to National datasets, as they are the main source of data and information required to run farmers based models. Spanish, Greek and Polish datasets have been characterised in ARDIT, as these are the countries where the use cases are run. In addition, tables of the RICA (the Italian FADN) were also characterized.

The Farm Accountancy Data Network (FADN) is an annual sample survey established by the European Economic Commission in 1965, with EEC Regulation 79/56 and updated with EC Regulation 1217/2009 and subsequent amendments and additions. It has been carried out in Italy since 1968 (RICA), with a similar approach in all EU Member States, and represents the only harmonised source of microeconomic data on the evolution of incomes and on the economic and structural dynamics of agricultural holdings³.

The FADN survey does not represent the entire universe of farms surveyed in a given territory, but only those that, due to their economic size, can be considered professional and market-oriented. The methodology adopted aims to provide representative data on three dimensions: region, economic size and technical-economic order.

The more than 86,000 holdings in the Community FADN represent almost 5 million Union holdings, 90% of agricultural area and 90% of Standard Production. The figure below shows the evolution of the Community FADN as a function of EU enlargement. The graph shows the size of the national samples (average figure 2015-2017). The Italian sample came to represent 30% of the EU sample in the 1980s.

Figure 1: Evolution of the Community FADN as a function of EU enlargement.

Currently (average data 2014-2019), the Italian FADN sample is based on a reasoned sample of about 11,000 farms, structured in such a way as to represent the different farming types and sizes present on the national territory. It allows an average national coverage of 95% of the Utilised Agricultural Area, 97% of the value of Standard Production, 92% of Labour Units and 91% of Livestock Units.

In the case of Spain, all the databases that have been used for the participatory research activities of the **Andalusian use case** have been characterised. Not all the data sources identified in

³ <https://rica.crea.gov.it/cos-e-la-rica-725.php>

January 2020 have been characterised because not all of them would be useful for ABM or because of their specificity in the subject matter. Moreover, it was detected that some data sources were duplicated in the list resulting from the first identification and characterisation process, i.e. the same original data was linked from different institutional data portals. The main source of these duplications is the fact that, given the regional nature of Use Case 1, centred on Andalusia, many of the identified data sources are generated by regional agencies, but are then incorporated and aggregated by the Ministry at the national level. In these cases, a single characterisation has been introduced in the ARDIT tool.

The selected databases for the **Greek** use case include relevant national socioeconomic and agricultural themes mainly issued from the Hellenic Statistical Authority (ELSTAT). Their selection was based on the following criteria:

- Relevance of the selected datasets to the research activities conducted to the WP7 and specifically Task 7.2 - Policy Impact Assessment
- Relevance of the selected datasets to the needs for the thorough description of the AGRICORE use cases and the preparation of Deliverable 7.3 - Updated description of the AGRICORE use cases

The selected national databases include the main four themes of agricultural statistics issued by the Hellenic Statistical Authority. The selected databases include the Census of Agricultural and Livestock Holdings, the Greek Farm Structure Survey (FSS), the Greek Annual Agricultural Statistical Survey as well as ELSTAT's Livestock/Crops Surveys.

The **Polish** use case objective was to perform a detailed analysis and impact assessment of the national level measurement M10.1 (agri-environment-climate commitments), the Polish agricultural system in general and specifically the ecosystem services in the country. The selection of the national datasets characterized in ARDIT was determined by the topical scope of the conducted analysis in the Polish Use Case. We focused on including examples of both socioeconomic and climate-environment datasets respectively.

Table 1 below contains all the datasets that have been identified and characterised in the context of Task 1.5, depicting the provider and the location of the dataset in the institutional repository, in terms of the folder and sub-folder.

Table 1: List of characterised National and Regional datasets s within Task T1.5

Dataset Provider	Folder	Sub-Folder/Dataset Name
RICA	Structural characteristics	Data
RICA	Structural characteristics	indices
RICA	Balance sheet	Data
RICA	Balance sheet	indices
RICA	Management results	Data
RICA	Management results	Economic indices
RICA	Management results	Profitability indices
RICA	Sectorial results	Crops
RICA	Sectorial results	Livestock
RICA	Sectorial results	Processed products
Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Alimentation	Spanish Statistics on Means of Production	Use of Fertilisers

Ministry of Agriculture/Junta de Andalucía	NA	Sistema de Identificación Geográfica de Identificación de Parcelas Agrícolas (SIGPAC)
Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Alimentation	NA	ESYRCE (for Spain)
Ministry of Agriculture	NA	FADN for Spain
National Statistics Institute of Spain	NA	Agricultural Census (2009) (for Spain)
Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Alimentation	Spanish Statistics on Means of Production	Commercialisation of Phytosanitary Products
Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Alimentation	Spanish Statistics on Means of Production	Utilisation of Phytosanitary Products
Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Alimentation	Spanish Statistics on Means of Production	Registration of New Machinery
Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Alimentation	Spanish Statistics on Means of Production	Use of Fertilisers
Ministry of Agriculture and Fishing, Alimentation and Environment	National Agricultural Economic Statistics	Short-term prices of agricultural products (for Spain)
Ministry of Agriculture and Fishing, Alimentation and Environment	National Agricultural Economic Statistics	Agricultural rates and salaries (for Spain)
Ministry of Agriculture and Fishing, Alimentation and Environment	National Agricultural Economic Statistics	Agricultural rates and prices received (for Spain)
Ministry of Agriculture and Fishing, Alimentation and Environment	National Agricultural Economic Statistics	Agricultural rates and prices paid (for Spain)
Ministry of Agriculture and Fishing, Alimentation and Environment	National Agricultural Economic Statistics	Average land prices for agricultural use (for Spain)
Ministry of Environment, Rural and Marine Environment	NA	National Soil Erosion Inventory (INES) (for Spain)
Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Rural Development	NA	Climate data obtained by the Agroclimatic Stations Net (for Spain)
Meteorology Statal Agency	NA	Statistics of meterophenological variables (for Spain)
Junta de Andalucía, Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Sustainable Development	NA	Statistics of land prices in Andalusia
Junta de Andalucía, Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Sustainable Development	NA	Information system for organic production in Andalusia (SIPEA) (for Spain)
Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Alimentation	NA	Official Agricultural Machinery Register (ROMA) (for Spain)
Subdirectorate General of Short-term Analysis and Economic Forecasts of the General Directorate of Macroeconomic Analysis	NA	BDSICE Costs and prices Agricultural price index (for Spain)
Subdirectorate General of Short-term Analysis and Economic Forecasts of the General Directorate of Macroeconomic Analysis	NA	BDSICE National production and demand indicators Agriculture (for Spain)
Subdirectorate General of Short-term Analysis and Economic Forecasts of the General Directorate of Macroeconomic Analysis	NA	BDSICE Price and costs Agricultural wage index (for Spain)
Junta de Andalucía. Counseling of Agriculture, Fisheries and Sustainable Development	NA	Agrifood Foreign Trade Statistics
Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Alimentation	NA	Monthly production, movement and stock data (AICA)
Junta de Andalucía, Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Sustainable Development	NA	SIPEA. Information system on organic Production in Andalusia.

ELSTAT	Agriculture, Livestock, Fishery	Livestock Surveys (for Greece)
ELSTAT	Agriculture, Livestock, Fishery	Crops Survey (for Greece)
ELSTAT	Agriculture, Livestock, Fishery	Annual Agricultural Statistical Survey (for Greece)
ELSTAT	Agriculture, Livestock, Fishery	FSS (for Greece)
ELSTAT	Agriculture, Livestock, Fishery	Census of Agricultural and Livestock Holdings 2009 (for Greece)
Eurostat		Labour force by sex, type of the farm and size of the farm (ef_lf_size)
Eurostat	Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries	Training of farm managers
Joint Research Centre	Soil Threads Data	Soil pH in Europe
Local Data Bank	Agriculture	Agricultural holdings
Local Data Bank	Agriculture	Land use
Local Data Bank	Agriculture	Growing of crops Fruits and vegetables
Local Data Bank	Agriculture	Growing of crops crop production
Local Data Bank	Agriculture	Growing of crops consumption of mineral fertilisers
Local Data Bank	Environmental protection	Land surface and soil protection
Local Data Bank	Environmental protection	Nature and biodiversity protection
Local Data Bank	Environmental protection	Usable underground water resources
Local Data Bank	Forestry and hunting	Forest environment: threats and protection
Local Data Bank	Forestry and hunting	Economic exploitation of forest
Local Data Bank	Forestry and hunting	Forestry of all forms of ownership
Institute of Soil Science and Plants Cultivation State Research Institute	Agricultural Drought Monitoring System	

3.1 Characterisation within the project duration

During Task 1.1, project partners performed an initial characterisation of a number of datasets (listed in the table in Selection of Datasets Characterised so Far of D1.1) to identify the information that had to be captured by the ARDIT ontology and defined the necessary information required for further characterisation in ARDIT.

Consequently, the ARDIT backend was organised in 7 sections:

1. One **GENERAL** section where information such as the name of the table, the description, the type of dataset, the producer, issue date and last update ... are captured. In this category, the user can indicate the catalogue to which the dataset belongs (EUROSTAT, FAO, OECD, etc ...). Spatial resolution is a characteristic dedicated to geo-referenced datasets to depict the minimum spatial separation resolvable in a dataset, measured in meters, while the temporal resolution is intended to provide a summary indication of the temporal resolution of the data

distribution as a single value. More complex descriptions of various aspects of temporal precision, accuracy, resolution and other statistics can be provided using the Data Quality Vocabulary [VOCAB-DQV]⁴. In this section, we can also find the activities that generated or provided the business context for the creation of the dataset ("Was generated by"). An activity is something that occurs over a period of time and acts upon or with entities; it may include consuming, processing, transforming, modifying, relocating, using, or generating entities. The activity associated with the generation of a dataset will typically be an initiative, project, mission, survey, ongoing activity ("business as usual") etc.

Ultimately, if the dataset is cited in the literature, or on other datasets or used by some other related resources, such as publications, etc., this information can be depicted in the field "Is referenced by".

2. The second section is dedicated to the **PURPOSE** of the dataset, and define what kind of analysis the dataset was created for. The purpose property has been added in the AGRICORE ontology and it identifies the purpose of the dataset, i.e., for what kind of analysis that dataset has been created: there is an internal vocabulary of terms that will be enriched over time. In this section, we find information on the temporal extent of the data collection period, on the object of the dataset (i.e., the type of data that has been analysed and represented), on the purposes of the dataset and the data, and on the theme covered (derived from DCAT-AP).
3. The **GEOGRAPHICAL COVERAGE** section depicts the geographic features of a dataset. It's a spatial property. It's a list of spatial regions or named places. It can be represented using a controlled vocabulary or with geographic coordinates.
4. The **DISTRIBUTION** of a data set is the format in which the data can be retrieved. A dataset might be available in multiple formats, such as spreadsheet, pdf, CSV, etc. This section, besides information on the title, issue date and description, collects all data on access rights, byte size, procedures to access the data, URL and format.
5. The **UNIT OF ANALYSIS (UoA)** is the object to which the variables are referred. Every dataset has at least one UoA, but in one dataset there could be more than one UoA. The UoA is generally something spatially defined, such as the holdings, a region or a country, but it can also be something different such as a commodity. While defining a new Unit of Analysis, the following information will be captured: the temporal extent (that could have a different value from the one of the datasets), the aggregation level, unit or scale, whether the dataset is a census, the population coverage if not a census, the statistical representativeness or the number of elements in the sample (if known) and the downscaling strategy (if any).
6. Once the UoA has been created, the related variables are characterised by the introduction of the following properties: unit of measurement, temporal extent, mathematical representation, data frequency, aggregation level and the UoA to which the variable refers. In the case of price variables, currency, price type and size unit will be depicted as well.
7. In ARDIT there is also a section to list the **KEYWORDS** describing or representing the dataset.

Table 2 below depicts the list of fields to be filled while characterising a dataset in ARDIT.

⁴ https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-2/#Property:dataset_temporal_resolution

Table 2: Template for the ARDIT Dataset Characterisation (Methodological Grid)

Characteristic captured and presented in ARDIT	Explanation/Example
GENERAL	This section regards general information and characteristics about the dataset.
Title	Name or identifier of the dataset.
Description	Short description of the dataset, its purpose or the type of data collected.
Issued	Indicates the date of the first formal issuance or publication of the specific dataset.
Last update	Indicates the most recent date on which the dataset was changed, updated or modified.
Dataset type	A dataset can be either geo-referenced or socioeconomic. The dataset type is usually determined by the type of its Units of Analysis or the type of its variables.
Producer	Indicates the institution/organisation which generated, published or maintains the dataset.
Link	Provides an URL to the landing page of the described dataset.
Language	Indicates the original language in which the data and metadata are available
Periodicity of the publication	Indicates the frequency with which the data (variables) is updated (between one issue and the following one).
Catalogues	Indicates the catalogue to which the dataset belongs (if any).
Temporal resolution	Indicates the shortest period of time between two consecutive samples of any of the variables contained within the dataset.
Spatial resolution	(Only for geo-referenced datasets) Indicates the smallest resolvable spatial separation (measured in metres) between neighbouring Units of Analysis, and thus between their corresponding geo-referenced variables.
Resource type	Indicates the nature or genre of the resource (e.g. collection, interactive resource)
Was generated by	Indicates the activities that generated or provided the business context for the creation of the dataset.
Is referenced by	Indicates other datasets or scientific publications that cite or (re)use data contained in the dataset being described.
PURPOSE	This section depicts what kind of analysis the dataset was created for.
Temporal extent	Indicates the time period for which data are available.
Subjects	Indicates the topics covered by the dataset.
Useful for the analysis of (purpose)	Indicates which types of analysis could be performed using the data contained in the dataset's variables.
Theme covered	Indicates the themes covered by the dataset.
GEOGRAPHICAL COVERAGE	This section describes the geographical scope of the dataset. It is therefore a property describing a particular physical or administrative spatial entity. It is possible to describe the geographical coverage using several alternatives (but only one of them at a time): list with 1+ physical continents <i>OR</i> list with 1+ countries <i>OR</i> list with 1+ NUTS1 entities <i>OR</i> list with 1+ NUTS2 entities <i>OR</i> list with 1+ NUTS3 entities <i>OR</i> list with 1+ ADM1 geo-entities <i>OR</i> list with 1+ ADM2 geo-entities. In future releases, it will be also possible to use a coordinates box for this.
DISTRIBUTIONS	The distributions of a dataset are the set of different formats/shapes in which the data can be retrieved. (e.g. pdf, CSV)
License	Indicates the legal framework under which the distribution is made available
Access right	Indicates a declaration on the rights that concerns how the distribution is accessed. (e.g. public, restricted)
Byte size	Indicates the memory size required to store the data contained in the dataset.
Procedures to access the data	Describes the guidelines and procedures required for accessing private datasets.
Access URL	Indicates the URL from where the data contained in the dataset can be accessed.
Download URL	Indicates the URL of the downloadable file in a given format (if exists).
Format	Indicates the file format of the raw data file (e.g. xls, csv, html, pc).
Compress format	Indicate the compression format (if any) of the downloadable file in which the data is contained.

Packaging format	Indicates the packaging format of the distribution when several data files are grouped together.
Data service	Indicates the data service that gives access to the distribution of the dataset.
Publisher	The entity responsible for making the data service available.
Creator	The entity responsible for producing the data service.
UNIT OF ANALYSIS	It's the object to which the variables refer. Every dataset has at least one UoA.
Area size	(Only for geo-referenced datasets) Indicates the spatial magnitude of the unit of analysis.
Area size unit	(Only for geo-referenced datasets) Indicates the physical unit corresponding to the magnitude of area size of the UoA.
Aggregation Level	Number of Units of Analysis for which the data is aggregated / Area size for which the Units of Analysis are aggregated.
Aggregation Level Unit	Political-Administrative or physical unit of the aggregation level (e.g. the Unit of Analysis can be the Agricultural Holdings, whose results are aggregated at a national (country) level).
Census	Boolean property that indicates whether the dataset is a census (100% of Units of Analysis were polled to gather the data).
Population coverage	Indicates (when known) the proportion of Units of Analysis sampled with respect to the size of the total population of Units of Analysis. Could be either a float between 0 and 1 or a percentage between 0 and 100.
Unit of analysis number	Indicates the total number of Units of Analysis that form the sample.
Statistical representativeness	Provides information on how the sample was built. It is a value between 0 and 1 that refers to what percentage of the total real population of units of analysis is represented by the sample used to generate the dataset.
Available stratification criteria & suggested downscaling methodologies	Indicates which additional stratification levels are resolvable within the dataset (i.e. the criteria to filter among Units of Analysis and their possible values). Additionally, for data available at higher (geographical or administrative) scale levels, methodologies can be suggested to generate data at smaller scales.
VARIABLES INCLUDED	It lists all the variables contained within the dataset. Those variables can be geo-referenced or socioeconomic, depending on the dataset and Unit of Analysis types.
Name	Identifier of the variable.
Unit of Measurement	Physical unit in which the variable is displayed.
Temporal extent	Indicates the time period for which data are available. Normally it has the same value as the dataset's temporal extent, but it might be also different (shorter) for some variables.
Mathematical representation	Indicates whether the value of the variable is an instantaneous value, or an extreme value (maximum, minimum), or the average of several values, etc.
Data frequency	To indicate the frequency with which data are collected and processed during the "temporal extent". (e.g.: dataset with two variables for temperature, one is the monthly average, another one is the maximum annual temperature)
Aggregation level	To indicate the spatial units of the data (e. g., NUTS1, NUTS2, NUTS3 or other administrative regions/units, 50000 (e.g., 1:50000 scale map), 0.25 degrees). It refers to the level of detail of the data set/ analysis. It shall be expressed as a set of zero to many resolution distances (typically for gridded data and imagery-derived products) or equivalent scales (typically for maps or map-derived products).
Data origin	Indicates whether the values of the variable have been obtained by actual physical measurements or surveys (measured), <i>OR</i> by qualitative observation (observed), <i>OR</i> by calculations on other raw variables (calculated), <i>OR</i> are predictions obtained using models or other forecasting techniques (forecast).
Reference Values	Sometimes variables are coded (or modified) using value identifiers generated by the dataset producers themselves. This property may include such codes and their meaning (or their modifying value) in natural language.
Unit of analysis	Indicates the UoA the variable is related to.
KEYWORDS	This section is to indicate the keywords regarding the dataset.

In this framework, STAM took care of keeping updated the ontology, while IDENER of communicating the required changes and adaptations both to the ARDIT developers and to the data providers (people performing the characterisations). UNIPR was in charge of the characterisation of the socioeconomic datasets, STAM was in charge of the characterisation of the geo-referenced datasets and IDENER took the role of supervisor and reviewer of the work done.

The list of datasets characterised in the context of this deliverable could be updated throughout the project period to address any additional need identified by the project modellers.

An iterative approach will allow maturing the governance structure aiming for its maintenance after the project finalisation. In the current stage, the AGRICORE partners have established that for each dataset to be included in the platform, a reviewer of the quality of its characterisation is defined.

During the project, an extensive list of characterization of the required datasets has been already produced. Nonetheless, as coordinator of the project, IDENER will be in charge of monitoring any additional data characterisation need identifying within the execution of the UCs. Any additional need will be notified by the UC responsible to the coordinator and the actions required to tackle it.

Finally, a special committee formed by representatives of STAM, UNIPR and IDENER will be formed. This Committee will be tasked with the continuous monitoring of the characterisation process, identifying the relevant aspects that may require a modification of the current ontology.

3.2 Characterisation challenges

One of the first issues addressed in the characterisation of the national and regional dataset, was the decision on the language to be used, as these datasets are mostly in the local language and translating information into English could have been not fully accurate. Thus considering that also non-local researchers or policymakers could be potentially interested in that information, it has been agreed to translate everything into English. However, in some cases (e.g. RICA tables), we also kept the local language description of the variables in between brackets, to avoid confusion, providing that there is no correspondence in the codes (RICA/FADN), as explained below.

Since for the Italian FADN, the RICA, the microdata is private, it was decided to characterise the reports, which nevertheless contain aggregated data. The difficulty was in the characterisation of the variables because unlike most other national FADNs, the RICA does not use the same SY/SE nomenclature, but a slightly different aggregation methodology that makes it difficult to compare the data with other national FADNs.

Some of the datasets characterised for the Andalusian use case contain a lot of organised information with a different variable structure, which is why some of them have had to be differentiated as separate datasets. For example, the Agricultural Census database has been subdivided into 56 different datasets.

The experience in ARDIT has been satisfactory and has been improving with each of the modifications it has undergone subsequently, there are still some aspects to improve, such as the fact that there is no "warning notification" of the modifications that are going to be made, or tools such as "undo" that by mistake you may have made a modification or elimination of some database that was not foreseen.

The main challenge encountered during the characterisation of the Greek dataset was the irregularity of the statistics period publication. Even if most of the databases are characterised as "annual" or "a census", the actual available data are published at irregular intervals or the

statistics presented to the relevant websites are lacking recent updates. Furthermore, several datasets characteristics are attributed differently in the Greek and English languages, thus creating shortcomings for the completion of the proper characterisation.

3.3 Characterisation after the project

Upon completing the activities of the AGRICORE project and having published the ARDIT on the public internet, researchers interested in using and contributing to the tool with the characterisation of new datasets will be able to do so by means of the same functionality employed by project partners in the lifetime of the project. It is obvious that for ensuring the survival of the developed portal, a continuous upgrade and maintenance of the data included should be promoted. To do so, a clear governance structure should be defined.

Although the final version of such governance will be established later in the project (as this relies on the activities pertaining to other WPs and tasks, such as WP8, Exploitation, clustering and open sourcing, and WP9 with the PEDR and DMP), an initial potential governance structure is already under discussion.

The ARDIT tool will be developed to include a Datasource life cycle management system. This system, among other things, will establish a set of roles within the platform which will be linked to specific responsibilities. The corresponding roles will be defined within the project by both AAT and IDENER and the people assigned with them will be identified; initially within the personnel of such companies. However, project activities already include efforts to increase the adoption and interest in the project tools (including ARDIT) and external requests from potential contributors are expected.

4 Conclusion

Agricultural research and agricultural policy impact assessment is normally supported by the analysis of several datasets with different characteristics and their own complexity. Some datasets are statistically oriented (such as Eurostat), following the evolution of statistical macroeconomics phenomena by giving a structural or cognitive overview. They might be used to make a forecast analysis (ex-ante analysis) or a policy evaluation (ex-post). Some other datasets are policy-oriented (such as FADN), providing specific information for policymakers and for specific policy sectors (fisheries, environment, agriculture etc.) Such datasets can be implemented by governments or international organisations oriented towards specific objectives, such as the fight against world hunger, rural development, etc. Therefore, datasets are created for a specific purpose and follow specific generation methodologies. A dataset must allow researchers to obtain information in the most efficient way, timely and functionally. To that end, it should contain those variables that are most common or most widely used, using appropriate units of analysis and standardised units of measurement. But it should also ensure that the information on these and other characteristics (the dataset metadata) is publicly available and easily interpretable by researchers during the phase of identifying and searching for relevant data. The tools to reach this objective are the ontologies, which allow a common way of conceptualising the characteristics of datasets, allowing easy extraction of metadata and grouping of datasets with similar properties. The quality and usefulness of these datasets descriptions depend on the quality and efficiency of the ontologies used by researchers as a basis to characterise them.

In the scope of the AGRICORE project, a new dedicated ontology (AGRICORE DCAT 2.0) was designed to capture the information needed down to the level of the variables. This ontology constitutes the base for the structural design of the Agricultural Research Data Index Tool (ARDIT), a web-based tool that allows the characterisation of agricultural datasets and their subsequent search and query.

As part of Task T1.5 of the AGRICORE project, 56 datasets have been described using ARDIT, namely 26 for Spain, 10 from the RICA (Italy), 8 for Greece and 11 for Poland. These characterisations have been included as an ANNEX to this deliverable. Additionally, the [JSON file](#) containing all the characterisations corresponding to tasks T1.3, T1.4, T1.5 and T1.6 of the AGRICORE Project has been uploaded to ZENODO⁵.

Characterisations of datasets are the result of human-made decision processes based on human-designed ontologies. Therefore, every characterisation is a dynamic outcome subject to modifications, either because someone else suggests a better way of describing some of its properties using the ontology, or because the ontology itself undergoes modifications to improve the way of describing certain characteristic(s). Therefore, there must be an overall process management approach to ensure the quality of the resulting products (the characterisations), i.e. the ability to keep useful and accurate information about the datasets and to access it easily and quickly. The former will be included as part of the ARDIT design to be submitted in M31. Furthermore, a governance structure for the ARDIT itself is important to guarantee the quality of the characterisation procedures during the project phase, but also to ensure proper management, information provisioning and tool maintenance in the future post-project stage.

⁵ [Zenodo](#) is a general purpose open access repository developed under the European OpenAIRE programme and operated by CERN.

5 References

[1]^E. Alatrish, "Comparison Some of Ontology Editors," Management Information Systems, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 18–24, 2013, [Online].

Available:

<https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/bdf8/056feec90b60c338d3818a20e17c4b199458.pdf? ga=2.36105125.422640853.1595319726-1671690332.1587569242>

For preparing this report, the following deliverables have been taken into consideration:

Deliverable Number	Deliverable Title	Lead beneficiary	Type	Dissemination Level	Due date
D1.1	Standardised Methodology and Set of Ontologies for the Characterisation of Data Sources	UNIPR	Report	Public	M09
D1.3	EU statistics datasets	STAM	Report	Public	M29
D1.4	Geo-referenced datasets	UNIPR	Report	Public	M29
D1.6	Previous research results as information sources	UNIPR	Report	Public	M29

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National Agricultural Economic Statistics: Average land prices for Agricultural use

General information

Description: The main objective is to measure the annual evolution of the land classes price level. The importance of this survey lies in its multiple uses, including serving as a reference in the operations related to purchase-sale transactions, valuations for expropriations, taxes, etc.

Producer: Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food

Link: <https://www.mapa.gob.es/es/estadistica/temas/estadisticas-agrarias/economia/encuesta-precios-tierra/>

Languages: Spanish | Castilian

Catalogue:

Subjects: agricultural economics

Useful for the analysis of: Agricultural costs

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution:

Resource type:

Was generated by: Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: ES11, ES12, ES13, ES21, ES22, ES23, ES24, ES30, ES41, ES42, ES43, ES51, ES52, ES53, ES61, ES62, ES70

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: December 22, 2021

Characterization created at: December 20, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2002

Last update: December 31, 2020

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 1998 - December, 2020

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Land price for agricultural use	Excel XLS	Public	https://www.mapa.gob.es/es/estadistica/temas/estadisticas-agrarias/economia/enquesta-precios-tierra/	Excel XLS	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
National average prices by Crop - Use of land	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Country		
Evolution of land prices	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Country	100	
National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Country		
Price of rainfed arable crops plus fallow land.	January, 1998 - December, 2020	NUTS2		
Evolution of the Price Index: Analysis by Autonomous Communities.	January, 1998 - December, 2020	NUTS2		

Price of irrigated arable crops.	January, 1998 - December, 2020	NUTS2		
Precio de los Frutales de fruto seco en secano.	January, 1998 - December, 2020	NUTS2		
Price of Citrus (irrigated).	January, 1998 - December, 2020	NUTS2		
Price of dry-farmed wine grapes.	January, 1998 - December, 2020	NUTS2		
Price of the Olive of oil mill in dry land.	January, 1998 - December, 2020	NUTS2		
National average prices by Autonomous Communities	January, 1998 - December, 2020	NUTS2		
National average prices by type of land (typologies) and Autonomous Regions	January, 1998 - December, 2020	NUTS2		
Evolution of the Price Index: Analysis by Crop - Use.	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Country		
Evolution of the Price Index: Analysis by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops.	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Country		
Price of the Uses (permanent meadows and prairies (dry/irrigated) and other surfaces for pasture).	January, 1998 - December, 2020	NUTS2		

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Prices: Fruit trees:	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land

Temperate climate rainfed						
Price change (€/ha): Fruit trees: Temperate climate rainfed	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Price change (%): Fruit trees: Temperate climate rainfed	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Impact: Fruit trees: Temperate climate rainfed	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Weightings Base: Fruit trees: temperate climate rainfed	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Prices: Fruit trees: Irrigated temperate climate	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Price change (€/ha): Fruit trees: Irrigated temperate climate	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Price change (%): Fruit trees: Irrigated temperate climate	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land

Impact: Fruit trees: Irrigated temperate climate	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Weightings Base: Fruit trees: Irrigated temperate climate	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Price change (%): Fruit trees: Dry subtropical climate	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Impact: Fruit trees: Dry subtropical climate	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Weightings Base: Fruit trees: Dry subtropical climate	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Price change (€/ha): Fruit trees: Dry subtropical climate	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Prices: Fruit trees: Dry subtropical climate	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Price change (%): Fruit trees: Irrigated	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land

subtropical climate						
Impact: Fruit trees: Irrigated subtropical climate	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Weightings Base: Fruit trees: Irrigated subtropical climate	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Price change (€/ha): Fruit trees: Irrigated subtropical climate	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Prices: Fruit trees: Irrigated subtropical climate	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Current prices (€/ha)	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	Evolution of land prices
Current prices (Index)	Socioeconomic variable	Index	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	Evolution of land prices
Current prices (% year-on-year change)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	Evolution of land prices
Prices: Fruit trees: Dry temperate climate	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land

Price change (€/ha): Dry temperate climate	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Price change (%): Dry temperate climate	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Impact: Dry temperate climate	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Weightings Base: Dry temperate climate	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Prices: Vineyard	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Price change (€/ha): Vineyard	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Price change (%): Vineyard	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Impact: Vineyard.	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Weightings Base: Vineyard	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land

Prices: Table grapes and sultanas dry	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Price change (€/ha): Table grapes and sultanas dry	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Price change (%): Table grapes and sultanas dry	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Prices: Fruit trees: Dry-farmed dry fruit	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Price change (€/ha): Fruit trees: Dry-farmed dry fruit	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Price change (%): Fruit trees: Dry-farmed dry fruit	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Impact: Fruit trees: Dry-farmed dry fruit	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Weightings Base: Fruit trees: Dry-farmed dry fruit	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Prices: Fruit trees: Dry fruit irrigated	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land

GDP deflator (Index)	Socioeconomic variable	Index	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	Evolution of land prices
GDP deflator (% year-on-year change)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	Evolution of land prices
Constant prices (€/ha)	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	Evolution of land prices
Constant prices (Index)	Socioeconomic variable	Index	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	Evolution of land prices
Constant prices (% year-on-year change)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	Evolution of land prices
Price change (€/ha): Fruit trees: Dry fruit irrigated	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Prices: Arable and fallow land: Rainfed	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Price change (€/ha): Arable and fallow land: Rainfed	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Price change (%): Arable and fallow land: Rainfed	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Impact: Arable and fallow land: Rainfed	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land

Weightings Base: Arable and fallow land: Rainfed	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Prices: Arable and fallow land: Irrigated	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Price change (€/ha): Arable and fallow land: Irrigated	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Price change (%): Arable and fallow land: Irrigated	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Impact: Arable and fallow land: Irrigated	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Weightings Base: Arable and fallow land: Irrigated	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Prices: Open-air vegetables irrigated	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Price change (€/ha): Open-air vegetables irrigated	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Price change (%): Open-air	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land

vegetables irrigated						
Impact: Open-air vegetables irrigated	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Weightings Base: Open-air vegetables irrigated	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Prices: Greenhouse vegetables irrigated	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Price change (€/ha): Greenhouse vegetables irrigated	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Price change (%): Greenhouse vegetables irrigated	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Impact: Greenhouse vegetables irrigated	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Weightings Base: Greenhouse vegetables irrigated	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land

Prices: Rice	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Price change (€/ha): Rice	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Price change (%): Rice	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Impact: Rice	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Weightings Base: Rice	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Prices: Citrus irrigated	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Price change (€/ha): Citrus irrigated	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Price change (%): Citrus irrigated	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Impact: Citrus irrigated	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Weightings Base: Citrus irrigated	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land

Price change (%): Fruit trees: Dry fruit irrigated	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Impact: Fruit trees: Dry fruit irrigated	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Weightings Base: Fruit trees: Dry fruit irrigated	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Prices: Wine grapes rainfed	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Price change (€/ha): Wine grapes rainfed	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Price change (%): Wine grapes rainfed	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Impact: Wine grapes rainfed	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Weightings Base: Wine grapes rainfed	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Prices: Irrigated wine grapes	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops
Impact: Table grapes and sultanas dry	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops

Weightings Base: Table grapes and sultanas dry	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops
Prices: Table grapes and sultanas irrigated	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Price change (€/ha): Table grapes and sultanas irrigated	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Price change (%): Table grapes and sultanas irrigated	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Impact: Table grapes and sultanas irrigated	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Weightings Base: Table grapes and sultanas irrigated	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Price change (€/ha): Irrigated wine grapes	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Price change (%): Irrigated wine grapes	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land

Impact: Irrigated wine grapes	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Weightings Base: Irrigated wine grapes	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Prices: Olive grove: Table olives rainfed	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Price change (€/ha): Olive grove: Table olives rainfed	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Price change (%): Olive grove: Table olives rainfed	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Impact: Olive grove: Table olives rainfed	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Weightings Base: Olive grove: Table olives rainfed	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Prices: Olive grove: Table olives irrigated	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Price change (€/ha): Olive grove: Table olives irrigated	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land

Price change (%): Olive grove: Table olives irrigated	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Impact: Olive grove: Table olives irrigated	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Weightings Base: Olive grove: Table olives irrigated	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Prices: Olive grove: Olive oil mill olives dry land	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Price change (€/ha): Olive grove: Olive oil mill olives dry land	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Price change (%): Olive grove: Olive oil mill olives dry land	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Impact: Olive grove: Olive oil mill olives dry land	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Weightings Base: Olive grove: Olive oil mill olives dry land	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land

Prices: Olive grove: Irrigated olive oil mill olives	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Prices: USES	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Price change (€/ha): Olive grove: Irrigated olive oil mill olives	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Price change (%): Olive grove: Irrigated olive oil mill olives	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Impact: Olive grove: Irrigated olive oil mill olives	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Weightings Base: Olive grove: Irrigated olive oil mill olives	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Price change (€/ha): USES	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Price change (%): USES	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land

Impact: USES	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Weightings Base: USES	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Prices: GENERAL	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Price change (€/ha): GENERAL	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Price change (%): GENERAL	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Impact: GENERAL	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Weightings Base: GENERAL	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops, National average prices by Crop - Use of land
Prices	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Autonomous Communities, Evolution of the Price Index: Analysis by Autonomous Communities., Price of rainfed arable crops plus fallow land., Price of irrigated arable crops., Price of Citrus (irrigated), Price of dry-farmed wine grapes., Price of the Olive of oil mill in dry land. , Price of the Uses (permanent meadows and prairies (dry/irrigated) and other surfaces for pasture)., Precio de los Frutales de fruto seco en secano.

Price change (€/ha)	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Autonomous Communities, Evolution of the Price Index: Analysis by Autonomous Communities, Price of rainfed arable crops plus fallow land., Price of irrigated arable crops., Price of Citrus (irrigated), Price of dry-farmed wine grapes., Price of the Olive of oil mill in dry land. , Price of the Uses (permanent meadows and prairies (dry/irrigated) and other surfaces for pasture), Precio de los Frutales de fruto seco en secano.
Price change (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Autonomous Communities, Evolution of the Price Index: Analysis by Autonomous Communities, Price of rainfed arable crops plus fallow land., Price of irrigated arable crops., Price of Citrus (irrigated), Price of dry-farmed wine grapes., Price of the Olive of oil mill in dry land. , Price of the Uses (permanent meadows and prairies (dry/irrigated) and other surfaces for pasture), Precio de los Frutales de fruto seco en secano.
Impact	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Autonomous Communities, Evolution of the Price Index: Analysis by Autonomous Communities, Price of rainfed arable crops plus fallow land., Price of irrigated arable crops., Price of Citrus (irrigated), Price of dry-farmed wine grapes., Price of the Olive of oil mill in dry land. , Price of the Uses (permanent meadows and prairies (dry/irrigated) and other surfaces for

						pasture), Precio de los Frutales de fruto seco en secano.
Weightings Base	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by Autonomous Communities, Evolution of the Price Index: Analysis by Autonomous Communities., Price of rainfed arable crops plus fallow land., Price of irrigated arable crops., Price of Citrus (irrigated), Price of dry-farmed wine grapes., Price of the Olive of oil mill in dry land. , Price of the Uses (permanent meadows and prairies (dry/irrigated) and other surfaces for pasture), Precio de los Frutales de fruto seco en secano.
Prices: Herbaceous+Red land (42.6% of UAA)	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by type of land (typologies) and Autonomous Regions
Price change (€/ha): Herbaceous+Red land (42.6% of UAA)	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by type of land (typologies) and Autonomous Regions
Price change (%): Herbaceous+Red land (42.6% of UAA)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by type of land (typologies) and Autonomous Regions
Impact: Herbaceous+Red land (42.6% of UAA)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by type of land (typologies) and Autonomous Regions

Weightings Base: Herbaceous+Red land (42.6% of UAA)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by type of land (typologies) and Autonomous Regions
Prices: Irrigated arable crops (6.2% of the UAA)	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by type of land (typologies) and Autonomous Regions
Price change (€/ha): Irrigated arable crops (6.2% of the UAA)	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by type of land (typologies) and Autonomous Regions
Price change (%): Irrigated arable crops (6.2% of the UAA)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by type of land (typologies) and Autonomous Regions
Impact: Irrigated arable crops (6.2% of the UAA)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by type of land (typologies) and Autonomous Regions
Weightings Base: Irrigated arable crops (6.2% of the UAA)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by type of land (typologies) and Autonomous Regions
Prices: Non- irrigated wine grapes (2.5% of UAA)	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by type of land (typologies) and Autonomous Regions

Price change (€/ha): Non-irrigated wine grapes (2.5% of UAA)	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by type of land (typologies) and Autonomous Regions
Price change (%): Non-irrigated wine grapes (2.5% of UAA)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by type of land (typologies) and Autonomous Regions
Impact: Non-irrigated wine grapes (2.5% of UAA)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by type of land (typologies) and Autonomous Regions
Weightings Base: Non-irrigated wine grapes (2.5% of UAA)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by type of land (typologies) and Autonomous Regions
Prices: Dry-farmed olives (7.0% of the UAA)	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by type of land (typologies) and Autonomous Regions
Price change (€/ha): Dry-farmed olives (7.0% of the UAA)	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by type of land (typologies) and Autonomous Regions
Price change (%): Dry-farmed olives (7.0% of the UAA)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by type of land (typologies) and Autonomous Regions

Impact: Dry-farmed olives (7.0% of the UAA)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by type of land (typologies) and Autonomous Regions
Weightings Base: Dry-farmed olives (7.0% of the UAA)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by type of land (typologies) and Autonomous Regions
Prices: Utilisation (permanent meadows and pastures and other grazing land) (32.8% of the UAA)	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by type of land (typologies) and Autonomous Regions
Price change (€/ha): Utilisation (permanent meadows and pastures and other grazing land) (32.8% of the UAA)	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by type of land (typologies) and Autonomous Regions
Price change (%): Utilisation (permanent meadows and pastures and other grazing land) (32.8% of the UAA)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by type of land (typologies) and Autonomous Regions

Impact: Utilisation (permanent meadows and pastures and other grazing land) (32.8% of the UAA)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by type of land (typologies) and Autonomous Regions
Weightings Base: Utilisation (permanent meadows and pastures and other grazing land) (32.8% of the UAA)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	National average prices by type of land (typologies) and Autonomous Regions
Evolution of price index: RAINFED CROPS: Rainfed fruit trees	Socioeconomic variable	Index	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	Evolution of the Price Index: Analysis by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops.
Evolution of price index: RAINFED CROPS: Dryland vineyards	Socioeconomic variable	Index	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	Evolution of the Price Index: Analysis by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops.
Evolution of price index: RAINFED CROPS: Dry land olive groves	Socioeconomic variable	Index	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	Evolution of the Price Index: Analysis by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops.
Evolution of price index:	Socioeconomic variable	Index	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	Evolution of the Price Index: Analysis by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops.

IRRIGATED CROPS						
Evolution of price index: IRRIGATED CROPS: Irrigated arable crops	Socioeconomic variable	Index	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	Evolution of the Price Index: Analysis by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops.
Evolution of price index: IRRIGATED CROPS: Vegetables irrigated outdoor vegetables	Socioeconomic variable	Index	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	Evolution of the Price Index: Analysis by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops.
Evolution of price index: IRRIGATED CROPS: Irrigated greenhouse vegetables	Socioeconomic variable	Index	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	Evolution of the Price Index: Analysis by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops.
Evolution of price index: IRRIGATED CROPS: Rice	Socioeconomic variable	Index	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	Evolution of the Price Index: Analysis by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops.
Evolution of price index: CROP	Socioeconomic variable	Index	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	Evolution of the Price Index: Analysis by Crop - Use.
Evolution of price index: CROP: Rainfed arable and fallow crops	Socioeconomic variable	Index	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	Evolution of the Price Index: Analysis by Crop - Use.

Evolution of price index: CROP: Irrigated arable crops	Socioeconomic variable	Index	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	Evolution of the Price Index: Analysis by Crop - Use.
Evolution of price index: CROP: Irrigated open-air vegetables	Socioeconomic variable	Index	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	Evolution of the Price Index: Analysis by Crop - Use.
Evolution of price index: CROP: Irrigated greenhouse vegetables	Socioeconomic variable	Index	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	Evolution of the Price Index: Analysis by Crop - Use.
Evolution of price index: CROP: Rice	Socioeconomic variable	Index	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	Evolution of the Price Index: Analysis by Crop - Use.
Evolution of price index: CROP: Citrus irrigated	Socioeconomic variable	Index	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	Evolution of the Price Index: Analysis by Crop - Use.
Evolution of price index: CROP: Vineyard	Socioeconomic variable	Index	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	Evolution of the Price Index: Analysis by Crop - Use.
Evolution of price index: CROP: Olive groves	Socioeconomic variable	Index	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	Evolution of the Price Index: Analysis by Crop - Use.
Evolution of price index: CROP: Fruit trees	Socioeconomic variable	Index	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	Evolution of the Price Index: Analysis by Crop - Use.

Evolution of price index: USES	Socioeconomic variable	Index	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	Evolution of the Price Index: Analysis by Crop - Use., Evolution of the Price Index: Analysis by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops.
Evolution of price index: RAINFED CROPS	Socioeconomic variable	Index	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	Evolution of the Price Index: Analysis by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops.
Evolution of price index: RAINFED CROPS: Rainfed arable and fallow crops	Socioeconomic variable	Index	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	Evolution of the Price Index: Analysis by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops.
Evolution of price index: IRRIGATED CROPS: Irrigated citrus	Socioeconomic variable	Index	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	Evolution of the Price Index: Analysis by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops.
Evolution of price index: IRRIGATED CROPS: Irrigated fruit trees	Socioeconomic variable	Index	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	Evolution of the Price Index: Analysis by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops.
Evolution of price index: IRRIGATED CROPS: Irrigated vineyard	Socioeconomic variable	Index	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	Evolution of the Price Index: Analysis by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops.
Evolution of price index: IRRIGATED CROPS: Irrigated olive groves	Socioeconomic variable	Index	January, 1998 - December, 2020	Average	Annual	Evolution of the Price Index: Analysis by Rainfed Crops - Irrigated Crops.

Production, movement and stock data (AICA): Olive grove sector

General information

Description: The data includes the main indicators related to the production and transformation of olives, as well as internal marketing and exports. This data is used by AICA to develop its functions, supervising, managing and maintaining the information system of the olive market

Producer: Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food

Link: https://www.mapa.gob.es/es/agricultura/temas/producciones-agricolas/aceite-oliva-y-aceituna-mesa/Datos_produccion_movimiento_existencias_AICA.aspx

Languages: Spanish | Castilian

Catalogue:

Subjects: crop production, olive oil, stock exchange

Useful for the analysis of: Agricultural costs

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Monthly

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Spain

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 14, 2022

Characterization created at: December 16, 2021

Issued: October 31, 2016

Last update: May 31, 2021

Periodicity: Monthly

Temporal extent: October, 2016 - May, 2021

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Production, movement and stock data of olive grove	PDF	Public	https://www.mapa.gob.es/es/agricultura/temas/producciones-agricolas/aceite-oliva-y-aceituna-mesa/Datos_produccion_movimiento_existencias_AICA.aspx	PDF	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Olive grove	October, 2016 - May, 2021	Country		
Olive grove (Comparison)	October, 2016 - May, 2021	Country	100	
Olive grove (Accumulated)	October, 2016 - May, 2021	Country	100	
Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): MANZANILLA	October, 2016 - May, 2021	Country	100	
Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): GORDAL	October, 2016 - May, 2021	Country	100	
Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): HOJIBLANCA	October, 2016 - May, 2021	Country		
Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): CACEREÑA	October, 2016 - May, 2021	Country	100	

Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): OTHERS	October, 2016 - May, 2021	Country	100	
Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): TOTAL	October, 2016 - May, 2021	Country	100	
Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): CARRASQUEÑA	October, 2016 - May, 2021	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
National stock balance (Production)	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand tons	October, 2016 - May, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Olive grove
National stock balance (Import)	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand tons	October, 2016 - May, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Olive grove
National stock balance (Export)	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand tons	October, 2016 - May, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Olive grove
National stock balance (Final stock)	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand tons	October, 2016 - May, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Olive grove
National stock balance (Exports to Italy)	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand tons	October, 2016 - May, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Olive grove
National stock balance (Exports to Other countries)	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand tons	October, 2016 - May, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Olive grove

National stock balance (Imports to Italy)	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand tons	October, 2016 - May, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Olive grove
National stock balance (Imports to Other countries)	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand tons	October, 2016 - May, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Olive grove
Aparental total internal market (Sales, ANIERAC)	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand tons	October, 2016 - May, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Olive grove
Aparental total internal market (Other exits and loses)	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand tons	October, 2016 - May, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Olive grove
Aparental total internal market (Export)	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand tons	October, 2016 - May, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Olive grove
Stock (Oil mill)	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand tons	October, 2016 - May, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Olive grove
Stock (Heritage)	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand tons	October, 2016 - May, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Olive grove
Stock (Operators packing machines)	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand tons	October, 2016 - May, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Olive grove
Initial stocks: intamadora (varieties)	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand Tons	October, 2016 - May, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): TOTAL, Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): OTHERS, Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): CACEREÑA, Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): HOJIBLANCA, Olive grove (Balance of the campaign):

						GORDAL, Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): MANZANILLA , Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): CARRASQUEÑA
Production	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand tons	October, 2016 - May, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Olive grove (Comparison)
Imports	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand tons	October, 2016 - May, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Olive grove (Comparison)
Exports	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand tons	October, 2016 - May, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Olive grove (Comparison)
Aparent internal market	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand tons	October, 2016 - May, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Olive grove (Comparison)
Total market	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand tons	October, 2016 - May, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Olive grove (Comparison)
Stocks in mills and heritage	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand tons	October, 2016 - May, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Olive grove (Comparison)
Stocks in packaging and equity	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand tons	October, 2016 - May, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Olive grove (Comparison)
Total stocks	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand tons	October, 2016 - May, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Olive grove (Comparison)
Production (varieties)	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand tons	October, 2016 - May, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): TOTAL, Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): OTHERS, Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): CACEREÑA, Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): HOJIBLANCA, Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): GORDAL, Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): MANZANILLA , Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): CARRASQUEÑA

Shrinkage and waste (varieties)	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand tons	October, 2016 - May, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): TOTAL, Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): OTHERS, Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): CACEREÑA, Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): HOJIBLANCA, Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): GORDAL, Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): MANZANILLA , Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): CARRASQUEÑA
Adjustments (varieties)	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand tons	October, 2016 - May, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): TOTAL, Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): OTHERS, Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): CACEREÑA, Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): HOJIBLANCA, Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): GORDAL, Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): MANZANILLA , Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): CARRASQUEÑA
Initial stocks: packaging machine (varieties)	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand Tons	October, 2016 - May, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): TOTAL, Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): OTHERS, Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): CACEREÑA, Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): HOJIBLANCA, Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): GORDAL, Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): MANZANILLA , Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): CARRASQUEÑA
Imports: intamadora (varieties)	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand Tons	October, 2016 - May, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): TOTAL, Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): OTHERS, Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): CACEREÑA, Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): HOJIBLANCA,

						Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): GORDAL, Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): MANZANILLA , Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): CARRASQUEÑA
Final stocks: intamadora (varieties)	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand Tons	October, 2016 - May, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): TOTAL, Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): OTHERS, Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): CACEREÑA, Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): HOJIBLANCA, Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): GORDAL, Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): MANZANILLA , Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): CARRASQUEÑA
Final stocks: packaging machine (varieties)	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand Tons	October, 2016 - May, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): TOTAL, Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): OTHERS, Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): CACEREÑA, Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): HOJIBLANCA, Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): GORDAL, Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): MANZANILLA , Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): CARRASQUEÑA
Olives marketed (varieties): Export	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand tons	October, 2016 - May, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): TOTAL, Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): OTHERS, Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): CACEREÑA, Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): HOJIBLANCA, Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): GORDAL, Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): MANZANILLA , Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): CARRASQUEÑA

Olives marketed (varieties): Domestic market	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand tons	October, 2016 - May, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): TOTAL, Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): OTHERS, Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): CACEREÑA, Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): HOJIBLANCA, Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): GORDAL, Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): MANZANILLA , Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): CARRASQUEÑA
Imports: packaging machine (varieties)	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand Tons	October, 2016 - May, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): TOTAL, Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): OTHERS, Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): CACEREÑA, Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): HOJIBLANCA, Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): GORDAL, Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): MANZANILLA , Olive grove (Balance of the campaign): CARRASQUEÑA
Input of net raw of olive	Socioeconomic variable	Tons	October, 2016 - May, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Olive grove
Total varieties: intamadora	Socioeconomic variable	Nº intamadora	October, 2016 - May, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Olive grove
Total varieties: Net raw olive input	Socioeconomic variable	Tons	October, 2016 - May, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Olive grove
Production (Accumulated)	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand tons	October, 2016 - May, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Olive grove (Accumulated)
Imports (Accumulated)	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand tons	October, 2016 - May, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Olive grove (Accumulated)
Exports (Accumulated)	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand tons	October, 2016 - May, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Olive grove (Accumulated)

Aparent internal market (Accumulated)	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand tons	October, 2016 - May, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Olive grove (Accumulated)
Total market (Accumulated)	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand tons	October, 2016 - May, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Olive grove (Accumulated)
Oil mills. Annual summary of net oil outflows	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand tons	October, 2016 - May, 2021	Average	Monthly	Olive grove
Packaging machines, refineries and operators: Stocks total (With oil mill)	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand tons	October, 2016 - May, 2021	Average	Monthly	Olive grove
Packaging machines, refineries and operators: Stocks total (Whithout oil mill)	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand tons	October, 2016 - May, 2021	Average	Monthly	Olive grove
Packaging machines, refineries and operators: Stocks total (Extra virgin Olive Oil)	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand tons	October, 2016 - May, 2021	Average	Monthly	Olive grove
Packaging machines, refineries and operators: Stocks total	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand tons	October, 2016 - May, 2021	Average	Monthly	Olive grove

(Virgin Olive Oil)						
Packaging machines, refineries and operators: Stocks total (Olive Oil)	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand tons	October, 2016 - May, 2021	Average	Monthly	Olive grove
Packaging machines, refineries and operators: Stocks total (Refined Olive Oil)	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand tons	October, 2016 - May, 2021	Average	Monthly	Olive grove
Packaging machines, refineries and operators: Annual Stocks suumary	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand tons	October, 2016 - May, 2021	Average	Monthly	Olive grove
Packaging machines, refineries and operators: Number of companies that send data (With oil mill)	Socioeconomic variable	Number of companies	October, 2016 - May, 2021	Average	Monthly	Olive grove
Packaging machines, refineries and operators: Number of	Socioeconomic variable	Number of companies	October, 2016 - May, 2021	Average	Monthly	Olive grove

companies that send data (Without oil mill)						
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Crop Surveys (for Greece)

General information

Description: The main objective of the survey is the collection of data on cultivated areas under fruit trees by species (apple trees, pear trees, peach trees, apricot trees, cherry trees, orange trees, lemon trees, small citrus fruit trees and olive trees), the number of trees, as well as other characteristics, such as variety, density of tree plantation and age.

Producer: ELSTAT

Link: <https://www.statistics.gr/en/statistics/-/publication/SPG63/->

Languages: Greek, Modern (1453-)

Catalogue: ELSTAT - Areas and production

Subjects: crop production, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Agricultural costs, Agriculture policy

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution:

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: GR11, GR30, GR41, GR23, GR13, GR21, GR14, GR22, GR12, GR43, GR42, GR25, GR24

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 7, 2022

Characterization created at: January 7, 2022

Issued: September 1, 2018

Last update: September 1, 2018

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 2002 - January, 2017

Keywords: production, orchard survey

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Crop Surveys	SDMX	Public	https://www.statistics.gr/en/statistics/-/publication/SPG63/	SDMX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Region	January, 2002 - January, 2017	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Number of holdings	Socioeconomic variable		January, 2002 - January, 2007		Irregular	
Area of cultivation	Socioeconomic variable		January, 2002 - January, 2017			
Number of trees	Socioeconomic variable		January, 2002 - January, 2017			

Agricultural Census **LEGAL PERSONALITY OF THE TITLE HOLDER AND LAND TENURE REGIME: Number, total area and UAA of operation according to the legal status of the owner and management.**

General information

Description: Census. Collection of information regarding the agrarian structure, to serve as the basis for the directory of agricultural operations, in compliance with the legal regulations established by the European Union

Producer: Spanish National Statistics Institute

Link: https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106

Languages: Spanish | Castilian

Catalogue:

Subjects: agricultural product, agricultural region, agricultural statistics

Useful for the analysis of: Use of agricultural area

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: National Statistics Institute (Spain)

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Spain

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 18, 2022

Characterization created at: December 13, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2009

Last update: November 3, 2011

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2009

Keywords: agricultural area

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Agricultural Census	Excel XLSX	Public	https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural holding	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Natural person and agricultural manager (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding

Natural person and agricultural manager	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Natural person and agricultural manager (UAA)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Mercantile company	Socioeconomic variable	Operations number	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Public entity	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Production cooperative	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Other legal status (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Other legal status	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Other legal status (UAA)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Mercantile company (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Mercantile company (UAA)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding

Public entity (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Public entity (UAA)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Production cooperative (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Production cooperative(UAA)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
All agricultural holdings (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
All agricultural holdings	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
All agricultural holdings (UAA)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Natural person (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Natural person	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Natural person (UAA)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding

Agricultural Census CROPS: Cultivation of genetically modified organisms

General information

Description: Census. Collection of information regarding the agrarian structure, to serve as the basis for the directory of agricultural operations, in compliance with the legal regulations established by the European Union

Producer: Spanish National Statistics Institute

Link: https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106

Languages: Spanish | Castilian

Catalogue:

Subjects: agricultural product, agricultural region, agricultural statistics

Useful for the analysis of: Use of agricultural area

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: National Statistics Institute (Spain)

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Spain

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 17, 2022

Characterization created at: December 15, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2009

Last update: November 3, 2011

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2009

Keywords: agricultural area

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Agricultural Census	Excel XLSX	Public	https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural holding with UAA	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Cultivated agricultural land	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Cultivated agricultural land (Area)	Socioeconomic variable	hectare	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA

Livestock Surveys (for Greece)

General information

Description: The statistical surveys on livestock are carried out every year in order to provide information on the total number of bovine animals, pigs, sheep and goats, as well as on the total domestic production of meat, milk and dairy products, at the Regional level (NUTS 2), thus offering a basis for decision-making concerning Common Agricultural Policy.

Producer: ELSTAT

Link: <https://www.statistics.gr/en/statistics/-/publication/SPK13/->

Languages: Greek, Modern (1453-)

Catalogue: ELSTAT - Areas and production

Subjects: livestock, animal product, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Agriculture policy

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution:

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: GR11, GR22, GR12, GR43, GR42, GR25, GR24, GR30, GR41, GR23, GR13, GR21, GR14

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 7, 2022

Characterization created at: January 7, 2022

Issued: June 1, 2020

Last update: June 1, 2020

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 1998 - January, 2019

Keywords: livestock, livestock animal units

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Livestock Surveys	SDMX	Public	https://www.statistics.gr/en/statistics/-/publication/SPK13/	SDMX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Livestock Surveys	January, 1998 - January, 2019	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Livestock Holdings	Socioeconomic variable		January, 1998 - January, 2019		Annual	
Cattle	Socioeconomic variable	Number	January, 1998 - January, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Livestock Surveys
Pigs	Socioeconomic variable	Number	January, 1998 - January, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Livestock Surveys
Goats	Socioeconomic variable	Number	January, 1998 - January, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Livestock Surveys
Sheep	Socioeconomic variable		January, 1998 - January, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Livestock Surveys

Agricultural Census CROPS: Energy crops

General information

Description: Census. Collection of information regarding the agrarian structure, to serve as the basis for the directory of agricultural operations, in compliance with the legal regulations established by the European Union

Producer: Spanish National Statistics Institute

Link: https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106

Languages: Spanish | Castilian

Catalogue:

Subjects: agricultural product, agricultural region, agricultural statistics

Useful for the analysis of: Use of agricultural area

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: National Statistics Institute (Spain)

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Spain

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 17, 2022

Characterization created at: January 17, 2022

Issued: January 1, 2009

Last update: November 3, 2011

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2009

Keywords: agricultural area

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Agricultural Census	Excel XLSX	Public	https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural holding with UAA	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Other energy crops	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Other energy crops (Area)	Socioeconomic variable	hectare	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Total energy crops	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Total energy crops (Area)	Socioeconomic variable	hectare	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA

Energy crops on withdrawal land	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Energy crops on withdrawal land (Area)	Socioeconomic variable	hectare	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA

Agricultural Census CROPS: Mushroom, wild mushrooms and other worked mushrooms

General information

Description: Census. Collection of information regarding the agrarian structure, to serve as the basis for the directory of agricultural operations, in compliance with the legal regulations established by the European Union

Producer: Spanish National Statistics Institute

Link: https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106

Languages: Spanish | Castilian

Catalogue:

Subjects: agricultural product, agricultural region, agricultural statistics

Useful for the analysis of: Use of agricultural area

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: National Statistics Institute (Spain)

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Spain

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 17, 2022

Characterization created at: December 15, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2009

Last update: November 3, 2011

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2009

Keywords: agricultural area

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Agricultural Census	Excel XLSX	Public	https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural holding with UAA	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Cultivated agricultural land	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Cultivated agricultural land	Socioeconomic variable	hectare	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA

Annual Agricultural Statistical Survey (for Greece)

General information

Description: The Annual Agricultural Survey aims to collect data that are categorized into four broad groups: Agriculture; Livestock; Agricultural Machinery; Fisheries - Coastal and Inland Waters

Producer: ELSTAT

Link: <https://www.statistics.gr/en/statistics/-/publication/SPG06/->

Languages: Greek, Modern (1453-)

Catalogue: ELSTAT - Areas and production

Subjects: agricultural holdings, agricultural product, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Agriculture policy

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution:

Resource type: Collection

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Greece

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 7, 2022

Characterization created at: January 7, 2022

Issued: June 24, 2021

Last update: June 24, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2001 - January, 2019

Keywords: agricultural holdings, agricultural area, agricultural machinery, agricultural product;

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Annual Agricultural Survey	SDMX	Public		SDMX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Annual Agricultural Survey	January, 2001 - January, 2019	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Crop areas	Socioeconomic variable	Hectare	January, 2001 - January, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Annual Agricultural Survey
Cereals	Socioeconomic variable	Hectares	January, 2001 - January, 2019	Instant value	Annual	
Edible pulse	Socioeconomic variable	Hectatres	January, 2001 - January, 2019	Instant value	Annual	
Fodder seeds	Socioeconomic variable		January, 2001 - January, 2019	Instant value	Annual	
Industrial plants	Socioeconomic variable		January, 2001 - January, 2019	Instant value	Annual	
Fodder plants for hey	Socioeconomic variable	Hectares	January, 2001 - January, 2019	Instant value	Annual	

Fodder plants for grass	Socioeconomic variable	Hectates	January, 2001 - January, 2019	Instant value	Annual	
Melons, watermelons and potatoes	Socioeconomic variable	Hectares	January, 2001 - January, 2019	Instant value	Annual	
Vegetables	Socioeconomic variable	Hectares	January, 2001 - January, 2019	Instant value	Annual	
Garden Area	Socioeconomic variable	Hectares	January, 2001 - January, 2019	Instant value	Annual	
Wines	Socioeconomic variable	Hectares	January, 2001 - January, 2019	Instant value	Annual	
Tree crops	Socioeconomic variable	Hectares	January, 2001 - January, 2019	Instant value	Annual	
Irrigated areas	Socioeconomic variable	Hectares	January, 2001 - January, 2019	Instant value	Annual	
Production	Socioeconomic variable		January, 2001 - January, 2019	Instant value	Annual	
Number of operating machinery	Socioeconomic variable	Number	January, 2001 - January, 2019	Instant value	Annual	
Horses, mules and donkeys	Socioeconomic variable	Number	January, 2001 - January, 2019	Instant value	Annual	
Oxen, bulls, heifers, cows and buffaloes	Socioeconomic variable	Number	January, 2001 - January, 2019	Instant value	Annual	
Sheep, goats and pigs	Socioeconomic variable	Number	January, 2001 - January, 2019	Instant value	Annual	
Poultry, rabbits	Socioeconomic variable	Number	January, 2001 - January, 2019	Instant value	Annual	

Milk production	Socioeconomic variable		January, 2001 - January, 2019	Instant value	Annual	
Meat production	Socioeconomic variable		January, 2001 - January, 2019	Instant value	Annual	
Production of other primary livestock by-products	Socioeconomic variable		January, 2001 - January, 2019	Instant value	Annual	
Production of selected livestock by-products	Socioeconomic variable		January, 2001 - January, 2019	Instant value	Annual	

Agricultural Census CROPS: Irrigable area

General information

Description: Census. Collection of information regarding the agrarian structure, to serve as the basis for the directory of agricultural operations, in compliance with the legal regulations established by the European Union

Producer: Spanish National Statistics Institute

Link: https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106

Languages: Spanish | Castilian

Catalogue:

Subjects: agricultural product, agricultural region, agricultural statistics

Useful for the analysis of: Use of agricultural area

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: National Statistics Institute (Spain)

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Spain

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 17, 2022

Characterization created at: December 15, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2009

Last update: November 3, 2011

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2009

Keywords: agricultural area

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Agricultural Census	Excel XLSX	Public	https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural holding with UAA	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Total irrigable land	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Total irrigable land (Area)	Socioeconomic variable	hectare	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Irrigated land	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Irrigated land (Area)	Socioeconomic variable	hectare	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA

Non-irrigated land	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Non-irrigated land (Area)	Socioeconomic variable	hectare	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA

Farm Structure Survey (Greece)

General information

Description: The purpose of the FSS is to determine the basic structural features of the agricultural and livestock holdings in Greece. Data are collected, according to Community legislation, on: General characteristics; Utilized agricultural area; Livestock; Variables of special interest, such as labour force, rural development issues, management and cultivation methods.

Producer: ELSTAT

Link: <https://www.statistics.gr/en/statistics/-/publication/SPG12/->

Languages: Greek, Modern (1453-)

Catalogue: ELSTAT - Areas and production

Subjects: agricultural holdings, agricultural statistics, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Agriculture policy

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution:

Resource type:

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Greece

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 7, 2022

Characterization created at: January 7, 2022

Issued: August 1, 2018

Last update: August 1, 2018

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 2003 - January, 2016

Keywords: agricultural holdings, agricultural economy, agriculture

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Farm Structure Survey	SDMX	Public		SDMX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Farm Structure Survey	January, 2003 - January, 2016	Country		

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Number of persons employed in agricultural holdings	Socioeconomic variable	Number	January, 2003 - January, 2016	Instant value	Irregular	
Employment of holders and their household members	Socioeconomic variable	Number	January, 2003 - January, 2016	Instant value	Irregular	
Holdings of natural persons and workdays	Socioeconomic variable	Number	January, 2003 - January, 2016	Instant value	Irregular	
Distribution of holders and	Socioeconomic variable	Number	January, 2003 - January, 2016	Instant value	Irregular	

their household members employed in the holding						
Holdings and utilised agricultural area, divided into mixed, agricultural and livestock holdings	Socioeconomic variable	Number	January, 2003 - January, 2016	Instant value	Irregular	
Holdings and area	Socioeconomic variable	Number	January, 2003 - January, 2016	Instant value	Irregular	
Holdings and area with annual crops	Socioeconomic variable	Number	January, 2003 - January, 2016	Instant value	Irregular	
Holdings and area with cereals for the production of grain	Socioeconomic variable	Number	January, 2003 - January, 2016	Instant value	Irregular	
Holdings and areas with tree crops	Socioeconomic variable	Number	January, 2006 - January, 2013	Instant value	Irregular	
Holdings and areas with vineyards	Socioeconomic variable	Number	January, 2006 - January, 2013	Instant value	Irregular	
Holdings with irrigated areas by type of crops	Socioeconomic variable		January, 2006 - January, 2013	Instant value	Irregular	

Holdings and number of animals	Socioeconomic variable	Number	January, 2003 - January, 2016	Instant value	Irregular	
Holdings and livestock units	Socioeconomic variable	Number	January, 2003 - January, 2016	Instant value	Irregular	

Agricultural Census: Work on the exploitation: Other family work according to sex and percentage time worked

General information

Description: Census. Collection of information regarding the agrarian structure, to serve as the basis for the directory of agricultural operations, in compliance with the legal regulations established by the European Union

Producer: Spanish National Statistics Institute

Link: https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106

Languages: Spanish | Castilian

Catalogue:

Subjects: agricultural product, agricultural region, agricultural statistics

Useful for the analysis of: Use of agricultural area

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: National Statistics Institute (Spain)

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Spain

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 18, 2022

Characterization created at: January 18, 2022

Issued: January 1, 2009

Last update: November 3, 2011

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2009

Keywords: agricultural area

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Agricultural Census	Excel XLSX	Public	https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural holding	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Percentage of time worked >= 25 to < 50% (Both genders)	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Percentage of time worked >= 50 to < 75% (Male)	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding

Percentage of time worked >= 50 to < 75% (Female)	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Percentage of time worked >= 50 to < 75% (Agricultural holdings)	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Percentage of time worked >= 50 to < 75% (Both genders)	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Percentage of time worked >= 75 to < 100% (Male)	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Percentage of time worked >= 75 to < 100% (Female)	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Percentage of time worked >= 75 to < 100% (Agricultural holdings)	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Percentage of time worked >= 75 to < 100% (Both genders)	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Percentage of time worked 100 % (Male)	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding

Percentage of time worked 100 % (Female)	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Percentage of time worked 100 % (Agricultural holdings)	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Percentage of time worked 100 % (Both genders)	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Percentage of time worked < 25% (Agricultural holdings)	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Percentage of time worked < 25% (Both genders)	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Percentage of time worked >= 25 to < 50% (Agricultural holdings)	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Percentage of time worked < 25% (Male)	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Percentage of time worked < 25% (Female)	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding

Percentage of time worked >= 25 to < 50% (Male)	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Percentage of time worked >= 25 to < 50% (Female)	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding

Agricultural Census: Ecological Agriculture and Livestock Breeding: Ecological production

General information

Description: Census. Collection of information regarding the agrarian structure, to serve as the basis for the directory of agricultural operations, in compliance with the legal regulations established by the European Union

Producer: Spanish National Statistics Institute

Link: https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106

Languages: Spanish | Castilian

Catalogue:

Subjects: agricultural product, agricultural region, agricultural statistics

Useful for the analysis of: Use of agricultural area

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: National Statistics Institute (Spain)

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Spain

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 18, 2022

Characterization created at: December 15, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2009

Last update: November 3, 2011

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2009

Keywords: agricultural area

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Agricultural Census	Excel XLSX	Public	https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural holding with UAA	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Total	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Total (Area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Certified agricultural holdings	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA

Certified agricultural holdings (Area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Agricultural holdings in period of conversion	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Agricultural holdings in period of conversion (Area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA

Statistics of land prices in Andalusia

General information

Description: The objective of this survey is to measure the evolution of the average price level of the most significant land classes, those that are free for sale and whose destination is that of their agricultural exploitation.

Producer: Regional Ministry of Agriculture, Livestock, Fisheries and Sustainable Development

Link: <https://www.juntadeandalucia.es/organismos/agriculturaganaderiapescaydesarrollosostenible/servicios/estadistica-cartografia/actividad/detalle/175057/175454.html>

Languages: Spanish | Castilian

Catalogue:

Subjects: price of agricultural produce, land use

Useful for the analysis of: Agricultural costs

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Collection

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: ES611, ES612, ES613, ES614, ES615, ES616, ES617, ES618

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 14, 2022

Characterization created at: December 17, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2002

Last update: March 31, 2017

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2002 - December, 2015

Keywords: agricultural economy, land prices, prices

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Land price	PDF	Public	https://www.juntadeandalucia.es/organismos/agriculturaganaderiapescaydesarrollosostenible/servicios/estadistica-cartografia/actividad/detalle/175057/175454.html	PDF	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Rainfed labour	January, 2002 - December, 2015	NUTS3		
Open-air vegetables	January, 2002 - December, 2015	NUTS3		
Olive trees rainfed	January, 2002 - December, 2015	NUTS3		
Irrigated labour	January, 2002 - December, 2015	NUTS3		
Orange tree	January, 2002 - December, 2015	NUTS3		

Olive groves dry olive groves	January, 2002 - December, 2015	NUTS3		
Stone fruit trees	January, 2002 - December, 2015	NUTS3		
Orange tree irrigated	January, 2002 - December, 2015	NUTS3		
Irrigated table olive groves	January, 2002 - December, 2015	NUTS3		
Irrigated stone fruit trees	January, 2002 - December, 2015	NUTS3		
Dried fruits and nuts rainfed	January, 2002 - December, 2015	NUTS3		
Strawberry	January, 2002 - December, 2015	NUTS3		
Irrigated cherry trees	January, 2002 - December, 2015	NUTS3		
Fleshy fruit	January, 2002 - December, 2015	NUTS3		
Rainfed cherry trees	January, 2002 - December, 2015	NUTS3		
Dried fruit irrigated	January, 2002 - December, 2015	NUTS3		
Lemon irrigated	January, 2002 - December, 2015	NUTS3		
Grassland, wasteland pasture	January, 2002 - December, 2015	NUTS3		
Rice	January, 2002 - December, 2015	NUTS3		
Irrigated olive groves	January, 2002 - December, 2015	NUTS3		

Vineyard rainfed	January, 2002 - December, 2015	NUTS3		
Irrigated vineyard	January, 2002 - December, 2015	NUTS3		
Table grapes	January, 2002 - December, 2015	NUTS3		
Pasture	January, 2002 - December, 2015	NUTS3		
Irrigated olive grove	January, 2002 - December, 2015	NUTS3		
Olive groves rainfed	January, 2002 - December, 2015	NUTS3		
Vineyard transformation rainfed	January, 2002 - November, 2015	NUTS3		
Vineyards transformation	January, 2002 - December, 2015	NUTS3		
Dry land table vineyard	January, 2002 - November, 2015	NUTS3		

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Maximum price	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 2002 - December, 2015	Instant value	Annual	Rainfed labour , Irrigated labour , Stone fruit trees, Irrigated stone fruit trees, Fleshy fruit , Dried fruits and nuts rainfed , Dried fruit irrigated , Grassland, wasteland pasture, Pasture, Open-air vegetables, Orange tree , Orange tree irrigated, Strawberry, Rainfed cherry trees , Irrigated cherry trees , Lemon irrigated , Rice, Olive groves rainfed , Irrigated olive grove, Olive trees rainfed , Irrigated table

						olive groves , Olive groves dry olive groves, Irrigated olive groves, Vineyard rainfed , Irrigated vineyard, Table grapes , Vineyard transformation rainfed, Vineyards transformation, Dry land table vineyard
Minimum price	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 2002 - December, 2015	Instant value	Annual	Rainfed labour , Irrigated labour , Stone fruit trees, Irrigated stone fruit trees, Fleshy fruit , Dried fruits and nuts rainfed , Dried fruit irrigated , Grassland, wasteland pasture, Pasture, Open-air vegetables, Orange tree , Orange tree irrigated, Strawberry, Rainfed cherry trees , Irrigated cherry trees , Lemon irrigated , Rice, Olive groves rainfed , Irrigated olive grove, Olive trees rainfed , Irrigated table olive groves , Olive groves dry olive groves, Irrigated olive groves, Vineyard rainfed , Irrigated vineyard, Table grapes , Vineyard transformation rainfed, Vineyards transformation, Dry land table vineyard
Most frequent price	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 2002 - December, 2015	Mode	Annual	Rainfed labour , Irrigated labour , Stone fruit trees, Irrigated stone fruit trees, Fleshy fruit , Dried fruits and nuts rainfed , Dried fruit irrigated , Grassland, wasteland pasture, Pasture, Open-air vegetables, Orange tree , Orange tree irrigated, Strawberry, Rainfed cherry trees , Irrigated cherry trees , Lemon irrigated , Rice, Olive groves rainfed , Irrigated olive grove, Olive trees rainfed , Irrigated table olive groves , Olive groves dry olive groves, Irrigated olive groves, Vineyard rainfed , Irrigated vineyard, Table grapes , Vineyard transformation rainfed,

						Vineyards transformation, Dry land table vineyard
Variation between two years	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 2002 - December, 2015	Instant value	Annual	Rainfed labour , Irrigated labour , Stone fruit trees, Irrigated stone fruit trees, Fleshy fruit , Dried fruits and nuts rainfed , Dried fruit irrigated , Grassland, wasteland pasture, Pasture, Open-air vegetables, Orange tree , Orange tree irrigated, Strawberry, Rainfed cherry trees , Irrigated cherry trees , Lemon irrigated , Rice, Olive groves rainfed , Irrigated olive grove, Olive trees rainfed , Irrigated table olive groves , Olive groves dry olive groves, Irrigated olive groves, Vineyard rainfed , Irrigated vineyard, Table grapes , Vineyard transformation rainfed, Vineyards transformation, Dry land table vineyard
Variation between two years (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2002 - December, 2015	Instant value	Annual	Rainfed labour , Irrigated labour , Stone fruit trees, Irrigated stone fruit trees, Fleshy fruit , Dried fruits and nuts rainfed , Dried fruit irrigated , Grassland, wasteland pasture, Pasture, Open-air vegetables, Orange tree , Orange tree irrigated, Strawberry, Rainfed cherry trees , Irrigated cherry trees , Lemon irrigated , Rice, Olive groves rainfed , Irrigated olive grove, Olive trees rainfed , Irrigated table olive groves , Olive groves dry olive groves, Irrigated olive groves, Vineyard rainfed , Irrigated vineyard, Table grapes , Vineyard transformation rainfed, Vineyards transformation, Dry land table vineyard

Agricultural Census: Rural development and equipment for the production of renewable energy: Rural development: other supplementary activities of the agricultural holding

General information

Description: Census. Collection of information regarding the agrarian structure, to serve as the basis for the directory of agricultural operations, in compliance with the legal regulations established by the European Union

Producer: Spanish National Statistics Institute

Link: https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106

Languages: Spanish | Castilian

Catalogue:

Subjects: agricultural product, agricultural region, agricultural statistics

Useful for the analysis of: Use of agricultural area

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: National Statistics Institute (Spain)

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Spain

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 18, 2022

Characterization created at: December 15, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2009

Last update: November 3, 2011

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2009

Keywords: agricultural area

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Agricultural Census	Excel XLSX	Public	https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural holding	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Total	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Tourism, accommodation and other	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding

recreational activities						
Transformation of agricultural products (production of cold meats, cheese, wine,...)	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Production of renewable energy to sell (wind, biogas, solar, etc.)	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Transformation of wood (sawn)	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Aquaculture (breeding of fish, crabs, frogs,...)	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Contracted agricultural work for other agricultural holdings	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Contracted non-agricultural work	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Forestry	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding

Others	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Craftwork	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding

Agricultural Census: Ecological Agriculture and Livestock Breeding: Distribution of certified organic agriculture area (certified and/or conversion period)

General information

Description: Census. Collection of information regarding the agrarian structure, to serve as the basis for the directory of agricultural operations, in compliance with the legal regulations established by the European Union

Producer: Spanish National Statistics Institute

Link: https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106

Languages: Spanish | Castilian

Catalogue:

Subjects: agricultural product, agricultural region, agricultural statistics

Useful for the analysis of: Use of agricultural area

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: National Statistics Institute (Spain)

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Spain

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 18, 2022

Characterization created at: December 15, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2009

Last update: November 3, 2011

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2009

Keywords: agricultural area

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Agricultural Census	Excel XLSX	Public	https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural holding with UAA	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Total crops (Area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Total crops	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA

Leguminous plants (Area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Potatoes (Area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Sugar beet (Area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Oleaginous crops (Area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Vegetables (Area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Cereals (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Permanent fields or grass lands (Area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Fruit trees (except citrus fruit) (Area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Citrus fruit trees (Area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Leguminous plants	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Potatoes	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Sugar beet	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA

Oleaginous crops	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Olive groves	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Vinification grapes	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Other crops	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Olive groves (Area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Vinification grapes (Area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Other crops (Area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Vegetables	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Permanent fields or grass lands	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Cereals	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Fruit trees (except citrus fruit)	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA

Citrus fruit trees	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
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Census of Agricultural and Livestock Holdings

General information

Description: The Agricultural and Livestock Census contributes to the collection of information on the agricultural and livestock holdings of Greece, at various geographical levels, and during different time periods, thus offering a tool for decision-making concerning the Common Agricultural Policy

Producer: ELSTAT

Link: <https://www.statistics.gr/en/statistics/-/publication/SPG11/>

Languages: Greek, Modern (1453-)

Catalogue: ELSTAT - Areas and production

Subjects: agricultural holdings, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Agriculture policy

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution:

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Greece

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 7, 2022

Characterization created at: January 7, 2022

Issued: August 26, 2013

Last update: August 26, 2013

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 2000 - January, 2009

Keywords: agricultural census

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Census of Agricultural and Livestock Holdings	SDMX	Public		SDMX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Census of Agricultural and Livestock Holdings	January, 2000 - January, 2009	Country		

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Number of persons employed in agriculture	Socioeconomic variable	Number	January, 2000 - January, 2009	Instant value	Irregular	
Number of persons employed in the total of holdings	Socioeconomic variable	Number	January, 2000 - January, 2009	Instant value	Irregular	
Number of holdings and utilised agricultural area	Socioeconomic variable	Number	January, 2000 - January, 2009	Instant value	Irregular	

Distribution of the utilized agricultural area of holdings	Socioeconomic variable	Number	January, 2000 - January, 2009	Instant value	Irregular	
Holdings with irrigated and irrigable areas	Socioeconomic variable	Number	January, 2000 - January, 2009	Instant value	Irregular	
Number of own agricultural machinery used in the holdings	Socioeconomic variable	Number	January, 2000 - January, 2009	Instant value	Irregular	
Holdings and number of animals	Socioeconomic variable	Number	January, 2000 - January, 2009	Instant value	Irregular	
Holdings and livestock units (LSU)	Socioeconomic variable		January, 2000 - January, 2009	Instant value	Irregular	

Agricultural Census: Ecological Agriculture and Livestock Breeding: Livestock ecological production

General information

Description: Census. Collection of information regarding the agrarian structure, to serve as the basis for the directory of agricultural operations, in compliance with the legal regulations established by the European Union

Producer: Spanish National Statistics Institute

Link: https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106

Languages: Spanish | Castilian

Catalogue:

Subjects: agricultural product, agricultural region, agricultural statistics

Useful for the analysis of: Use of agricultural area

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: National Statistics Institute (Spain)

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Spain

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 18, 2022

Characterization created at: December 15, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2009

Last update: November 3, 2011

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2009

Keywords: agricultural area

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Agricultural Census	Excel XLSX	Public	https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural holding	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Bovine (agricultural holdings)	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Bovine (heads)	Socioeconomic variable	Number of heads	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Birds (agricultural holdings)	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding

Other animals (agricultural holdings)	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Sheep and goats (agricultural holdings)	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Pigs (agricultural holdings)	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Birds (heads)	Socioeconomic variable	Number of heads	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Sheep and goats (heads)	Socioeconomic variable	Number of heads	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Pigs (heads)	Socioeconomic variable	Number of heads	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding

Agricultural Census: Rural development and equipment for the production of renewable energy: Rural development, importance of the other supplementary activities of the agricultural holding

General information

Description: Census. Collection of information regarding the agrarian structure, to serve as the basis for the directory of agricultural operations, in compliance with the legal regulations established by the European Union

Producer: Spanish National Statistics Institute

Link: https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106

Languages: Spanish | Castilian

Catalogue:

Subjects: agricultural product, agricultural region, agricultural statistics

Useful for the analysis of: Use of agricultural area

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: National Statistics Institute (Spain)

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Spain

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 18, 2022

Characterization created at: December 15, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2009

Last update: February 16, 2016

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2009

Keywords: agricultural area

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Agricultural Census	Excel XLSX	Public	https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural holding	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Percentage share of output of these activities in final production: % <10	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding

Percentage share of output of these activities in final production: 10<%<50	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Percentage share of output of these activities in final production: 50<%<100	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding

National Agricultural Economic Statistics: Short-term prices of agricultural products

General information

Description: The objective of this survey is the calculation of the average prices of the agricultural products with the major national relevance and/or with specific regulations in the Common Market Organization (CMO) of the EU.

Producer: Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food

Link: <https://www.mapa.gob.es/es/estadistica/temas/estadisticas-agrarias/economia/precios-coyunturales-prod-agricolas/>

Languages: Spanish | Castilian

Catalogue:

Subjects: agricultural economics, price of agricultural produce

Useful for the analysis of: Agricultural costs

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: weekly

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: ES513, ES514, ES521, ES522, ES523, ES611, ES612, ES613, ES614, ES615, ES616, ES617, ES618, ES620, ES114, ES220, ES230, ES241, ES243, ES300, ES411, ES412, ES413, ES414, ES415, ES416, ES417, ES418, ES419, ES421, ES422, ES423, ES424, ES425, ES431, ES432, ES511, ES512

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 13, 2022

Characterization created at: December 22, 2021

Issued: January 11, 2005

Last update: December 12, 2021

Periodicity: Weekly

Temporal extent: January, 2005 - December, 2021

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Prices of agricultural products (excel spreadsheet))	Excel XLS	Public	https://www.mapa.gob.es/es/estadistica/temas/estadisticas-agrarias/economia/precios-coyunturales-prod-agricolas/	Excel XLS	False
Prices of agricultural products (PDF))	PDF	Public	https://www.mapa.gob.es/es/estadistica/temas/estadisticas-agrarias/economia/precios-coyunturales-prod-agricolas/	PDF	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
National Producer Prices of Fruit on the Internal Market: Daily Prices and Weekly Weighted Average Prices in Representative Markets	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Country	100	

National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils	January, 2005 - December, 2021	NUTS3	100	
National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables	January, 2005 - December, 2021	NUTS3	100	
Average Prices on Representative Markets for Cereals, Alfalfa and Rice	January, 2005 - December, 2021	NUTS3		
National Average Prices of Livestock Products	January, 2005 - December, 2021	NUTS3	100	
Average Prices on Representative Markets: Barley	January, 2005 - December, 2021	NUTS3		
Average Representative Market Prices: Wheat and alfalfa	January, 2005 - December, 2021			
Average Prices in Representative Markets: Maize and Rice	January, 2005 - December, 2021	NUTS3		
Average Prices in Representative Markets for Wines	January, 2005 - December, 2021	NUTS3		
Average Prices in representative Markets for Oils and sunflower Seeds	January, 2005 - December, 2021	NUTS3		
Output Prices of Fruit on the Internal Market: Daily and Weekly Wighted Average Prices on Representative Markets	January, 2005 - December, 2021	NUTS3	100	

Provincial Producer Prices of Fruit on the Internal Market: Daily Prices and Weekly Weighted Average Prices in Representative Markets	January, 2005 - December, 2021	NUTS3		
Provincial Producer Prices of Horticultural Products on the Internal Market: Daily and Weekly Weighted Average Prices	January, 2005 - December, 2021	NUTS3	100	
National Average Prices of Other bovine animals	January, 2005 - December, 2021	NUTS3	100	
Average Prices of Precocious Pigs, Piglets and Other Grades	January, 2005 - December, 2021	NUTS3	100	
National Producer Prices of Horticultural Products on the Internal Market: Daily and Weekly Weighted Average Prices	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Country	100	
National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses	January, 2005 - December, 2021	NUTS3	100	
National Average Prices for Live bovine Carcasses	January, 2005 - December, 2021	NUTS3	100	
National Average Prices of Fresh or chilled Sheep Carcasses	January, 2005 - December, 2021	NUTS3	100	
Average Prices of White-Capped Pig Carcasses	January, 2005 - December, 2021	NUTS3	100	

Average Prices in Provincial Representative Markets for Fattening Pigs	January, 2005 - December, 2021	NUTS3	100	
Average Prices of Pigs: Iberian Trunks	January, 2005 - December, 2021	NUTS3	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
National Price: CHICKEN: Chicken P90 (65% rdto.)	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg carcass	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Price: CHICKEN: Chicken P90 (65% rdto.): weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Price: CHICKEN: Chicken P10 (83% rdto.): weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Price: EGGS: Cage type eggs, average Class L and M	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Price: EGGS: Cage type eggs, average Class L and M: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products

National Price: EGGS: Cage type eggs, average Class L and M: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Price: EGGS: Cage type eggs - Class L	Socioeconomic variable	€/ dozen	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Price: EGGS: Cage type eggs - Class L: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Price: EGGS: Cage type eggs - Class L: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Price: EGGS: Cage Type Eggs - Class M	Socioeconomic variable	€/ dozen	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Price: EGGS: Cage Type Eggs - Class M: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Price: EGGS: Cage Type Eggs - Class M: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Price: EGGS: Floor Type	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products

Eggs average Class L and M						
National Price: EGGS: Floor Type Eggs average Class L and M: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Price: EGGS: Floor Type Eggs average Class L and M: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Price: EGGS: Floor Type Eggs - L Class	Socioeconomic variable	€/ dozen	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Price: EGGS: Floor Type Eggs - L Class: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Price: EGGS: Floor Type Eggs - L Class: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Price: EGGS: Floor Type Eggs - Class M	Socioeconomic variable	€/ dozen	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Price: EGGS: Floor Type Eggs - Class M: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products

National Price: EGGS: Floor Type Eggs - Class M: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Price: RABBIT: Rabbit1,8-2,2 kilo, live	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Price: RABBIT: Rabbit1,8-2,2 kilo, live: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Price: RABBIT: Rabbit1,8-2,2 kilo, live: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Price: MILK AND MILK PRODUCTS: Buttermilk powder	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Price: MILK AND MILK PRODUCTS: Buttermilk powder: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Price: MILK AND MILK PRODUCTS: Buttermilk	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products

powder: weekly variation (%)						
National Price: MILK AND MILK PRODUCTS: Unsalted butter (format 25 kg)	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Price: MILK AND MILK PRODUCTS: Unsalted butter (format 25 kg): weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Price: MILK AND MILK PRODUCTS: Unsalted butter (format 25 kg): weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Price: MILK AND MILK PRODUCTS: Raw cow's milk	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 litres	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Price: MILK AND MILK PRODUCTS: Raw cow's milk: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Price: MILK AND MILK PRODUCTS: Raw cow's milk:	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products

weekly variation (%)						
National Price: HONEY: Bulk multi-flower honey	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Price: HONEY: Bulk multi-flower honey: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Price: HONEY: Bulk multi-flower honey: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
Average prices of fresh or chilled sheep carcasses on national representative markets for the EU: REPRESENTATIVE MARKET - Lamb 9-19 kg: Albacete: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Fresh or chilled Sheep Carcasses
Average Prices in Representative Markets: Common Wheat Bread Wheat	Socioeconomic variable	€/ ton	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices on Representative Markets for Cereals, Alfalfa and Rice

Average Prices in Representative Markets: Common Wheat Bread Wheat: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices on Representative Markets for Cereals, Alfalfa and Rice
Average Prices in Representative Markets: Common Wheat Bread Wheat: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices on Representative Markets for Cereals, Alfalfa and Rice
Average Prices in Representative Markets: Durum Wheat	Socioeconomic variable	€/ ton	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices on Representative Markets for Cereals, Alfalfa and Rice
Average Prices in Representative Markets: Durum Wheat: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices on Representative Markets for Cereals, Alfalfa and Rice
Average Prices in Representative Markets: Durum Wheat: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices on Representative Markets for Cereals, Alfalfa and Rice
Average Prices in Representative Markets: Alfalfa Bales	Socioeconomic variable	€/ ton	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices on Representative Markets for Cereals, Alfalfa and Rice
Average Prices in Representative Markets: Alfalfa	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices on Representative Markets for Cereals, Alfalfa and Rice

Bales: weekly variation						
Average Prices in Representative Markets: Alfalfa Bales: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices on Representative Markets for Cereals, Alfalfa and Rice
Average Prices in Representative Markets: Alfalfa Pellets	Socioeconomic variable	€/ ton	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices on Representative Markets for Cereals, Alfalfa and Rice
Average Prices in Representative Markets: Alfalfa Pellets : weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices on Representative Markets for Cereals, Alfalfa and Rice
Average Prices in Representative Markets: Alfalfa Pellets : weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices on Representative Markets for Cereals, Alfalfa and Rice
Average Prices in Representative Markets: Barley Feed	Socioeconomic variable	€/ ton	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices on Representative Markets: Barley
Average Prices in Representative Markets: Barley Feed: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices on Representative Markets: Barley
Average Prices in Representative Markets: Barley	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices on Representative Markets: Barley

Feed: weekly variation (%)						
Average Prices in Representative Markets: Barley Malt	Socioeconomic variable	€/ ton	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices on Representative Markets: Barley
Average Prices in Representative Markets: Barley Malt: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices on Representative Markets: Barley
Average Prices in Representative Markets: Barley Malt: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices on Representative Markets: Barley
Average prices of fresh or chilled sheep carcasses on national representative markets for the EU: REPRESENTATIVE MARKET - Lamb 9-19 kg: Extremadura	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg canal	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Fresh or chilled Sheep Carcasses
Average prices of fresh or chilled sheep carcasses on national representative markets for the EU:	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Fresh or chilled Sheep Carcasses

REPRESENTATIVE MARKET - Lamb 9-19 kg: Extremadura: weekly variation						
Average prices of fresh or chilled sheep carcasses on national representative markets for the EU: REPRESENTATIVE MARKET - Lamb 9-19 kg: Segovia	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg canal	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Fresh or chilled Sheep Carcasses
Average prices of fresh or chilled sheep carcasses on national representative markets for the EU: REPRESENTATIVE MARKET - Lamb 9-19 kg: Segovia: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Fresh or chilled Sheep Carcasses
Average prices of fresh or chilled sheep carcasses on national representative markets for the EU: REPRESENTATIVE	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg canal	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Fresh or chilled Sheep Carcasses

MARKET - Lamb 9-19 kg: Toledo						
Average Prices in Representative Markets: Maize Grain	Socioeconomic variable	€/ ton	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Representative Markets: Maize and Rice
Average Prices in Representative Markets: Maize Grain: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Representative Markets: Maize and Rice
Average Prices in Representative Markets: Maize Grain: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Representative Markets: Maize and Rice
Average Prices in Representative Markets: Paddy rice (Indica)	Socioeconomic variable	€/ ton	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Representative Markets: Maize and Rice
Average Prices in Representative Markets: Paddy rice (Indica): weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Representative Markets: Maize and Rice
Average Prices in Representative Markets: Paddy rice (Indica): weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Representative Markets: Maize and Rice

Average Prices in Representative Markets: Husk rice (Japonica)	Socioeconomic variable	€/ ton	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Representative Markets: Maize and Rice
Average Prices in Representative Markets: Husk rice (Japonica): weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Representative Markets: Maize and Rice
Average Prices in Representative Markets: Husk rice (Japonica): weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Representative Markets: Maize and Rice
Average Prices in Representative Markets: White rice (Indica)	Socioeconomic variable	€/ ton	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Representative Markets: Maize and Rice
Average Prices in Representative Markets: White rice (Indica): weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Representative Markets: Maize and Rice
Average Prices in Representative Markets: White rice (Indica): weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Representative Markets: Maize and Rice
Average Prices in Representative Markets: White rice (Japonica)	Socioeconomic variable	€/ ton	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Representative Markets: Maize and Rice

Average Prices in Representative Markets: White rice (Japonica): weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Representative Markets: Maize and Rice
Average Prices in Representative Markets: White rice (Japonica): weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Representative Markets: Maize and Rice
Average Prices in Representative Markets: Steamed white rice	Socioeconomic variable	€/ ton	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Representative Markets: Maize and Rice
Average Prices in Representative Markets: Steamed white rice: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Representative Markets: Maize and Rice
Average Prices in Representative Markets: Steamed white rice: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Representative Markets: Maize and Rice
Average Prices in Representative Markets: Broken rice	Socioeconomic variable	€/ ton	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Representative Markets: Maize and Rice
Average Prices in Representative Markets: Broken	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Representative Markets: Maize and Rice

rice weekly variation						
Average Prices in Representative Markets: Broken rice: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Representative Markets: Maize and Rice
Average prices of fresh or chilled sheep carcasses on national representative markets for the EU: REPRESENTATIVE MARKET - Lamb 9-19 kg: Toledo: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Fresh or chilled Sheep Carcasses
Average prices of fresh or chilled sheep carcasses on national representative markets for the EU: REPRESENTATIVE MARKET - Lamb 9-19 kg: Zaragoza	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg canal	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Fresh or chilled Sheep Carcasses
Average prices of fresh or chilled sheep carcasses on national representative markets for the EU:	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Fresh or chilled Sheep Carcasses

REPRESENTATIVE MARKET - Lamb 9-19 kg: Zaragoza: weekly variation						
Average prices of fresh or chilled sheep carcasses on national representative markets for the EU: REPRESENTATIVE MARKET - Lamb 9-19 kg: Weighted average	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg canal	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Fresh or chilled Sheep Carcasses
Average Prices in Representative Markets: White Wine without PDO/IPG: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Representative Markets for Wines
Average Prices in Representative Markets: White Wine without PDO/IPG: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Representative Markets for Wines
Average Prices in Representative Markets: Red wine without PDO / IPG: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Representative Markets for Wines

Average Prices in Representative Markets: Red wine without PDO / IPG: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Representative Markets for Wines
Average prices of fresh or chilled sheep carcasses on national representative markets for the EU: REPRESENTATIVE MARKET - Lamb 9-19 kg: Weighted average: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Fresh or chilled Sheep Carcasses
Average Prices in Representative Markets: Extra virgin olive oil	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in representative Markets for Oils and sunflower Seeds
Average Prices in Representative Markets: Extra virgin olive oil: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in representative Markets for Oils and sunflower Seeds
Average Prices in Representative Markets: Extra virgin olive oil: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in representative Markets for Oils and sunflower Seeds

Average Prices in Representative Markets: Virgin olive oil	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in representative Markets for Oils and sunflower Seeds
Average Prices in Representative Markets: Virgin olive oil: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in representative Markets for Oils and sunflower Seeds
Average Prices in Representative Markets: Virgin olive oil: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in representative Markets for Oils and sunflower Seeds
Average Prices in Representative Markets: Lampante olive oil	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in representative Markets for Oils and sunflower Seeds
Average Prices in Representative Markets: Lampante olive oil: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in representative Markets for Oils and sunflower Seeds
Average Prices in Representative Markets: Lampante olive oil: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in representative Markets for Oils and sunflower Seeds
Average Prices in Representative Markets	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in representative Markets for Oils and sunflower Seeds

Markets: Refined olive oil						
Average Prices in Representative Markets: Refined olive oil : weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in representative Markets for Oils and sunflower Seeds
Average Prices in Representative Markets: Refined olive oil: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in representative Markets for Oils and sunflower Seeds
Average Prices in Representative Markets: Crude olive pomace oil	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in representative Markets for Oils and sunflower Seeds
Average Prices in Representative Markets: Crude olive pomace oil: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in representative Markets for Oils and sunflower Seeds
Average Prices in Representative Markets: Crude olive pomace oil : weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in representative Markets for Oils and sunflower Seeds
Average Prices in Representative Markets: Refined olive pomace oil	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in representative Markets for Oils and sunflower Seeds

Average Prices in Representative Markets: Refined olive pomace oil : weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in representative Markets for Oils and sunflower Seeds
Average Prices in Representative Markets: Refined olive pomace oil: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in representative Markets for Oils and sunflower Seeds
Average Prices in Representative Markets: Sunflower seed (high oleic)	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in representative Markets for Oils and sunflower Seeds
Average Prices in Representative Markets: Sunflower seed (high oleic): weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in representative Markets for Oils and sunflower Seeds
Average Prices in Representative Markets: Sunflower seed (high oleic): weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in representative Markets for Oils and sunflower Seeds
Average Prices in Representative Markets: Sunflower seed oil (Conventional)	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in representative Markets for Oils and sunflower Seeds

Average Prices in Representative Markets: Sunflower seed oil (Conventional): weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in representative Markets for Oils and sunflower Seeds
Average Prices in Representative Markets: Sunflower seed oil (Conventional): weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in representative Markets for Oils and sunflower Seeds
Average Carcass Prices for White-Capped Pig Carcasses: : Class S (>60% lean content)	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg canal	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices of White-Capped Pig Carcasses
Average Carcass Prices for White-Capped Pig Carcasses: : Class S (>60% lean content): weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices of White-Capped Pig Carcasses
Average Carcass Prices for White-Capped Pig Carcasses: Class E (60%-55% lean content)	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg canal	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices of White-Capped Pig Carcasses

Average Carcass Prices for White-Capped Pig Carcasses: : Class E (60%-55% lean content)): weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices of White-Capped Pig Carcasses
Fruit Production in the Internal Market: Clementine	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Provincial Producer Prices of Fruit on the Internal Market: Daily Prices and Weekly Weighted Average Prices in Representative Markets, National Producer Prices of Fruit on the Internal Market: Daily Prices and Weekly Weighted Average Prices in Representative Markets
Average Carcass Prices for White-Capped Pig Carcasses: Class U (55%-50% lean content)	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg canal	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices of White-Capped Pig Carcasses
Average Carcass Prices for White-Capped Pig Carcasses: Class U (55%-50% lean content): weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices of White-Capped Pig Carcasses
Average Carcass Prices for White-Capped Pig Carcasses: Class R (50%-45% lean content)	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg canal	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices of White-Capped Pig Carcasses

Average Carcass Prices for White-Capped Pig Carcasses: Class R (50%-45% lean content) : weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices of White-Capped Pig Carcasses
Fruit Production in the Internal Market: Lemon	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Provincial Producer Prices of Fruit on the Internal Market: Daily Prices and Weekly Weighted Average Prices in Representative Markets, National Producer Prices of Fruit on the Internal Market: Daily Prices and Weekly Weighted Average Prices in Representative Markets
Fruit Production in the Internal Market: Mandarin	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Provincial Producer Prices of Fruit on the Internal Market: Daily Prices and Weekly Weighted Average Prices in Representative Markets, National Producer Prices of Fruit on the Internal Market: Daily Prices and Weekly Weighted Average Prices in Representative Markets
Fruit Production in the Internal Market: Orange	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Provincial Producer Prices of Fruit on the Internal Market: Daily Prices and Weekly Weighted Average Prices in Representative Markets, National Producer Prices of Fruit on the Internal Market: Daily Prices and Weekly Weighted Average Prices in Representative Markets
Fruit Production in the Internal Market: Satsuma	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Provincial Producer Prices of Fruit on the Internal Market: Daily Prices and Weekly Weighted Average Prices in Representative Markets, National

						Producer Prices of Fruit on the Internal Market: Daily Prices and Weekly Weighted Average Prices in Representative Markets
Fruit Production in the Internal Market: Apple	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Provincial Producer Prices of Fruit on the Internal Market: Daily Prices and Weekly Weighted Average Prices in Representative Markets
Fruit Production in the Internal Market: Pear	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Provincial Producer Prices of Fruit on the Internal Market: Daily Prices and Weekly Weighted Average Prices in Representative Markets, National Producer Prices of Fruit on the Internal Market: Daily Prices and Weekly Weighted Average Prices in Representative Markets
Fruit Production in the Internal Market: Table grape	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Provincial Producer Prices of Fruit on the Internal Market: Daily Prices and Weekly Weighted Average Prices in Representative Markets, National Producer Prices of Fruit on the Internal Market: Daily Prices and Weekly Weighted Average Prices in Representative Markets
Average Carcass Prices for White-Capped Pig Carcasses: Class O (45%-40% lean content)	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg canal	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices of White-Capped Pig Carcasses
Average Carcass Prices for White-Capped Pig Carcasses: Class O	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices of White-Capped Pig Carcasses

(45%-40% lean content) : weekly variation						
Average Carcass Prices for White-Capped Pig Carcasses: Class P (<40% lean content)	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg canal	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices of White-Capped Pig Carcasses
Average Carcass Prices for White-Capped Pig Carcasses: Class P (<40% lean content) : weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices of White-Capped Pig Carcasses
Fruit Production in the Internal Market: Other fruits	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Provincial Producer Prices of Fruit on the Internal Market: Daily Prices and Weekly Weighted Average Prices in Representative Markets, National Producer Prices of Fruit on the Internal Market: Daily Prices and Weekly Weighted Average Prices in Representative Markets
Horticultural Production in the Internal Market: Garlic	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Producer Prices of Horticultural Products on the Internal Market: Daily and Weekly Weighted Average Prices, Provincial Producer Prices of Horticultural Products on the Internal Market: Daily and Weekly Weighted Average Prices
Horticultural Production in the	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Producer Prices of Horticultural Products on the Internal Market: Daily and Weekly Weighted Average Prices,

Internal Market: Aubergine						Provincial Producer Prices of Horticultural Products on the Internal Market: Daily and Weekly Weighted Average Prices
Horticultural Production in the Internal Market: Courgette	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Producer Prices of Horticultural Products on the Internal Market: Daily and Weekly Weighted Average Prices, Provincial Producer Prices of Horticultural Products on the Internal Market: Daily and Weekly Weighted Average Prices
Horticultural Production in the Internal Market: Onion	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Producer Prices of Horticultural Products on the Internal Market: Daily and Weekly Weighted Average Prices, Provincial Producer Prices of Horticultural Products on the Internal Market: Daily and Weekly Weighted Average Prices
[Horticultural Production in the Internal Market: Mushroom	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Producer Prices of Horticultural Products on the Internal Market: Daily and Weekly Weighted Average Prices, Provincial Producer Prices of Horticultural Products on the Internal Market: Daily and Weekly Weighted Average Prices
Horticultural Production in the Internal Market: Cauliflower	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Producer Prices of Horticultural Products on the Internal Market: Daily and Weekly Weighted Average Prices, Provincial Producer Prices of Horticultural Products on the Internal Market: Daily and Weekly Weighted Average Prices

Horticultural Production in the Internal Market: Cabbage-Cabbage	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Producer Prices of Horticultural Products on the Internal Market: Daily and Weekly Weighted Average Prices, Provincial Producer Prices of Horticultural Products on the Internal Market: Daily and Weekly Weighted Average Prices
Horticultural Production in the Internal Market: Green bean	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Producer Prices of Horticultural Products on the Internal Market: Daily and Weekly Weighted Average Prices, Provincial Producer Prices of Horticultural Products on the Internal Market: Daily and Weekly Weighted Average Prices
Horticultural Production in the Internal Market: Lettuce	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Producer Prices of Horticultural Products on the Internal Market: Daily and Weekly Weighted Average Prices, Provincial Producer Prices of Horticultural Products on the Internal Market: Daily and Weekly Weighted Average Prices
Horticultural Production in the Internal Market: Melon	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Producer Prices of Horticultural Products on the Internal Market: Daily and Weekly Weighted Average Prices, Provincial Producer Prices of Horticultural Products on the Internal Market: Daily and Weekly Weighted Average Prices
Horticultural Production in the Internal Market: Cucumber	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Producer Prices of Horticultural Products on the Internal Market: Daily and Weekly Weighted Average Prices, Provincial Producer Prices of Horticultural Products on the Internal

						Market: Daily and Weekly Weighted Average Prices
Horticultural Production in the Internal Market: Sweet pepper	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Producer Prices of Horticultural Products on the Internal Market: Daily and Weekly Weighted Average Prices, Provincial Producer Prices of Horticultural Products on the Internal Market: Daily and Weekly Weighted Average Prices
Horticultural Production in the Internal Market: Leek	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Producer Prices of Horticultural Products on the Internal Market: Daily and Weekly Weighted Average Prices, Provincial Producer Prices of Horticultural Products on the Internal Market: Daily and Weekly Weighted Average Prices
Horticultural Production in the Internal Market: Tomato	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Producer Prices of Horticultural Products on the Internal Market: Daily and Weekly Weighted Average Prices, Provincial Producer Prices of Horticultural Products on the Internal Market: Daily and Weekly Weighted Average Prices
Horticultural Production in the Internal Market: Carrot	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Producer Prices of Horticultural Products on the Internal Market: Daily and Weekly Weighted Average Prices, Provincial Producer Prices of Horticultural Products on the Internal Market: Daily and Weekly Weighted Average Prices
National Price: Common wheat for breadmaking	Socioeconomic variable	€/ton	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils

National Price: Durum wheat	Socioeconomic variable	€/ton	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Feed barley	Socioeconomic variable	€/ton	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Malt barley	Socioeconomic variable	€/ton	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Grain maize	Socioeconomic variable	€/ton	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Japonica paddy rice	Socioeconomic variable	€/ton	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
Average Prices in Representative Markets: White Wine without PDO/IPG	Socioeconomic variable	€/ hL	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Representative Markets for Wines
Average Prices in Representative Markets: Red wine without PDO / IPG	Socioeconomic variable	€/ hL	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Representative Markets for Wines
National Price: Indica paddy rice	Socioeconomic variable	€/ton	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Japonica white rice	Socioeconomic variable	€/ton	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils

National Price: Indica white rice	Socioeconomic variable	€/ton	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Parboiled white rice	Socioeconomic variable	€/ton	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Broken rice	Socioeconomic variable	€/ton	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Conventional sunflower seed	Socioeconomic variable	€/ton	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: High oleic sunflower seed	Socioeconomic variable	€/ton	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Rapeseed	Socioeconomic variable	€/ton	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Sunflower cake. 34%-36% protein	Socioeconomic variable	€/ton	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Soybean cake. 44%-47% protein	Socioeconomic variable	€/ton	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Alfalfa. Bales 1st Cat. 16.5%-18% protein	Socioeconomic variable	€/ton	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Alfalfa. Standard pellets. 14%-16% protein	Socioeconomic variable	€/ton	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils

National Price: Dried peas	Socioeconomic variable	€/ton	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Lentils	Socioeconomic variable	€/ton	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Dried beans	Socioeconomic variable	€/ton	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Chickpeas	Socioeconomic variable	€/ton	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: White wine without PDO/PGI	Socioeconomic variable	€/hectolitre	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Red wine without PDO/PGI, 12 p. colour	Socioeconomic variable	€/hectolitre	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Extra virgin olive oil < 0.8°	Socioeconomic variable	€/100 kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Virgin olive oil, from 0.8° to 2°	Socioeconomic variable	€/100 kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Lampante olive oil > 2°	Socioeconomic variable	€/100 kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Refined olive oil	Socioeconomic variable	€/100 kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils

National Price: Crude olive- pomace oil	Socioeconomic variable	€/100 kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Refined olive- pomace oil	Socioeconomic variable	€/100 kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Refined conventional sunflower oil	Socioeconomic variable	€/100 kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Refined high oleic sunflower oil	Socioeconomic variable	€/100 kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Refined soybean oil	Socioeconomic variable	€/100 kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Table olives, average of varieties	Socioeconomic variable	€/100 kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Gordal variety	Socioeconomic variable	€/100 kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Hojiblanca variety	Socioeconomic variable	€/100 kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Manzanilla variety	Socioeconomic variable	€/100 kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Common wheat	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils

for breadmaking: weekly variation						
National Price: Common wheat for breadmaking weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Durum wheat: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Durum wheat: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Feed barley: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Feed barley: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Malt barley: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Malt barley: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Grain maize weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils

National Price: Grain maize weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	€/ton	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Japonica paddy rice: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Japonica paddy rice: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Indica paddy rice: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Indica paddy rice weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Japonica white rice weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Japonica white rice: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Indica white rice: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils

National Price: Indica white rice: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Parboiled white rice weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Parboiled white rice: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Broken rice: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Broken rice: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Conventional sunflower seed: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Conventional sunflower seed: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: High oleic sunflower seed: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils

National Price: High oleic sunflower seed weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Rapeseed: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Rapeseed: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Sunflower cake. 34%-36% protein: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Sunflower cake. 34%-36% protein: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category A: U-2	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg canal	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses
National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category A: U-2: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses
National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category A: U-3	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg canal	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses

National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category A: U-3: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses
National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category A: U	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg canal	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses
National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category A: R-2	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg canal	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses
National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category A: R-2: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses
National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category A: R-3	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg canal	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses
National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category A: R-3: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses
National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category A: R	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg canal	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses

National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category A: R: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses
National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category A: O-2	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg canal	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses
National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category A: O-2: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses
National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category A: O-3	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg canal	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses
National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category A: O-3: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses
National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category A: O	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg canal	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses
National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category A: O: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses

National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category D: P-2	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg canal	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses
National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category D: P-2: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses
National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category D: P-3	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg canal	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses
National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category D: P-3: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses
National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category D: P	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg canal	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses
National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category D: P: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses
National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category D: R-3	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg canal	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses

National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category D: R-3: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses
National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category D: R-4	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg canal	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses
National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category D: R-4: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses
National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category D: R	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg canal	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses
National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category D: R: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses
National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category D: O-2	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg canal	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses
National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category D: O-2: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses

National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category D: 0-3	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg canal	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses
National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category D: 0-3: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses
National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category D: 0-4	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg canal	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses
National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category D: 0-4: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses
National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category D: 0	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg canal	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses
National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category D: 0: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses
National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category E: U-2	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg canal	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses

National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category E: U-2: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses
National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category E: U-3	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg canal	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses
National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category E: U-3: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses
National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category E: U	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg canal	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses
National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category E: U: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses
National Price: Soybean cake. 44%-47% protein: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Soybean cake. 44%-47% protein: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils

National Price: Alfalfa. Bales 1st Cat. 16.5%-18% protein: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Alfalfa. Bales 1st Cat. 16.5%-18% protein: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Alfalfa. Standard pellets. 14%-16% protein: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Alfalfa. Standard pellets. 14%-16% protein: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Dried peas: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Dried peas: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Lentils: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Lentils: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils

National Price: Dried beans: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Dried beans: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Chickpeas weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Chickpeas: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: White wine without PDO/PGI: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: White wine without PDO/PGI: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Red wine without PDO/PGI, 12 p. colour: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Red wine without PDO/PGI, 12 p. colour: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils

National Price: Extra virgin olive oil < 0.8°: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Extra virgin olive oil < 0.8°: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Virgin olive oil, from 0.8° to 2°: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Virgin olive oil, from 0.8° to 2°: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Lampante olive oil > 2°: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Lampante olive oil > 2°: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Refined olive oil: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Refined olive oil: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils

National Price: Crude olive- pomace oil: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Crude olive- pomace oil: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Refined olive- pomace oil: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Refined olive- pomace oil: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Refined conventional sunflower oil: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Refined conventional sunflower oil: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Refined high oleic sunflower oil: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils

National Price: Refined high oleic sunflower oil: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Refined soybean oil: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Refined soybean oil: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Table olives, average of varieties: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Table olives, average of varieties: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Gordal variety:weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Gordal variety: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils

National Price: Hojiblanca variety: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Hojiblanca variety: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Manzanilla variety: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: Manzanilla variety: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category E: R-2	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg canal	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses
National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category E: R-2: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses
National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category E: R-3	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg canal	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses
National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals:	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses

Category E: R-3: weekly variation						
National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category E: R-4	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg canal	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses
National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category E: R-4: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses
National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category E: R	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg canal	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses
National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category E: R: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses
National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category E: O-2	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg canal	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses
National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category E: O-2: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses
National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category E: O-3	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg canal	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses

National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category E: 0-3: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses
National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category E: 0-4	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg canal	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses
National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category E: 0-4: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses
National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category E: 0	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg canal	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses
National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category E: 0: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses
National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category Z: U-2	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg canal	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses
National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category Z: U-2: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses

National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category Z: U-3	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg canal	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses
National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category Z: U-3: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses
National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category Z: U	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg canal	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses
National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category Z: U: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses
National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category Z: R-2	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg canal	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses
National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category Z: R-2: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses
National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category Z: R-3	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg canal	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses

National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category Z: R-3: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses
National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category Z: R	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg canal	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses
National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category Z: R: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses
National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category Z: O-2	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg canal	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses
National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category Z: O-2: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses
National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category Z: O-3	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg canal	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses
National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category Z: O-3: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses

National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category Z: O	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg canal	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses
National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category Z: O: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses
National Price: FRUIT: Orange Navel Group	Socioeconomic variable	€/100 kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: FRUIT: Orange Navel Group: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: FRUIT: Orange Navel Group: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
Average prices of fresh or chilled sheep carcasses on national representative markets for the EU: REPRESENTATIVE MARKET - Lamb 9-19 kg: Barcelona: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Fresh or chilled Sheep Carcasses

Average prices of fresh or chilled sheep carcasses on national representative markets for the EU: REPRESENTATIVE MARKET - Lamb 9-19 kg: Madrid	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg canal	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Fresh or chilled Sheep Carcasses
National Price: FRUIT: Clementine	Socioeconomic variable	€/100 kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: FRUIT: Clementine: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: FRUIT: Clementine: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: FRUIT: Lemon	Socioeconomic variable	€/100 kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: FRUIT: Lemon: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: FRUIT: Lemon: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables

National Price: FRUIT: Mandarin	Socioeconomic variable	€/100 kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: FRUIT: Mandarin: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: FRUIT: Mandarin: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: FRUIT: Orange Group Blancas	Socioeconomic variable	€/100 kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: FRUIT: Orange Group Blancas: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: FRUIT: Orange Salustiana	Socioeconomic variable	€/100 kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: FRUIT: Orange Salustiana: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: FRUIT: Orange Salustiana: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: FRUIT: Orange Navel Group	Socioeconomic variable	€/100 kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils

National Price: FRUIT: Orange Navel Group: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: FRUIT: Orange Navel Group: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of cereals, Rice, Oilseeds, Oil Cakes, Proteins, Wines and Oils
National Price: FRUIT: Navel Orange	Socioeconomic variable	€/100 kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: FRUIT: Navel Orange: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: FRUIT: Navel Orange: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: FRUIT: Navelina orange	Socioeconomic variable	€/100 kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: FRUIT: Navelina orange: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: FRUIT: Navelina orange: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables

National Price: FRUIT: Apple Fuji	Socioeconomic variable	€/100 kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: FRUIT: Apple Fuji: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: FRUIT: Apple Fuji: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: FRUIT: Apple Gala	Socioeconomic variable	€/100 kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: FRUIT: Apple Gala: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: FRUIT: Apple Gala: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: FRUIT: Apple Golden	Socioeconomic variable	€/100 kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: FRUIT: Apple Golden: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: FRUIT: Apple Golden: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables

National Price: FRUIT: Apple Granny Smith	Socioeconomic variable	€/100 kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: FRUIT: Apple Granny Smith: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: FRUIT: Apple Granny Smith: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: FRUIT: Apple Red Delicious and other red apples	Socioeconomic variable	€/100 kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: FRUIT: Apple Red Delicious and other red apples: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: FRUIT: Apple Red Delicious and other red apples: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: FRUIT: White Pear	Socioeconomic variable	€/100 kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: FRUIT: White	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables

Pear: weekly variation						
National Price: FRUIT: White Pear: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: FRUIT: Conference Pear	Socioeconomic variable	€/100 kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: FRUIT: Conference Pear: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: FRUIT: Conference Pear: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: FRUIT: Avocado	Socioeconomic variable	€/100 kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: FRUIT: Avocado: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: FRUIT: Avocado: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: FRUIT: Persimmon	Socioeconomic variable	€/100 kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables

National Price: FRUIT: Persimmon: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: FRUIT: Persimmon: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: FRUIT: Pomegranate	Socioeconomic variable	€/100 kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: FRUIT: Pomegranate: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: FRUIT: Pomegranate: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: FRUIT: Banana	Socioeconomic variable	€/100 kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: FRUIT: Banane: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: FRUIT: Banana: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables

National Price: VEGETABLES: Chard	Socioeconomic variable	€/100 kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: VEGETABLES: Chard: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: VEGETABLES: Chard: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: VEGETABLES: Dried garlic	Socioeconomic variable	€/100 kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: VEGETABLES: Dried garlic: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: VEGETABLES: Dried garlic: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: VEGETABLES: Artichoke	Socioeconomic variable	€/100 kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: VEGETABLES: Artichoke: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables

National Price: VEGETABLES: Artichoke: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: VEGETABLES: Aubergine	Socioeconomic variable	€/100 kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: VEGETABLES: Aubergine: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: VEGETABLES: Aubergine: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: VEGETABLES: Broccoli	Socioeconomic variable	€/100 kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: VEGETABLES: Broccoli : weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: VEGETABLES: Broccoli : weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: VEGETABLES: Courgette	Socioeconomic variable	€/100 kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: VEGETABLES:	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables

Courgette: weekly variation						
National Price: VEGETABLES: Courgette: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: VEGETABLES: Onion	Socioeconomic variable	€/100 kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: VEGETABLES: Onion: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: VEGETABLES: Onion: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: VEGETABLES: Mushroom	Socioeconomic variable	€/100 kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: VEGETABLES: Mushroom: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: VEGETABLES: Mushroom: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: VEGETABLES: Cauliflower	Socioeconomic variable	€/100 kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables

National Price: VEGETABLES: Cauliflower: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: VEGETABLES: Cauliflower: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: VEGETABLES: Endive	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 u	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: VEGETABLES: Endive: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: VEGETABLES: Endive: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: VEGETABLES: Spinach	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: VEGETABLES: Spinach: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: VEGETABLES: Spinach: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables

National Price: VEGETABLES: Green bean	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: VEGETABLES: Green bean: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: VEGETABLES: Green bean: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: VEGETABLES: Green flat bean	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: VEGETABLES: Green flat bean: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: VEGETABLES: Green flat bean: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: VEGETABLES: Romaine lettuce	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 u	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: VEGETABLES: Romaine lettuce: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables

National Price: VEGETABLES: Romaine lettuce: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: VEGETABLES: Cucumber	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: VEGETABLES: Cucumber: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: VEGETABLES: Cucumber: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: VEGETABLES: Italian green pepper	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: VEGETABLES: Italian green pepper: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: VEGETABLES: Italian green pepper: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: VEGETABLES: Leek	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables

National Price: VEGETABLES: Leek: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: VEGETABLES: Leek: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: VEGETABLES: Cherry tomato	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: VEGETABLES: Cherry tomato: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: VEGETABLES: Cherry tomato: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: VEGETABLES: Cluster tomato	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: VEGETABLES: Cluster tomato: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: VEGETABLES: Cluster tomato: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables

National Price: VEGETABLES: Tomato, round, smooth	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: VEGETABLES: Tomato, round, smooth: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: VEGETABLES: Tomato, round, smooth: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: VEGETABLES: Carrot	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: VEGETABLES: Carrot: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: VEGETABLES: Carrot: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: VEGETABLES: Potato	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National Price: VEGETABLES: Potato: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables

National Price: VEGETABLES: Potato: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables
National prices for carcasses of adult bovine animals: Category A: U: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices for Heavy Bovine Carcasses
National Average Live Cattle Prices: Males up to 480 kg live	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg live	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Pries for Live bovine Carcasses
National Average Live Cattle Prices: Males up to 480 kg live: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Pries for Live bovine Carcasses
National Average Live Cattle Prices: Males over 480 kg live	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg live	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Pries for Live bovine Carcasses
National Average Live Cattle Prices: Males over 480 kg live: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Pries for Live bovine Carcasses
National Average Live Cattle Prices: Females that have calved	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg live	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Pries for Live bovine Carcasses

National Average Live Cattle Prices: Females that have calved: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Pries for Live bovine Carcasses
National Average Live Cattle Prices: Other females up to 380 kg live	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg live	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Pries for Live bovine Carcasses
National Average Live Cattle Prices: Other females up to 380 kg live: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Pries for Live bovine Carcasses
National Average Live Cattle Prices: Other female bovines over 380 kg live	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg live	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Pries for Live bovine Carcasses
National Average Live Cattle Prices: Other female bovines over 380 kg live: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Pries for Live bovine Carcasses
National Average Prices of Other Bovine Animals: CALVES 8 DAYS TO 4 WEEKS: Friesian male	Socioeconomic variable	€/ head	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Other bovine animals

National Average Prices of Other Bovine Animals: CALVES 8 DAYS TO 4 WEEKS: Friesian male: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Other bovine animals
National Average Prices of Other Bovine Animals: CALVES 8 DAYS TO 4 WEEKS: Male crossbred	Socioeconomic variable	€/ head	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Other bovine animals
National Average Prices of Other Bovine Animals: CALVES 8 DAYS TO 4 WEEKS: Male crossbred: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Other bovine animals
National Average Prices of Other Bovine Animals: CALVES 8 DAYS TO 4 WEEKS: Friesian female	Socioeconomic variable	€/ head	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Other bovine animals
National Average Prices of Other Bovine Animals: CALVES 8 DAYS TO 4 WEEKS: Friesian female: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Other bovine animals

National Average Prices of Other Bovine Animals: CALVES 8 DAYS TO 4 WEEKS: Female crossbred	Socioeconomic variable	€/ head	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Other bovine animals
National Average Prices of Other Bovine Animals: CALVES 8 DAYS TO 4 WEEKS: Female crossbred: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Other bovine animals
National Average Prices of Other Bovine Animals: CALVES 8 DAYS TO 4 WEEKS: National weighted average	Socioeconomic variable	€/ head	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Other bovine animals
National Average Prices of Other Bovine Animals: CALVES 8 DAYS TO 4 WEEKS: National weighted average: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Other bovine animals
National Average Prices of Other Bovine Animals: CALVES 6 TO 12 MONTHS OLD: Friesian male	Socioeconomic variable	basis 200 kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Other bovine animals

National Average Prices of Other Bovine Animals: CALVES 6 TO 12 MONTHS OLD: Friesian male: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Other bovine animals
National Average Prices of Other Bovine Animals: CALVES 6 TO 12 MONTHS OLD: Male crossbred	Socioeconomic variable	basis 200 kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Other bovine animals
National Average Prices of Other Bovine Animals: CALVES 6 TO 12 MONTHS OLD: Male crossbred: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Other bovine animals
National Average Prices of Other Bovine Animals: CALVES 6 TO 12 MONTHS OLD: Friesian female	Socioeconomic variable	basis 200 kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Other bovine animals
National Average Prices of Other Bovine Animals: CALVES 6 TO 12 MONTHS OLD: Friesian female: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Other bovine animals

National Average Prices of Other Bovine Animals: CALVES 6 TO 12 MONTHS OLD: Female crossbred	Socioeconomic variable	basis 200 kg	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Other bovine animals
National Average Prices of Other Bovine Animals: CALVES 6 TO 12 MONTHS OLD: Female crossbred: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Other bovine animals
National Average Prices of Other Bovine Animals: CALVES 6 TO 12 MONTHS OLD: National weighted average	Socioeconomic variable	€/100 Kg live	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Other bovine animals
National Average Prices of Other Bovine Animals: CALVES 6 TO 12 MONTHS OLD: National weighted average: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Other bovine animals
National Price: BEEF: Heifers, 180-300 kg	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg carcass	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Price: BEEF: Heifers,	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products

180-300 kg: weekly variation						
National Price: BEEF: Heifers, 180-300 kg: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Price: BEEF: Males 12 to 24 months (Class R)	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg carcass	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Price: BEEF: Males 12 to 24 months (Class R): weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Price: BEEF: Males 12 to 24 months (Class R): weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Price: BEEF: Animals from 8 to 12 months (Class R)	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg carcass	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Price: BEEF: Animals from 8 to 12 months (Class R): weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Price: BEEF: Animals from 8 to 12	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products

months (Class R): weekly variation (%)						
National Price: BEEF: Live cattle, all categories	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg live	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Price: BEEF: Live cattle, all categories: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Price: BEEF: Live cattle, all categories: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Price: BEEF: LAMB: Lambs 9-19 kilos: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Price: BEEF: LAMB: Lambs 9-19 kilos: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Price: LAMB: Lambs 9- 19 kilos	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg carcass	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Price: FRUIT: Orange Group Blancas: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices at Origin of fruits and Vegetables

National Price: LAMB: Lambs 12-16 kilos	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg carcass	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Price: LAMB: Lambs 12-16 kilos: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Price: LAMB: Lambs 12-16 kilos: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Price: LAMB: Light lambs (12-13 kilos)	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg carcass	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Price: LAMB: Light lambs (12-13 kilos): weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Price: LAMB: Light lambs (12-13 kilos): weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Price: LAMB: Heavy lambs (13-16 kilos)	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg carcass	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Price: LAMB: Heavy lambs (13-16	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products

kilos): weekly variation						
National Price: LAMB: Heavy lambs (13-16 kilos): weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Price: SWINE: Pigs >60% lean (Class S)	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg carcass	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Price: SWINE: Pigs >60% lean (Class S): weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Price: SWINE: Pigs >60% lean (Class S): weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Price: SWINE: Pigs 60-55% lean (Class E)	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg carcass	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Price: SWINE: Pigs 60-55% lean (Class E): weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Price: SWINE: Pigs 60-55% lean (Class E): weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products

National Price: SWINE: Pigs 55-50% lean (Class U)	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg carcass	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Price: SWINE: Pigs 55-50% lean (Class U): weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Price: SWINE:Pigs 55-50% lean (Class U): weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Price: SWINE: Pig 50-45% lean (Class R)	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg carcass	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Price: SWINE: Pig 50-45% lean (Class R): weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Price: SWINE: Pig 50-45% lean (Class R): weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Price: SWINE: Piglet 20 kg	Socioeconomic variable	€/ unit	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products

National Price: SWINE: Piglet 20 kg: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Price: SWINE: Piglet 20 kg: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Price: CHICKEN: Chicken, average carcasses 83% and 65% loss on average: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Price: CHICKEN: Chicken, average carcasses 83% and 65% loss on average: weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Price: CHICKEN: Chicken, average carcasses 83% and 65% loss on average	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg carcass	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Price: CHICKEN: Chicken P10 (83% rdto.)	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg carcass	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products

National Price: CHICKEN: Chicken P10 (83% rdto.): weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Price: CHICKEN: Chicken P10 (83% rdto.): weekly variation (%)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Livestock Products
National Average Prices of Fresh or Chilled Sheep Carcasses: Lambs I (12 to 13 kg/carcass): weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Fresh or chilled Sheep Carcasses
National Average Prices of Fresh or Chilled Sheep Carcasses: Lambs I (12 to 13 kg/carcass)	Socioeconomic variable	kg/carcas	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Fresh or chilled Sheep Carcasses
National Average Prices of Fresh or Chilled Sheep Carcasses: Lambs II (13.1 to 16 kg/carcass)	Socioeconomic variable	kg/carcas	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Fresh or chilled Sheep Carcasses
National Average Prices of Fresh or Chilled Sheep Carcasses: Lambs II (13.1 to 16	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Fresh or chilled Sheep Carcasses

kg/carcass): weekly variation						
National Average Prices of Fresh or Chilled Sheep Carcasses: Weighted average	Socioeconomic variable	kg/carcas	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Fresh or chilled Sheep Carcasses
National Average Prices of Fresh or Chilled Sheep Carcasses: Weighted average: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Fresh or chilled Sheep Carcasses
Average prices of fresh or chilled sheep carcasses on national representative markets for the EU: REPRESENTATIVE MARKET - Lamb 9-19 kg: Barcelona	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg canal	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Fresh or chilled Sheep Carcasses
Average prices of fresh or chilled sheep carcasses on national representative markets for the EU: REPRESENTATIVE MARKET - Lamb 9-19 kg: Madrid: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Fresh or chilled Sheep Carcasses

Average prices of fresh or chilled sheep carcasses on national representative markets for the EU: REPRESENTATIVE MARKET - Lamb 9-19 kg: Valencia	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg canal	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Fresh or chilled Sheep Carcasses
Average prices of fresh or chilled sheep carcasses on national representative markets for the EU: REPRESENTATIVE MARKET - Lamb 9-19 kg: Valencia: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Fresh or chilled Sheep Carcasses
Average prices of fresh or chilled sheep carcasses on national representative markets for the EU: REPRESENTATIVE MARKET - Lamb 9-19 kg: Albacete	Socioeconomic variable	€/ 100 Kg canal	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	National Average Prices of Fresh or chilled Sheep Carcasses
Average Prices in Representative Provincial Markets for	Socioeconomic variable	€/Kg live	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Provincial Representative Markets for Fattening Pigs

Fattening Pigs: SELECT (lower fat level): Barcelona						
Average Prices in Representative Provincial Markets for Fattening Pigs: SELECT (lower fat level): Barcelona: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Provincial Representative Markets for Fattening Pigs
Average Prices in Representative Provincial Markets for Fattening Pigs: SELECT (lower fat level): Huesca	Socioeconomic variable	€/Kg live	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Provincial Representative Markets for Fattening Pigs
Average Prices in Representative Provincial Markets for Fattening Pigs: SELECT (lower fat level): Huesca: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Provincial Representative Markets for Fattening Pigs
Average Prices in Representative Provincial Markets for Fattening Pigs: SELECT (lower fat level): Lleida	Socioeconomic variable	€/Kg live	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Provincial Representative Markets for Fattening Pigs

Average Prices in Representative Provincial Markets for Fattening Pigs: SELECT (lower fat level): Lleida: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Provincial Representative Markets for Fattening Pigs
Average Prices in Representative Provincial Markets for Fattening Pigs: SELECT (lower fat level): Murcia	Socioeconomic variable	€/Kg live	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Provincial Representative Markets for Fattening Pigs
Average Prices in Representative Provincial Markets for Fattening Pigs: SELECT (lower fat level): Murcia: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Provincial Representative Markets for Fattening Pigs
Average Prices in Representative Provincial Markets for Fattening Pigs: SELECT (lower fat level): Pontevedra	Socioeconomic variable	€/Kg live	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Provincial Representative Markets for Fattening Pigs
Average Prices in Representative Provincial Markets for Fattening Pigs:	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Provincial Representative Markets for Fattening Pigs

SELECT (lower fat level): Pontevedra: weekly variation						
Average Prices in Representative Provincial Markets for Fattening Pigs: SELECT (lower fat level): Salamanca	Socioeconomic variable	€/Kg live	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Provincial Representative Markets for Fattening Pigs
Average Prices in Representative Provincial Markets for Fattening Pigs: SELECT (lower fat level): Salamanca: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Provincial Representative Markets for Fattening Pigs
Average Prices in Representative Provincial Markets for Fattening Pigs: SELECT (lower fat level): Segovia	Socioeconomic variable	€/Kg live	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Provincial Representative Markets for Fattening Pigs
Average Prices in Representative Provincial Markets for Fattening Pigs: SELECT (lower fat level): Segovia: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Provincial Representative Markets for Fattening Pigs

Average Prices in Representative Provincial Markets for Fattening Pigs: SELECT (lower fat level): Zaragoza	Socioeconomic variable	€/Kg live	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Provincial Representative Markets for Fattening Pigs
Average Prices in Representative Provincial Markets for Fattening Pigs: SELECT (lower fat level): Zaragoza: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Provincial Representative Markets for Fattening Pigs
Average Prices in Representative Provincial Markets for Fattening Pigs: NORMAL (normal level of fat): Zaragoza	Socioeconomic variable	€/Kg live	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Provincial Representative Markets for Fattening Pigs
Average Prices in Representative Provincial Markets for Fattening Pigs: NORMAL (normal level of fat): Zaragoza: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Provincial Representative Markets for Fattening Pigs

Average Prices in Representative Provincial Markets for Fattening Pigs: NORMAL (normal level of fat): Segovia	Socioeconomic variable	€/Kg live	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Provincial Representative Markets for Fattening Pigs
Average Prices in Representative Provincial Markets for Fattening Pigs: NORMAL (normal level of fat): Segovia: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Provincial Representative Markets for Fattening Pigs
Average Prices in Representative Provincial Markets for Fattening Pigs: FAT (higher fat level): Segovia	Socioeconomic variable	€/Kg live	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Provincial Representative Markets for Fattening Pigs
Average Prices in Representative Provincial Markets for Fattening Pigs: FAT (higher fat level): Segovia: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Provincial Representative Markets for Fattening Pigs

Average Prices in Representative Provincial Markets for Fattening Pigs: FAT (higher fat level): Zaragoza	Socioeconomic variable	€/Kg live	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Provincial Representative Markets for Fattening Pigs
Average Prices in Representative Provincial Markets for Fattening Pigs: FAT (higher fat level): Zaragoza: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Provincial Representative Markets for Fattening Pigs
Average Prices in Representative Provincial Markets for Fattening Pigs: FAT (higher fat level): Salamanca	Socioeconomic variable	€/Kg live	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Provincial Representative Markets for Fattening Pigs
Average Prices in Representative Provincial Markets for Fattening Pigs: FAT (higher fat level): Salamanca: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Provincial Representative Markets for Fattening Pigs
Average Prices in Representative Provincial Markets for Fattening Pigs:	Socioeconomic variable	€/Kg live	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Provincial Representative Markets for Fattening Pigs

NORMAL (normal level of fat): Salamanca						
Average Prices in Representative Provincial Markets for Fattening Pigs: NORMAL (normal level of fat): Salamanca: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Provincial Representative Markets for Fattening Pigs
Average Prices in Representative Provincial Markets for Fattening Pigs: NORMAL (normal level of fat): Pontevedra	Socioeconomic variable	€/Kg live	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Provincial Representative Markets for Fattening Pigs
Average Prices in Representative Provincial Markets for Fattening Pigs: FAT (higher fat level): Pontevedra: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Provincial Representative Markets for Fattening Pigs
Average Prices in Representative Provincial Markets for Fattening Pigs: FAT (higher fat	Socioeconomic variable	€/Kg live	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Provincial Representative Markets for Fattening Pigs

level): Pontevedra:						
Average Prices in Representative Provincial Markets for Fattening Pigs: NORMAL (normal level of fat): Pontevedra: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Provincial Representative Markets for Fattening Pigs
Average Prices in Representative Provincial Markets for Fattening Pigs: NORMAL (normal level of fat): Murcia	Socioeconomic variable	€/Kg live	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Provincial Representative Markets for Fattening Pigs
Average Prices in Representative Provincial Markets for Fattening Pigs: NORMAL (normal level of fat): Murcia: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Provincial Representative Markets for Fattening Pigs
Average Prices in Representative Provincial Markets for Fattening Pigs:	Socioeconomic variable	€/Kg live	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Provincial Representative Markets for Fattening Pigs

FAT (higher fat level): Murcia						
Average Prices in Representative Provincial Markets for Fattening Pigs: FAT (higher fat level): Murcia: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Provincial Representative Markets for Fattening Pigs
Average Prices in Representative Provincial Markets for Fattening Pigs: NORMAL (normal level of fat): Lleida	Socioeconomic variable	€/Kg live	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Provincial Representative Markets for Fattening Pigs
Average Prices in Representative Provincial Markets for Fattening Pigs: FAT (higher fat level): Lleida	Socioeconomic variable	€/Kg live	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Provincial Representative Markets for Fattening Pigs
Average Prices in Representative Provincial Markets for Fattening Pigs: FAT (higher fat level): Lleida: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Provincial Representative Markets for Fattening Pigs

Average Prices in Representative Provincial Markets for Fattening Pigs: NORMAL (normal level of fat): Huesca	Socioeconomic variable	€/Kg live	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Provincial Representative Markets for Fattening Pigs
Average Prices in Representative Provincial Markets for Fattening Pigs: NORMAL (normal level of fat): Huesca: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Provincial Representative Markets for Fattening Pigs
Average Prices in Representative Provincial Markets for Fattening Pigs: FAT (higher fat level): Huesca	Socioeconomic variable	€/Kg live	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Provincial Representative Markets for Fattening Pigs
Average Prices in Representative Provincial Markets for Fattening Pigs: FAT (higher fat level): Huesca: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Provincial Representative Markets for Fattening Pigs

Average Prices in Representative Provincial Markets for Fattening Pigs: NORMAL (normal level of fat): Barcelona	Socioeconomic variable	€/Kg live	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Provincial Representative Markets for Fattening Pigs
Average Prices in Representative Provincial Markets for Fattening Pigs: NORMAL (normal level of fat): Barcelona: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Provincial Representative Markets for Fattening Pigs
Average Prices in Representative Provincial Markets for Fattening Pigs: FAT (higher fat level): Barcelona	Socioeconomic variable	€/Kg live	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Provincial Representative Markets for Fattening Pigs
Average Prices in Representative Provincial Markets for Fattening Pigs: FAT (higher fat level): Barcelona: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices in Provincial Representative Markets for Fattening Pigs

Average Prices for Precocious Pigs, Piglets and Other Qualities: cull sows	Socioeconomic variable	€/Kg live	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices of Precocious Pigs, Piglets and Other Grades
Average Prices for Precocious Pigs, Piglets and Other Qualities: cull sows: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices of Precocious Pigs, Piglets and Other Grades
Average Prices for Precocious Pigs, Piglets and Other Qualities: Fattened pigs Category U	Socioeconomic variable	€/Kg live	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices of Precocious Pigs, Piglets and Other Grades
Average Prices for Precocious Pigs, Piglets and Other Qualities: Fattened pigs Category U: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices of Precocious Pigs, Piglets and Other Grades
Average Prices for Precocious Pigs, Piglets and Other Qualities: Piglets Segovia (Base weight 20kg)	Socioeconomic variable	€/Kg live	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices of Precocious Pigs, Piglets and Other Grades
Average Prices for Precocious Pigs, Piglets and Other Qualities: Piglets	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices of Precocious Pigs, Piglets and Other Grades

Segovia (Base weight 20kg): weekly variation						
Average Prices for Precocious Pigs, Piglets and Other Qualities: Piglets Lleida (Base weight 20kg)	Socioeconomic variable	€/Kg live	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices of Precocious Pigs, Piglets and Other Grades
Average Prices for Precocious Pigs, Piglets and Other Qualities: Piglets Lleida (Base weight 20kg): weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices of Precocious Pigs, Piglets and Other Grades
Average Prices for Precocious Pigs, Piglets and Other Qualities: Piglets National average. Normal quality. Base weight 20kg.	Socioeconomic variable	€/Kg live	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices of Precocious Pigs, Piglets and Other Grades
Average Prices for Precocious Pigs, Piglets and Other Qualities: Piglets National average. Normal quality. Base weight 20kg.: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices of Precocious Pigs, Piglets and Other Grades
Average Pig Prices: Iberian Pork Trunks:	Socioeconomic variable	€/Kg live	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices of Pigs: Iberian Trunks

Tostones From 5 to 9 kilos						
Average Pig Prices: Iberian Pork Trunks: Tostones From 5 to 9 kilos: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices of Pigs: Iberian Trunks
Average Pig Prices: Iberian Pork Trunks: Tostones From 9 to 12 kilos	Socioeconomic variable	€/Kg live	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices of Pigs: Iberian Trunks
Average Pig Prices: Iberian Pork Trunks: Tostones From 9 to 12 kilos: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices of Pigs: Iberian Trunks
Average Pig Prices: Iberian Pork Trunks: Lechón Ibérico Cruzado Base 23 kg	Socioeconomic variable	€/Kg live	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices of Pigs: Iberian Trunks
Average Pig Prices: Iberian Pork Trunks: Lechón Ibérico Cruzado Base 23 kg: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices of Pigs: Iberian Trunks

Average Pig Prices: Iberian Pork Trunks: Iberian Marranos from 35 to 60 kg	Socioeconomic variable	€/Kg live	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices of Pigs: Iberian Trunks
Average Pig Prices: Iberian Pork Trunks: Iberian Marranos from 35 to 60 kg: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices of Pigs: Iberian Trunks
Average Pig Prices: Iberian Pork Trunks: Iberian Primales from 60 to 100 kg	Socioeconomic variable	€/Kg live	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices of Pigs: Iberian Trunks
Average Pig Prices: Iberian Pork Trunks: Iberian Primales from 60 to 100 kg: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices of Pigs: Iberian Trunks
Average Pig Prices: Iberian Pork Trunks: Fattened Pigs (Intensive)	Socioeconomic variable	€/Kg live	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices of Pigs: Iberian Trunks
Average Pig Prices: Iberian Pork Trunks: Fattened Pigs (Intensive): weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices of Pigs: Iberian Trunks

Average Pig Prices: Iberian Pork Trunks: Free-range Fattened Pigs (Extensive Fattening)	Socioeconomic variable	€/Kg live	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices of Pigs: Iberian Trunks
Average Pig Prices: Iberian Pork Trunks: Free-range Fattened Pigs (Extensive Fattening): weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices of Pigs: Iberian Trunks
Average Pig Prices: Iberian Pork Trunks: 100% Iberian Acorn-fed Fattened Acorn-fed Pigs	Socioeconomic variable	€/Kg live	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices of Pigs: Iberian Trunks
Average Pig Prices: Iberian Pork Trunks: 100% Iberian Acorn-fed Fattened Acorn-fed Pigs: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices of Pigs: Iberian Trunks
Average Pig Prices: Iberian Pork Trunks:	Socioeconomic variable	€/Kg live	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices of Pigs: Iberian Trunks

Breeders for culling						
Average Pig Prices: Iberian Pork Trunks: Breeders for culling : weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices of Pigs: Iberian Trunks
Average Pig Prices: Iberian Pork Trunks: Breeders >6 months	Socioeconomic variable	€/Kg live	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices of Pigs: Iberian Trunks
Average Pig Prices: Iberian Pork Trunks: Breeders >6 months: weekly variation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Average	Weekly	Average Prices of Pigs: Iberian Trunks

Agricultural Census: Rural development and equipment for the production of renewable energy: Agricultural holdings which have benefitted from some measure in the last 3 years

General information

Description: Census. Collection of information regarding the agrarian structure, to serve as the basis for the directory of agricultural operations, in compliance with the legal regulations established by the European Union

Producer: Spanish National Statistics Institute

Link: https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106

Languages: Spanish | Castilian

Catalogue:

Subjects: agricultural product, agricultural region, agricultural statistics

Useful for the analysis of: Use of agricultural area

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: National Statistics Institute (Spain)

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Spain

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 18, 2022

Characterization created at: December 15, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2009

Last update: November 3, 2011

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2009

Keywords: agricultural area

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Agricultural Census	Excel XLSX	Public	https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural holding	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Use of consultancy services	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - November, 2011	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Diversification towards non-agricultural activities	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - November, 2011	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding

Development of tourist activities	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - November, 2011	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Modernisation of agricultural holdings	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - November, 2011	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Increase in the added value of agricultural and forestry products	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - November, 2011	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Compliance with the standards established in the community guidelines	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - November, 2011	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Involvement in programmes relating to food quality	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - November, 2011	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Natura 2000 subsidies to agricultural areas	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - November, 2011	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Payments linked to the directive relating to the water framework	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - November, 2011	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Payments relating to	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - November, 2011	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding

organic agriculture						
Payments relating to other agro-environmental aid	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - November, 2011	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Aid relating to animal welfare	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - November, 2011	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding

Agricultural Census: Rural development and equipment for the production of renewable energy: Equipment for production of renewable energy

General information

Description: Census. Collection of information regarding the agrarian structure, to serve as the basis for the directory of agricultural operations, in compliance with the legal regulations established by the European Union

Producer: Spanish National Statistics Institute

Link: https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106

Languages: Spanish | Castilian

Catalogue:

Subjects: agricultural product, agricultural region, agricultural statistics

Useful for the analysis of: Use of agricultural area

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: National Statistics Institute (Spain)

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Spain

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 18, 2022

Characterization created at: December 15, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2009

Last update: November 3, 2011

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2009

Keywords: agricultural area

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Agricultural Census	Excel XLSX	Public	https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural holding	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
All types	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - November, 2011	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Wind energy	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - November, 2011	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding

Bio-methane energy	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - November, 2011	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Other biomass energy	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - November, 2011	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Solar energy	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - November, 2011	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Water energy	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - November, 2011	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Other sources	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - November, 2011	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding

AREA-RICA - Livestock farming report (ANALISI SETTORIALE ALLEVAMENTI)

General information

Description: This database contains data about livestock farming in Italy from 2008 to 2019, divided into regions.

Producer: AREA-RICA

Link: https://arearica.crea.gov.it/report_e.php

Languages: Italian

Catalogue: RICA - report

Subjects: livestock farming, Environment, Economy and finance

Useful for the analysis of: Livestock farming, Price policy

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Year

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: AREA-RICA

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Italy

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: December 17, 2021

Characterization created at: December 9, 2021

Issued:

Last update: December 31, 2019

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2008 - December, 2019

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Excel	Excel XLS	Public	https://arearica.crea.gov.it/report_e.php	Excel XLS	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Mules and hinnies	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Geonames	95	
Deers	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Geonames	95	
Caprine animals	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Geonames	95	
Fur animals	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Geonames	95	
Quails	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Geonames	95	
Ovines	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Geonames	95	
Other cervids	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Geonames	95	
Hares	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Geonames	95	
Turkeys	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Geonames	95	

Ostriches	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Geonames	95	
Horses	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Geonames	95	
Chickens	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Geonames	95	
Wild boars	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Geonames	95	
Ducks	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Geonames	95	
Other birds	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Geonames	95	
Rabbits	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Geonames	95	
Grouses	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Geonames	95	
Partridges	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Geonames	95	
Donkeys	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Geonames	95	
Bovine animals	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Geonames	95	
Buffaloes	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Geonames	95	
Roe deers	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Geonames	95	
Guinea fowls	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Geonames	95	
Geese	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Geonames	95	

Swines	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Geonames	95	
Pigeons	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Geonames	95	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Gross profit of stable (Utile lordo di stalla)	Socioeconomic variable	€/UBA	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Hares, Other birds, Mules and hinnies, Other cervids, Turkeys, Ostriches, Ducks, Caprine animals, Horses, Deers, Chickens, Fur animals, Wild boars, Quails, Donkeys, Bovine animals, Buffaloes, Rabbits, Grouses, Partridges, Roe deers, Guinea fowls, Geese, Swines, Ovines, Pigeons
Specific costs (Costi specifici)	Socioeconomic variable	€/UBA	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Hares, Other birds, Mules and hinnies, Other cervids, Turkeys, Ostriches, Ducks, Caprine animals, Horses, Deers, Chickens, Fur animals, Wild boars, Quails, Donkeys, Bovine animals, Buffaloes, Rabbits, Grouses, Partridges, Roe deers, Guinea fowls, Geese, Swines, Ovines, Pigeons
Gross margin (Margine lordo)	Socioeconomic variable	€/UBA	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Hares, Other birds, Mules and hinnies, Other cervids, Turkeys, Ostriches, Ducks, Caprine animals, Horses, Deers, Chickens, Fur animals, Wild boars, Quails, Donkeys, Bovine animals, Buffaloes, Rabbits, Grouses, Partridges, Roe

						deers, Guinea fowls, Geese, Swines, Ovines, Pigeons
Operating margin (Margine operativo)	Socioeconomic variable	€/UBA	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Hares, Other birds, Mules and hinnies, Other cervids, Turkeys, Ostriches, Ducks, Caprine animals, Horses, Deers, Chickens, Fur animals, Wild boars, Quails, Donkeys, Bovine animals, Buffaloes, Rabbits, Grouses, Partridges, Roe deers, Guinea fowls, Geese, Swines, Ovines, Pigeons
Observations (Osservazioni)	Socioeconomic variable	nr	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Hares, Other birds, Mules and hinnies, Other cervids, Turkeys, Ostriches, Ducks, Caprine animals, Horses, Deers, Chickens, Fur animals, Wild boars, Quails, Donkeys, Bovine animals, Buffaloes, Rabbits, Grouses, Partridges, Roe deers, Guinea fowls, Geese, Swines, Ovines, Pigeons
Adult bovine unit (Unità bovina adulta UBA)	Socioeconomic variable	nr	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Hares, Other birds, Mules and hinnies, Other cervids, Turkeys, Ostriches, Ducks, Caprine animals, Horses, Deers, Chickens, Fur animals, Wild boars, Quails, Donkeys, Bovine animals, Buffaloes, Rabbits, Grouses, Partridges, Roe deers, Guinea fowls, Geese, Swines, Ovines, Pigeons
Consistency of animal (Consistenza capi)	Socioeconomic variable	nr	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Wild boars, Quails, Donkeys, Bovine animals, Buffaloes, Rabbits, Grouses, Partridges, Roe deers, Guinea fowls, Geese, Swines, Ovines, Pigeons, Hares, Other birds, Mules and hinnies, Other cervids,

						Turkeys, Ostriches, Ducks, Caprine animals, Horses, Deers, Chickens, Fur animals
Consistency of animal (milk herds) (Consistenza capi di cui capi da latte)	Socioeconomic variable	nr	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Hares, Other birds, Mules and hinnies, Other cervids, Turkeys, Ostriches, Ducks, Caprine animals, Horses, Deers, Chickens, Fur animals, Wild boars, Quails, Donkeys, Bovine animals, Buffaloes, Rabbits, Grouses, Partridges, Roe deers, Guinea fowls, Geese, Swines, Ovines, Pigeons
Total gross production (Produzione lorda totale)	Socioeconomic variable	€/UBA	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Hares, Other birds, Mules and hinnies, Other cervids, Turkeys, Ostriches, Ducks, Caprine animals, Horses, Deers, Chickens, Fur animals, Wild boars, Quails, Donkeys, Bovine animals, Buffaloes, Rabbits, Grouses, Partridges, Roe deers, Guinea fowls, Geese, Swines, Ovines, Pigeons
Gross saleable production (Produzione lorda vendibile)	Socioeconomic variable	€/UBA	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Hares, Other birds, Mules and hinnies, Other cervids, Turkeys, Ostriches, Ducks, Caprine animals, Horses, Deers, Chickens, Fur animals, Wild boars, Quails, Donkeys, Bovine animals, Buffaloes, Rabbits, Grouses, Partridges, Roe deers, Guinea fowls, Geese, Swines, Ovines, Pigeons
Reused/transformed production (Produzione reimpiegata/trasformata)	Socioeconomic variable	€/UBA	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Hares, Other birds, Mules and hinnies, Other cervids, Turkeys, Ostriches, Ducks, Caprine animals, Horses, Deers, Chickens, Fur animals, Wild boars, Quails,

						Donkeys, Bovine animals, Buffaloes, Rabbits, Grouses, Partridges, Roe deers, Guinea fowls, Geese, Swines, Ovines, Pigeons
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Agricultural Census: Work on the exploitation: Family labour: individual owners and agricultural managers according to age and sex

General information

Description: Census. Collection of information regarding the agrarian structure, to serve as the basis for the directory of agricultural operations, in compliance with the legal regulations established by the European Union

Producer: Spanish National Statistics Institute

Link: https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106

Languages: Spanish | Castilian

Catalogue:

Subjects: agricultural product, agricultural region, agricultural statistics

Useful for the analysis of: Use of agricultural area

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: National Statistics Institute (Spain)

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Spain

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 18, 2022

Characterization created at: December 15, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2009

Last update: November 3, 2011

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2009

Keywords: agricultural area

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Agricultural Census	Excel XLSX	Public	https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural holding	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
From 45 to 54 years old: Owners: Female	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
From 45 to 54 years old: Owners: Male	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding

From 55 to 64 years old: Manager-owners: Both genders	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
From 35 to 44 years old: Manager-owners: Both genders	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
From 35 to 44 years old: Manager-owners: Female	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
From 35 to 44 years old: Manager-owners: Male	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
From 25 to 34 years old: Owners: Both genders	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
From 25 to 34 years old: Owners: Female	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
From 25 to 34 years old: Owners: Male	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
All ages: Owners: Both genders	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding

All ages: Owners: Female	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
All ages: Owners: Male	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
All age: Manager- owners: Both genders	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
All ages: Manager- owners: Female	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
All ages: Manager- owners: Male	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
From 45 to 54 years old: Manager- owners: Female	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
From 55 to 64 years old: Owners: Female	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
From 45 to 54 years old: Manager- owners: Male	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
From 45 to 54 years old: Owners: Both genders	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Under 25 years old: Manager-	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding

owners: Both genders						
Under 25 years old: Manager-owners: Female	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Under 25 years old: Manager-owners: Male	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Under 25 years old: Owners: Both genders	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Under 25 years old: Owners: Female	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Under 25 years old: Owners: Male	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
From 25 to 34 years old: Manager-owners: Both genders	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
From 25 to 34 years old: Manager-owners: Female	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
From 25 to 34 years old: Manager-owners: Male	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
From 35 to 44 years old:	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding

Owners: Both genders						
From 35 to 44 years old: Owners: Female	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
From 35 to 44 years old: Owners: Male	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
From 45 to 54 years old: Manager-owners: Both genders	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
From 55 to 64 years old: Owners: Male	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
From 65 years of age and over: Manager-owners: Both genders	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
From 65 years of age and over: Manager-owners: Female	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
From 65 years of age and over: Manager-owners: Male	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
From 65 years of age and over:	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding

Owners: Both genders						
From 65 years of age and over: Owners: Female	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
From 65 years of age and over: Owners: Male	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
From 55 to 64 years old: Owners: Both genders	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
From 55 to 64 years old: Manager-owners: Male	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
From 55 to 64 years old: Manager-owners: Female	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding

Agricultural Census: Work on the exploitation: Number of people according to sex and percentage time worked

General information

Description: Census. Collection of information regarding the agrarian structure, to serve as the basis for the directory of agricultural operations, in compliance with the legal regulations established by the European Union

Producer: Spanish National Statistics Institute

Link: https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106

Languages: Spanish | Castilian

Catalogue:

Subjects: agricultural product, agricultural region, agricultural statistics

Useful for the analysis of: Use of agricultural area

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: National Statistics Institute (Spain)

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Spain

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 18, 2022

Characterization created at: December 15, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2009

Last update: November 3, 2011

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2009

Keywords: agricultural area

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Agricultural Census	Excel XLSX	Public	https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural holding	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Percentage of time worked >= 25 to < 50% (Both genders)	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Percentage of time worked >= 50 to < 75% (Male)	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding

Percentage of time worked >= 50 to < 75% (Female)	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Percentage of time worked >= 50 to < 75% (Agricultural holdings)	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Percentage of time worked >= 50 to < 75% (Both genders)	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Percentage of time worked >= 75 to < 100% (Male)	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Percentage of time worked >= 75 to < 100% (Female)	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Percentage of time worked >= 75 to < 100% (Agricultural holdings)	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Percentage of time worked >= 75 to < 100% (Both genders)	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Percentage of time worked 100 % (Male)	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding

Percentage of time worked 100 % (Female)	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Percentage of time worked 100 % (Agricultural holdings)	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Percentage of time worked 100 % (Both genders)	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Percentage of time worked < 25% (Agricultural holdings)	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Percentage of time worked < 25% (Both genders)	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Percentage of time worked >= 25 to < 50% (Agricultural holdings)	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Percentage of time worked < 25% (Male)	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Percentage of time worked < 25% (Female)	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding

Percentage of time worked >= 25 to < 50% (Male)	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Percentage of time worked >= 25 to < 50% (Female)	Socioeconomic variable	Number of persons	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding

Agricultural Census: Work on the exploitation: Permanent paid labour: agricultural managers according to age and days worked

General information

Description: Census. Collection of information regarding the agrarian structure, to serve as the basis for the directory of agricultural operations, in compliance with the legal regulations established by the European Union

Producer: Spanish National Statistics Institute

Link: https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106

Languages: Spanish | Castilian

Catalogue:

Subjects: agricultural product, agricultural region, agricultural statistics

Useful for the analysis of: Use of agricultural area

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: National Statistics Institute (Spain)

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Spain

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 18, 2022

Characterization created at: December 15, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2009

Last update: November 3, 2011

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2009

Keywords: agricultural area

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Agricultural Census	Excel XLSX	Public	https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural holding	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
From 65 years of age and over: Male	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural managers	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
From 55 to 64 years old: Owners: Both genders	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural managers	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding

All age: manager owners: Female	Socioeconomic variable	Operation number	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
All age: manager owners: Male	Socioeconomic variable	Operation number	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
From 55 to 64 years old: Male	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural managers	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
From 45 to 54 years old: Female	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural managers	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
From 45 to 54 years old: Male	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural managers	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
From 55 to 64 years old: Both genders	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural managers	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
From 35 to 44 years old: Both genders	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural managers	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
All ages: Total number of days for both genders	Socioeconomic variable	Number of days	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
From 65 years of age and over: Male	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural managers	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
From 65 years of age and over: Both genders	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural managers	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding

From 65 years of age and over: Female	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural managers	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Under 25 years old: Total number of days for both genders	Socioeconomic variable	Number of days	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
From 25 to 34 years old: Total number of days for both genders	Socioeconomic variable	Number of days	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
From 35 to 44 years old: Total number of days for both genders	Socioeconomic variable	Number of days	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
From 35 to 44 years old: Male	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural managers	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
From 45 to 54 years old: Both genders	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural managers	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
From 55 to 64 years old: Female	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural managers	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
From 55 to 64 years old: Male	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural managers	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding

From 65 years of age and over: Both genders	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural managers	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
From 35 to 44 years old: Female	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural managers	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
From 35 to 44 years old: Male	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural managers	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
From 25 to 34 years old: Both genders	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural managers	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
From 25 to 34 years old: Female	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural managers	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
From 25 to 34 years old: Male	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural managers	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
All ages: Both genders	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural managers	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
All ages: Female	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural managers	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
All ages: Male	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural managers	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
All ages: Both genders	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural managers	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding

From 45 to 54 years old: Female	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural managers	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
From 45 to 54 years old: Male	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural managers	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
From 45 to 54 years old: Both genders	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural managers	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Under 25 years old: Both genders	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural managers	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Under 25 years old: Female	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural managers	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Under 25 years old: Male	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural managers	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Under 25 years old: Both genders	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural managers	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Under 25 years old: Female	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural managers	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Under 25 years old: Male	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural managers	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
From 25 to 34 years old: Both genders	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural managers	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding

From 25 to 34 years old: Female	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural managers	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
From 25 to 34 years old: Male	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural managers	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
From 35 to 44 years old: Both genders	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural managers	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
From 55 to 64 years old: Female	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural managers	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
From 35 to 44 years old: Female	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural managers	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
From 65 years of age and over: Female	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural managers	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
From 45 to 54 years old: Total number of days for both genders	Socioeconomic variable	Number of days	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
From 55 to 64 years old: Total number of days for both genders	Socioeconomic variable	Number of days	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
From 65 years of age and over: Total number of	Socioeconomic variable	Number of days	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding

days for both genders						
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National Soil Erosion Inventory (INES) (for Spain). Potential erosion (laminar and runoff)

General information

Description: Provide homogeneous and comparable statistical information on soil erosion processes in the national territory

To serve as coordination instrument for the forestal policies and the soil conservation of the autonomous communities, national territory and EU.

To provide information to delimit the priority actuation areas in the fight against erosion

Producer: Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food

Link: <https://www.mapa.gob.es/es/estadistica/temas/publicaciones/anuario-de-estadistica/2017/default.aspx?parte=2&capitulo=12&grupo=7>

Languages: Spanish | Castilian

Catalogue:

Subjects: soil resources, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Land use, Soil

Useful for the analysis of: land use

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type:

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: ES423, ES432, ES425, ES533, ES523, ES532, ES422, ES431, ES421, ES531, ES521, ES620, ES613, ES616, ES615, ES618, ES614, ES611, ES617, ES612, ES630, ES640, ES708, ES707, ES704, ES709, ES706, ES705, ES703, ES112, ES120, ES130, ES213, ES212, ES220, ES413, ES211, ES414, ES241, ES513, ES114, ES412, ES243, ES230, ES113, ES512, ES511, ES418, ES419, ES417, ES416, ES514, ES242, ES424, ES415, ES300, ES411, ES522

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 13, 2022

Characterization created at: December 15, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2016

Last update: December 31, 2016

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2016 - December, 2016

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
National soil erosion inventory (INES)LAMINAR EROSION AND EROSION IN REGUEROS: Surface areas and soil losses according to erosion levels	PDF	Public	https://confluence.agricore-project.eu/pages/viewpage.action?pageId=8946440	PDF	False
National soil erosion inventory (INES)LAMINAR EROSION AND EROSION IN REGUEROS: Surface areas and soil losses according to erosion levels	Excel XLS	Public	https://confluence.agricore-project.eu/pages/viewpage.action?pageId=8946440	Excel XLS	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Erodible surface (t.ha-1.year-1)	January, 2016 - December, 2016	NUTS3	100	
Surface water bodies and wetlands (t.ha-1.year-1)	January, 2016 - December, 2016	NUTS3	100	
Artificial surfaces (t.ha-1.year-1)	January, 2016 - December, 2016	NUTS3	100	
Erosion Level 0-5 (t.ha-1 year-1)	January, 2016 - December, 2016	NUTS3	100	
Erosion Level 5 to 10 (t.ha-1 year-1)	January, 2016 - December, 2016	NUTS3		
Erosion Level 25 to 50 (t.ha-1 year-1)	January, 2016 - December, 2016	NUTS3	100	
Erosion Level 10 to 25 (t.ha-1 year-1)	January, 2016 - December, 2016	NUTS3		
Erosion Level 50 to100 (t.ha-1 year-1)	January, 2016 - December, 2016	NUTS3	100	
Erosion Level >200 (t.ha-1 year-1)	January, 2016 - December, 2016	NUTS3	100	
Erosion Level 100 to200 (t.ha-1 year-1)	January, 2016 - December, 2016	NUTS3	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Climatic resilience of vegetation-Low (percentages)	Socioeconomic variable	(percentages)	January, 2016 - December, 2016	Instant value	Annual	Erosion Level 0-5 (t.ha-1 year-1), Erosion Level 5 to 10 (t.ha-1 year-1), Erosion Level 25 to 50 (t.ha-1 year-1), Erosion Level 10 to 25 (t.ha-1 year-1), Erosion Level 50 to100 (t.ha-1 year-1), Erosion Level 100 to200 (t.ha-1 year-1), Erodible

						surface (t.ha-1.year-1), Surface water bodies and wetlands (t.ha-1.year-1, Artificial surfaces (t.ha-1.year-1, Erosion Level >200 (t.ha-1 year-1)
Climatic resilience of vegetation-half (Hectares)	Socioeconomic variable	(Hectares)	January, 2016 - December, 2016	Instant value	Annual	Erosion Level 0-5 (t.ha-1 year-1), Erosion Level 5 to 10 (t.ha-1 year-1), Erosion Level 25 to 50 (t.ha-1 year-1), Erosion Level 10 to 25 (t.ha-1 year-1), Erosion Level 50 to100 (t.ha-1 year-1), Erosion Level 100 to200 (t.ha-1 year-1), Erodible surface (t.ha-1.year-1), Surface water bodies and wetlands (t.ha-1.year-1, Artificial surfaces (t.ha-1.year-1, Erosion Level >200 (t.ha-1 year-1)
Climatic resilience of vegetation-Half (percentages)	Socioeconomic variable	(percentages)	January, 2016 - December, 2016	Instant value	Annual	Erosion Level 0-5 (t.ha-1 year-1), Erosion Level 5 to 10 (t.ha-1 year-1), Erosion Level 25 to 50 (t.ha-1 year-1), Erosion Level 10 to 25 (t.ha-1 year-1), Erosion Level 50 to100 (t.ha-1 year-1), Erosion Level 100 to200 (t.ha-1 year-1), Erodible surface (t.ha-1.year-1), Surface water bodies and wetlands (t.ha-1.year-1, Artificial surfaces (t.ha-1.year-1, Erosion Level >200 (t.ha-1 year-1)
Climatic resilience of vegetation-High (percentages)	Socioeconomic variable	(percentages)	January, 2016 - December, 2016	Instant value	Annual	Erosion Level 0-5 (t.ha-1 year-1), Erosion Level 5 to 10 (t.ha-1 year-1), Erosion Level 25 to 50 (t.ha-1 year-1), Erosion Level 10 to 25 (t.ha-1 year-1), Erosion Level 50 to100 (t.ha-1 year-1), Erosion Level 100 to200 (t.ha-1 year-1), Erodible surface (t.ha-1.year-1), Surface water bodies and wetlands (t.ha-1.year-1, Artificial surfaces (t.ha-1.year-1, Erosion Level >200 (t.ha-1 year-1)

Climatic resilience of vegetation-High (Hectares)	Socioeconomic variable	(Hectares)	January, 2016 - December, 2016	Instant value	Annual	Erosion Level 0-5 (t.ha-1 year-1), Erosion Level 5 to 10 (t.ha-1 year-1), Erosion Level 25 to 50 (t.ha-1 year-1), Erosion Level 10 to 25 (t.ha-1 year-1), Erosion Level 50 to100 (t.ha-1 year-1), Erosion Level 100 to200 (t.ha-1 year-1), Erodible surface (t.ha-1.year-1), Surface water bodies and wetlands (t.ha-1.year-1, Artificial surfaces (t.ha-1.year-1, Erosion Level >200 (t.ha-1 year-1)
Geographical Area (Hectares)	Socioeconomic variable	(Hectares)	January, 2016 - December, 2016	Instant value	Annual	Erosion Level 0-5 (t.ha-1 year-1), Erosion Level 5 to 10 (t.ha-1 year-1), Erosion Level 25 to 50 (t.ha-1 year-1), Erosion Level 10 to 25 (t.ha-1 year-1), Erosion Level 50 to100 (t.ha-1 year-1), Erosion Level 100 to200 (t.ha-1 year-1), Erodible surface (t.ha-1.year-1), Surface water bodies and wetlands (t.ha-1.year-1, Artificial surfaces (t.ha-1.year-1, Erosion Level >200 (t.ha-1 year-1)
Geographical Area (Percentages)	Socioeconomic variable	(Percentages)	January, 2016 - December, 2016	Instant value	Annual	Erosion Level 0-5 (t.ha-1 year-1), Erosion Level 5 to 10 (t.ha-1 year-1), Erosion Level 25 to 50 (t.ha-1 year-1), Erosion Level 10 to 25 (t.ha-1 year-1), Erosion Level 50 to100 (t.ha-1 year-1), Erosion Level 100 to200 (t.ha-1 year-1), Erodible surface (t.ha-1.year-1), Surface water bodies and wetlands (t.ha-1.year-1, Artificial surfaces (t.ha-1.year-1, Erosion Level >200 (t.ha-1 year-1)
Climatic resilience of vegetation-Low (Hectares)	Socioeconomic variable	(Hectares)	January, 2016 - December, 2016	Instant value	Annual	Erosion Level 0-5 (t.ha-1 year-1), Erosion Level 5 to 10 (t.ha-1 year-1), Erosion Level 25 to 50 (t.ha-1 year-1), Erosion Level 10 to 25 (t.ha-1 year-1), Erosion Level 50 to100 (t.ha-1 year-1), Erosion

						Level 100 to200 (t.ha-1 year-1), Erodeble surface (t.ha-1.year-1), Surface water bodies and wetlands (t.ha-1.year-1, Artificial surfaces (t.ha-1.year-1, Erosion Level >200 (t.ha-1 year-1)
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Standard Results of the Greek FADN

General information

Description: The Farm Accountancy Data Network is monitoring relevant Greek agricultural statistics since 1981. It concerns the annual sampling of input-output accounting data from 4,675 agricultural holdings from all over Greece, for the purpose of estimating technical-economic variables for the European Commission

Producer: EUROPEAN COMMISSION

Link: <https://agridata.ec.europa.eu/extensions/FADNPublicDatabase/FADNPublicDatabase.html>

Languages: English

Catalogue: FADN Public database (SO)

Subjects: agricultural holdings, accounting, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Farm Structure

Useful for the analysis of: Agricultural costs, Agricultural value added, Agriculture policy

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Interactive resource

Was generated by: annual sampling

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Malta, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 11, 2022

Characterization created at: January 11, 2022

Issued:

Last update: November 30, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2004 - December, 2019

Keywords: agricultural holdings, agricultural economy

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Excel workbooks	Excel XLSX	Public	https://agridata.ec.europa.eu/extensions/FADNPublicDatabase/FADNPublicDatabase.html	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural Holdings	January, 2004 - January, 2019	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
(SYS03)Sample farms	Socioeconomic variable		January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
(SE027)Permanent crops	Socioeconomic variable	Ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
(SE028)Permanent grassland	Socioeconomic variable	Ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings

(SE035)Cereals	Socioeconomic variable	Ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
(SE041)Other field crops	Socioeconomic variable	Ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
(SE042)Energy crops	Socioeconomic variable	Ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
(SE046)Vegetables and flowers	Socioeconomic variable	Ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
(SE050)Vineyards	Socioeconomic variable	Ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
(SE055)Orchards	Socioeconomic variable	Ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
(SE060)Olive groves	Socioeconomic variable	Ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
(SE065)Other permanent crops	Socioeconomic variable	Ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
(SE054)Permanent crops other than vineyards	Socioeconomic variable	Ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
(SE071)Forage crops	Socioeconomic variable	Ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings

(SE072)Agricultural fallows without any subsidies	Socioeconomic variable	Ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
(SE073)Set aside	Socioeconomic variable	Ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
(SE074)Total agricultural area out of production	Socioeconomic variable	Ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
(SE075)Woodland area	Socioeconomic variable	Ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
(SE080)Total livestock units	Socioeconomic variable	LU	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
(SE085)Dairy cows (incl. buffaloes)	Socioeconomic variable	LU	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
(SE086)Cattle dairy cows	Socioeconomic variable	LU	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
(SE087)Buffalo dairy cows	Socioeconomic variable	LU	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
(SE090)Other cattle	Socioeconomic variable	LU	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
(SE095)Sheep and goats	Socioeconomic variable	LU	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings

(SE100)Pigs	Socioeconomic variable	LU	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
(SE10)Poultry	Socioeconomic variable	LU	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
(SE110)Yield of wheat	Socioeconomic variable	q / ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
(SE115)Yield of maize	Socioeconomic variable	q / ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
(SE120)Stocking density	Socioeconomic variable	q / LU	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
(SE125)Milk yield (incl. buffaloes')	Socioeconomic variable	kg/ cow	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
(SE126)Milk yield cattle dairy cows	Socioeconomic variable	kg/ cow	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
(SE127)Milk yield buffalo dairy cows	Socioeconomic variable	kg/ cow	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
(SE131)Total output	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
(SE132)Total output /Total input	Socioeconomic variable	Ratio	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings

(SE135)Total output crops and crop production	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
(SE136)Total crop output/ha production	Socioeconomic variable	€ / Ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
(SE140)Cereals	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
(SE145)Protein crops	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
(SE146)Energy crops	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
(SE150)Potatoes	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
(SE155)Sugar beet	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
(SE160)Oil-seed crops	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
(SE165)Industrial crops	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE170 Vegetables & flowers	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings

SE175	Fruit	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE180	Citrus fruit	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE185	Wine and grapes	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE190	Olives & olive oil	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE195	Forage crops	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE200	Other crop output	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE206	Total output livestock and livestock products	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE207	Total livestock output / LU	Socioeconomic variable	€ / LU	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE211	Change in value of livestock	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE216	Cows' milk and milk products (incl. buffaloes')	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings

SE220	Beef and veal	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE225	Pigmeat	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE230	Sheep and goats	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE235	Poultrymeat	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE240	Eggs	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE618	Subsidies sheep & goats	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE619	Other livestock subsidies	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE624	Total support for rural development	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE415M	Farm Net Value Added - MEDIAN	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Median	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE245	Ewes' and goats' milk	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings

SE251 Other livestock & products	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE256 Other output	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE700 Total OGA output	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE715 Forestry and wood processing	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE720 Contractual work (services)	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE725 Agritourism	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE260 Farmhouse consumption	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE265 Farm use	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE270 Total Inputs	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE275 Total intermediate consumption	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings

SE281	Total specific costs	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE284	Specific crop costs / ha	Socioeconomic variable	€ / Ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE420	Farm Net Income	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE285	Seeds and plants	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE290	Seeds and plants home-grown	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE295	Fertilisers	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE296	Fertiliser N	Socioeconomic variable	q	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE297	Fertiliser P	Socioeconomic variable	q	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE298	Fertiliser K	Socioeconomic variable	q	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE300	Crop protection	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings

SE305 Other crop specific costs	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE309 Specific livestock costs / LU	Socioeconomic variable	€ / LU	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE310 Feed for grazing livestock	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE320 Feed for pigs and poultry	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE325 Feed for pigs and poultry home-grown	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE330 Other livestock specific costs, incl. veterinary expenses	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE750 All specific costs for other gainful activities	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE331 Forestry specific costs	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE336 Total farming overheads	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE340 Machinery & building current costs	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings

SE345 Energy	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE350 Contract work	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE356 Other direct inputs	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE360 Depreciation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE365 Total external factors	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE370 Wages paid	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE375 Rent paid	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
(SYS02) Farms represented	Socioeconomic variable		January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
(SE005) Economic size	Socioeconomic variable	Total standard output in € / 1000	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
(SE010) Total labour input	Socioeconomic variable	AWU	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings

(SE015)Unpaid labour input	Socioeconomic variable	AWU	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
(SE020)Paid labour input	Socioeconomic variable	AWU	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
(SE011)Labour input	Socioeconomic variable	Hours	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
(SE022)Share of OGA work in total work	Socioeconomic variable	%	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
(SE025)Total Utilised Agricultural Area	Socioeconomic variable	Ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Sum	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
(SE030)Rented U.A.A.	Socioeconomic variable	Ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
(SE026)Arable land	Socioeconomic variable	Ha	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE380 Interest paid	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE381 Balance of interest paid and received	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE605 Total subsidies - excluding on investments	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings

SE606 Total Direct Payments	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE610 Total subsidies on crops	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE611 Compensatory payments/area payments	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE612 Set aside premiums	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE613 Other crops subsidies	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE615 Total subsidies on livestock	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE616 Subsidies dairying	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE617 Subsidies other cattle	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE621 Environmental subsidies	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE622 LFA subsidies	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings

SE623 Other rural development payments	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE625 Subsidies on intermediate consumption	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE626 Subsidies on external factors	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE630 Decoupled payments	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE631 Single Farm Payment and Basic Payment Scheme	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE632 Single Area payment	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE640 Additional aid	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE650 Total aid for Article 68	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE699 Other subsidies	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE600 Balance current subsidies and taxes	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings

SE390 Taxes	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE395 VAT balance excluding on investments	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE405 Balance subsidies and taxes on investment	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE406 Subsidies on investments	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE409 Subsidies on agricultural investments	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE407 Payments to dairy outgoers	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE408 Balance of VAT on investments	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE410 Gross Farm Income	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE415 Farm Net Value Added	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE425 Farm Net Value Added / AWU	Socioeconomic variable	€/ AWU	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings

SE425M Farm Net Value Added / AWU - MEDIAN	Socioeconomic variable	€/ AWU	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Median	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE430 Family Farm Income / FWU	Socioeconomic variable	€/ AWU	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE436 Total assets closing valuation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE437 Total assets, opening valuation	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE441 Total fixed assets	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE446 Land, permanent crops and quotas	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE450 Farm buildings	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE455 Machinery and equipment	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE460 Breeding livestock	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE465 Total current assets	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings

SE470 Non-breeding livestock	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE475 Stock of agricultural products	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE476 Inventories	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE480 Other circulating capital	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE485 Total liabilities	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE490 Long & medium-term loans	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE495 Short-term loans	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE501 Net worth	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE506 Change in net worth	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE510 Average farm capital	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings

SE516	Gross Investment on fixed assets	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE521	Net Investment on fixed assets	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE526	Cash Flow (1)	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE530	Cash Flow (2)	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
SE532	Cash flow / farm total capital	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2004 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings

National Soil Erosion Inventory (INES) (for Spain). EROSION IN GULLS AND RAVINES: Areas of erosion zones in gullies and ravines according to levels of sheet and gully erosion.

General information

Description: Provide homogeneous and comparable statistical information on soil erosion processes in the national territory

To serve as coordination instrument for the forestal policies and the soil conservation of the autonomous communities, national territory and EU.

To provide information to delimit the priority actuation areas in the fight against erosion

Producer: Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food

Link: <https://www.mapa.gob.es/es/estadistica/temas/publicaciones/anuario-de-estadistica/2017/default.aspx?parte=2&capitulo=12&grupo=7>

Languages: Spanish | Castilian

Catalogue:

Subjects: soil resources, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Land use, Soil

Useful for the analysis of: land use

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type:

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: ES423, ES432, ES425, ES533, ES523, ES532, ES422, ES431, ES421, ES531, ES521, ES620, ES613, ES616, ES615, ES618, ES614, ES611, ES617, ES612, ES630, ES640, ES708, ES707, ES704, ES709, ES706, ES705, ES703, ES112, ES120, ES130, ES213, ES212, ES220, ES413, ES211,

ES414, ES241, ES513, ES114, ES412, ES243, ES230, ES113, ES512, ES511, ES418, ES419, ES417, ES416, ES514, ES242, ES424, ES415, ES300, ES411, ES522

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 13, 2022

Characterization created at: December 15, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2016

Last update: December 31, 2016

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2016 - December, 2016

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
National soil erosion inventory (INES)LAMINAR EROSION AND EROSION IN REGUEROS: Surface areas and soil losses according to erosion levels	PDF	Public	https://www.mapa.gob.es/es/estadistica/temas/publicaciones/anuario-de-estadistica/2017/default.aspx?parte=2&capitulo=12&grupo=7	PDF	False
National soil erosion inventory (INES)LAMINAR EROSION AND EROSION IN REGUEROS: Surface areas and soil losses	Excel XLS	Public	https://www.mapa.gob.es/es/estadistica/temas/publicaciones/anuario-de-estadistica/2017/default.aspx?parte=2&capitulo=12&grupo=7	Excel XLS	False

according to erosion levels					
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Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Erodible surface (t.ha-1.year-1)	January, 2016 - December, 2016	NUTS3	100	
Erosion Level 0-5 (t.ha-1 year-1)	January, 2016 - December, 2016	NUTS3	100	
Erosion Level 5 to 10 (t.ha-1 year-1)	January, 2016 - December, 2016	NUTS3		
Erosion Level 25 to 50 (t.ha-1 year-1)	January, 2016 - December, 2016	NUTS3	100	
Erosion Level 10 to 25 (t.ha-1 year-1)	January, 2016 - December, 2016	NUTS3		
Erosion Level 50 to100 (t.ha-1 year-1)	January, 2016 - December, 2016	NUTS3	100	
Erosion Level >200 (t.ha-1 year-1)	January, 2016 - December, 2016	NUTS3	100	
Erosion Level 100 to200 (t.ha-1 year-1)	January, 2016 - December, 2016	NUTS3	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Erosionable surface (Hectares)	Socioeconomic variable	(hectares)	January, 2016 - December, 2016	Instant value	Annual	Erosion Level 0-5 (t.ha-1 year-1), Erosion Level 5 to 10 (t.ha-1 year-1), Erosion Level 25 to 50 (t.ha-1 year-1), Erosion Level 10 to 25 (t.ha-1 year-1), Erosion Level 50 to100 (t.ha-1 year-1), Erosion Level 100 to200 (t.ha-1 year-1), Erodible

						surface (t.ha-1.year-1), Erosion Level >200 (t.ha-1 year-1)
Erosion area in gullies and ravines (Hectares)	Socioeconomic variable	(hectares)	January, 2016 - December, 2016	Instant value	Annual	Erosion Level 0-5 (t.ha-1 year-1), Erosion Level 5 to 10 (t.ha-1 year-1), Erosion Level 25 to 50 (t.ha-1 year-1), Erosion Level 10 to 25 (t.ha-1 year-1), Erosion Level 50 to100 (t.ha-1 year-1), Erosion Level 100 to200 (t.ha-1 year-1), Erodible surface (t.ha-1.year-1), Erosion Level >200 (t.ha-1 year-1)
Erosion area in gullies and ravines (Percentages)	Socioeconomic variable	(Percentages)	January, 2016 - December, 2016	Instant value	Annual	Erosion Level 0-5 (t.ha-1 year-1), Erosion Level 5 to 10 (t.ha-1 year-1), Erosion Level 25 to 50 (t.ha-1 year-1), Erosion Level 10 to 25 (t.ha-1 year-1), Erosion Level 50 to100 (t.ha-1 year-1), Erosion Level 100 to200 (t.ha-1 year-1), Erodible surface (t.ha-1.year-1), Erosion Level >200 (t.ha-1 year-1)

National Soil Erosion Inventory (INES) (for Spain). MASS MOVEMENTS: Surface areas according to potential and predominant typology

General information

Description: Provide homogeneous and comparable statistical information on soil erosion processes in the national territory

To serve as coordination instrument for the forestal policies and the soil conservation of the autonomous communities, national territory and EU.

To provide information to delimit the priority actuation areas in the fight against erosion

Producer: Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food

Link: <https://www.mapa.gob.es/es/estadistica/temas/publicaciones/anuario-de-estadistica/2017/default.aspx?parte=2&capitulo=12&grupo=7>

Languages: Spanish | Castilian

Catalogue:

Subjects: soil resources, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Land use, Soil

Useful for the analysis of: land use

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type:

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: ES423, ES432, ES425, ES533, ES523, ES532, ES422, ES431, ES421, ES531, ES521, ES620, ES613, ES616, ES615, ES618, ES614, ES611, ES617, ES612, ES630, ES640, ES708, ES707, ES704, ES709, ES706, ES705, ES703, ES112, ES120, ES130, ES213, ES212, ES220, ES413, ES211,

ES414, ES241, ES513, ES114, ES412, ES243, ES230, ES113, ES512, ES511, ES418, ES419, ES417, ES416, ES514, ES242, ES424, ES415, ES300, ES411, ES522

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 13, 2022

Characterization created at: December 15, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2016

Last update: December 31, 2016

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2016 - December, 2016

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
National soil erosion inventory (INES)LAMINAR EROSION AND EROSION IN REGUEROS: Surface areas and soil losses according to erosion levels	PDF	Public	https://www.mapa.gob.es/es/estadistica/temas/publicaciones/anuario-de-estadistica/2017/default.aspx?parte=2&capitulo=12&grupo=7	PDF	False
National soil erosion inventory (INES)LAMINAR EROSION AND EROSION IN REGUEROS: Surface areas and soil losses	Excel XLS	Public	https://www.mapa.gob.es/es/estadistica/temas/publicaciones/anuario-de-estadistica/2017/default.aspx?parte=2&capitulo=12&grupo=7	Excel XLS	False

according to erosion levels					
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Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
General landslides	January, 2016 - December, 2016	NUTS3	100	
Landslides	January, 2016 - December, 2016	NUTS3	100	
Landslides and landslides in general	January, 2016 - December, 2016	NUTS3	100	
Landslides and flows	January, 2016 - December, 2016	NUTS3		
Complex or mixed	January, 2016 - December, 2016	NUTS3	100	
No typologies	January, 2016 - December, 2016	NUTS3	100	
Erodible surface	January, 2016 - December, 2016	NUTS3	100	
Surface water bodies and wetlands	January, 2016 - December, 2016	NUTS3	100	
Artificial surfaces	January, 2016 - December, 2016	NUTS3	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Potentiality. Low or	Socioeconomic variable	Percentages	January, 2016 - December, 2016	Instant value	Annual	General landslides, Landslides, Landslides and landslides in general, Landslides and flows, No typologies, Erodible surface,

moderate (Percentages)						Surface water bodies and wetlands, Complex or mixed
Potentiality.Low or moderate (Hectares)	Socioeconomic variable	(hectares)	January, 2016 - December, 2016	Instant value	Annual	General landslides, Landslides, Landslides and landslides in general, Landslides and flows, No typologies, Erodible surface, Surface water bodies and wetlands, Complex or mixed
Potentiality.Half (Hectares)	Socioeconomic variable	(hectares)	January, 2016 - December, 2016	Instant value	Annual	General landslides, Landslides, Landslides and landslides in general, Landslides and flows, No typologies, Erodible surface, Surface water bodies and wetlands, Complex or mixed
Potentiality.Half (Percentages)	Socioeconomic variable	(Percentages)	January, 2016 - December, 2016	Instant value	Annual	General landslides, Landslides, Landslides and landslides in general, Landslides and flows, No typologies, Erodible surface, Surface water bodies and wetlands, Complex or mixed
Potentiality. High (Hectares)	Socioeconomic variable	(hectares)	January, 2016 - December, 2016	Instant value	Annual	General landslides, Landslides, Landslides and landslides in general, Landslides and flows, No typologies, Erodible surface, Surface water bodies and wetlands, Complex or mixed
Potentiality.High (Percentages)	Socioeconomic variable	(Percentages)	January, 2016 - December, 2016	Instant value	Annual	General landslides, Landslides, Landslides and landslides in general, Landslides and flows, No typologies, Erodible surface, Surface water bodies and wetlands, Complex or mixed
Potentiality. Very High (Percentages)	Socioeconomic variable	(Percentages)	January, 2016 - December, 2016	Instant value	Annual	General landslides, Landslides, Landslides and landslides in general, Landslides and flows, No typologies, Erodible surface, Surface water bodies and wetlands, Complex or mixed

Geographical Area (Hectares)	Socioeconomic variable	(hectares)	January, 2016 - December, 2016	Instant value	Annual	General landslides, Landslides, Landslides and landslides in general, Landslides and flows, No typologies, Erodible surface, Surface water bodies and wetlands, Complex or mixed
Geographical Area (Percentages)	Socioeconomic variable	(Percentages)	January, 2016 - December, 2016	Instant value	Annual	General landslides, Landslides, Landslides and landslides in general, Landslides and flows, No typologies, Erodible surface, Surface water bodies and wetlands, Complex or mixed
Potentiality. Null or Very Low (Hectares)	Socioeconomic variable	(hectares)	January, 2016 - December, 2016	Instant value	Annual	General landslides, Landslides, Landslides and landslides in general, Landslides and flows, No typologies, Erodible surface, Surface water bodies and wetlands, Complex or mixed
Potentiality. Null or Very Low (Percentages)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentages	January, 2016 - December, 2016	Instant value	Annual	General landslides, Landslides, Landslides and landslides in general, Landslides and flows, No typologies, Erodible surface, Surface water bodies and wetlands, Complex or mixed
Potentiality. Very High (Hectares)	Socioeconomic variable	(hectares)	January, 2016 - December, 2016	Instant value	Annual	General landslides, Landslides, Landslides and landslides in general, Landslides and flows, No typologies, Erodible surface, Surface water bodies and wetlands, Complex or mixed

National Soil Erosion Inventory (INES) (for Spain). EROSION RISK IN WATERCOURSES

General information

Description: Provide homogeneous and comparable statistical information on soil erosion processes in the national territory

To serve as coordination instrument for the forestal policies and the soil conservation of the autonomous communities, national territory and EU.

To provide information to delimit the priority actuation areas in the fight against erosion

Producer: Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food

Link: <https://www.mapa.gob.es/es/estadistica/temas/publicaciones/anuario-de-estadistica/2017/default.aspx?parte=2&capitulo=12&grupo=7>

Languages: Spanish | Castilian

Catalogue:

Subjects: soil resources, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Land use, Soil

Useful for the analysis of: land use

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type:

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: ES423, ES432, ES425, ES533, ES523, ES532, ES422, ES431, ES421, ES531, ES521, ES620, ES613, ES616, ES615, ES618, ES614, ES611, ES617, ES612, ES630, ES640, ES708, ES707, ES704, ES709, ES706, ES705, ES703, ES112, ES120, ES130, ES213, ES212, ES220, ES413, ES211, ES414, ES241, ES513, ES114, ES412, ES243, ES230, ES113, ES512, ES511, ES418, ES419, ES417, ES416, ES514, ES242, ES424, ES415, ES300, ES411, ES522

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 13, 2022

Characterization created at: December 15, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2016

Last update: December 31, 2016

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2016 - December, 2016

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
National soil erosion inventory (INES)LAMINAR EROSION AND EROSION IN REGUEROS: Surface areas and soil losses according to erosion levels	PDF	Public	https://www.mapa.gob.es/es/estadistica/temas/publicaciones/anuario-de-estadistica/2017/default.aspx?parte=2&capitulo=12&grupo=7	PDF	False
National soil erosion inventory (INES)LAMINAR EROSION AND EROSION IN REGUEROS: Surface areas and soil losses according to erosion levels	Excel XLS	Public	https://www.mapa.gob.es/es/estadistica/temas/publicaciones/anuario-de-estadistica/2017/default.aspx?parte=2&capitulo=12&grupo=7	Excel XLS	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Medium	January, 2016 - December, 2016	NUTS3	100	
High	January, 2016 - December, 2016	NUTS3	100	
Very High	January, 2016 - December, 2016	NUTS3	100	
Low	January, 2016 - December, 2016	NUTS3	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Geographical Area(Percentages)	Socioeconomic variable	(Percentages)	January, 2016 - December, 2016	Instant value	Annual	Low, High, Very High, Medium
Geographical Area(Hectares)	Socioeconomic variable	(hectares)	January, 2016 - December, 2016	Instant value	Annual	Low, High, Very High, Medium

National Soil Erosion Inventory (INES) (for Spain). Wind erosion risk

General information

Description: Provide homogeneous and comparable statistical information on soil erosion processes in the national territory

To serve as coordination instrument for the forestal policies and the soil conservation of the autonomous communities, national territory and EU.

To provide information to delimit the priority actuation areas in the fight against erosion

Producer: Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food

Link: <https://www.mapa.gob.es/es/estadistica/temas/publicaciones/anuario-de-estadistica/2017/default.aspx?parte=2&capitulo=12&grupo=7>

Languages: Spanish | Castilian

Catalogue:

Subjects: soil resources, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Land use, Soil

Useful for the analysis of: land use

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type:

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: ES423, ES432, ES425, ES533, ES523, ES532, ES422, ES431, ES421, ES531, ES521, ES620, ES613, ES616, ES615, ES618, ES614, ES611, ES617, ES612, ES630, ES640, ES708, ES707, ES704, ES709, ES706, ES705, ES703, ES112, ES120, ES130, ES213, ES212, ES220, ES413, ES211, ES414, ES241, ES513, ES114, ES412, ES243, ES230, ES113, ES512, ES511, ES418, ES419, ES417, ES416, ES514, ES242, ES424, ES415, ES300, ES411, ES522

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 13, 2022

Characterization created at: December 15, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2016

Last update: December 31, 2016

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2016 - December, 2016

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
National soil erosion inventory (INES)LAMINAR EROSION AND EROSION IN REGUEROS: Surface areas and soil losses according to erosion levels	PDF	Public	https://www.mapa.gob.es/es/estadistica/temas/publicaciones/anuario-de-estadistica/2017/default.aspx?parte=2&capitulo=12&grupo=7	PDF	False
National soil erosion inventory (INES)LAMINAR EROSION AND EROSION IN REGUEROS: Surface areas and soil losses according to erosion levels	Excel XLS	Public	https://www.mapa.gob.es/es/estadistica/temas/publicaciones/anuario-de-estadistica/2017/default.aspx?parte=2&capitulo=12&grupo=7	Excel XLS	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Medium	January, 2016 - December, 2016	NUTS3	100	
High	January, 2016 - December, 2016	NUTS3	100	
Very High	January, 2016 - December, 2016	NUTS3	100	
Low	January, 2016 - December, 2016	NUTS3	100	
Very low	January, 2016 - December, 2016			
Erodible Surface	January, 2016 - December, 2016	NUTS3	100	
Surface water bodies and wetlands	January, 2016 - December, 2016	NUTS3	100	
Artificial surfaces	January, 2016 - December, 2016	NUTS3	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Geographical Area(Percentages)	Socioeconomic variable	(Percentages)	January, 2016 - December, 2016	Instant value	Annual	Low, High, Very High, Medium, Very low, Erodible Surface, Surface water bodies and wetlands, Artificial surfaces
Geographical Area(Hectares)	Socioeconomic variable	(hectares)	January, 2016 - December, 2016	Instant value	Annual	Low, High, Very High, Medium, Very low, Erodible Surface, Surface water bodies and wetlands, Artificial surfaces

Local Data Bank - Growing of crops - consumption of mineral fertilizers

General information

Description: The data refer to consumption of mineral fertilizers including mixed fertilizers.

Producer: Statistics Poland

Link: <https://bdl.stat.gov.pl/BDL/metadane/podgrupy/180>

Languages: English

Catalogue:

Subjects: fertiliser, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Agriculture policy

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Year

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Poland

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 7, 2022

Characterization created at: December 13, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2010

Last update: October 6, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2010 - December, 2020

Keywords: consumption of mineral fertilizers

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
CSV	CSV	Public		CSV	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLS	Public		Excel XLS	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Consumption of mineral fertilizers according to the new definition	January, 2010 - December, 2019	NUTS2	95	
Consumption of mineral fertilizers including mixed fertilizers per 1 ha of agricultural land according to the new definition PRELIMINARY DATA	January, 2020 - December, 2020	NUTS2	95	
Consumption of lime fertilizers according to the new definition	January, 2010 - December, 2019	NUTS2	95	
Consumption of calcium fertilizers per 1 ha of agricultural land according to the new definition	January, 2010 - December, 2019	NUTS2	95	
Consumption of lime fertilizers according to the	January, 2020 - December, 2020	NUTS2	95	

new definition PRELIMINARY DATA				
Consumption of lime fertilizers per 1 ha of agricultural land according to the new definition PRELIMINARY DATA	January, 2020 - December, 2020	NUTS2	95	
Consumption of mineral fertilizers including mixed fertilizers according to the new definition PRELIMINARY DATA	January, 2020 - December, 2020	NUTS2	95	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
consumption of lime fertilizers according to the new definition, in total	Socioeconomic variable	t	January, 2010 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Consumption of lime fertilizers according to the new definition
consumption of lime fertilizers according to the new definition - private farms	Socioeconomic variable	t	January, 2010 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Consumption of lime fertilizers according to the new definition
consumption of calcium fertilizers per 1 ha of agricultural land according to the	Socioeconomic variable	kg	January, 2010 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Consumption of calcium fertilizers per 1 ha of agricultural land according to the new definition

new definition - private farms						
consumption of calcium fertilizers per 1 ha of agricultural land according to the new definition - in total	Socioeconomic variable	kg	January, 2010 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Consumption of calcium fertilizers per 1 ha of agricultural land according to the new definition
consumption of calcium fertilizers per 1 ha of agricultural land according to the new definition - Agricultural land in good agricultural condition in total	Socioeconomic variable	kg	January, 2010 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Consumption of calcium fertilizers per 1 ha of agricultural land according to the new definition
consumption of calcium fertilizers per 1 ha of agricultural land according to the new definition - Agricultural land in good agricultural condition private farms	Socioeconomic variable	kg	January, 2010 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Consumption of calcium fertilizers per 1 ha of agricultural land according to the new definition

consumption of lime fertilizers according to the new definition PRELIMINARY DATA - private farms	Socioeconomic variable	thous. t	January, 2020 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Consumption of lime fertilizers according to the new definition PRELIMINARY DATA
consumption of lime fertilizers according to the new definition PRELIMINARY DATA - in total	Socioeconomic variable	thous. t	January, 2020 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Consumption of lime fertilizers according to the new definition PRELIMINARY DATA
consumption of lime fertilizers per 1 ha of agricultural land according to the new definition PRELIMINARY DATA - in total	Socioeconomic variable	kg	January, 2020 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Consumption of lime fertilizers per 1 ha of agricultural land according to the new definition PRELIMINARY DATA
consumption of lime fertilizers per 1 ha of agricultural land according to the new definition PRELIMINARY DATA - private farms	Socioeconomic variable	kg	January, 2020 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Consumption of lime fertilizers per 1 ha of agricultural land according to the new definition PRELIMINARY DATA
consumption of lime fertilizers per 1 ha of agricultural land according to the new definition PRELIMINARY DATA	Socioeconomic variable	kg	January, 2020 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Consumption of lime fertilizers per 1 ha of agricultural land according to the new definition PRELIMINARY DATA

new definition PRELIMINARY DATA - Agricultural land in good agricultural condition in total						
consumption of lime fertilizers per 1 ha of agricultural land according to the new definition PRELIMINARY DATA - Agricultural land in good agricultural condition - farms	Socioeconomic variable	kg	January, 2020 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Consumption of lime fertilizers per 1 ha of agricultural land according to the new definition PRELIMINARY DATA
consumption of mineral fertilizers according to the new definition (nitrogenous, phoshatic, potassic) in total	Socioeconomic variable	t	January, 2010 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Consumption of mineral fertilizers according to the new definition
consumption of mineral fertilizers according to the new definition -	Socioeconomic variable	t	January, 2010 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Consumption of mineral fertilizers according to the new definition

in total - nitrogenous						
consumption of mineral fertilizers according to the new definition - in total - phosphatic	Socioeconomic variable	t	January, 2010 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Consumption of mineral fertilizers according to the new definition
consumption of mineral fertilizers according to the new definition - in total - potassic	Socioeconomic variable	t	January, 2010 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Consumption of mineral fertilizers according to the new definition
consumption of mineral fertilizers according to the new definition (nitrogenous, phosphatic, potassic) in private farms	Socioeconomic variable	t	January, 2010 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Consumption of mineral fertilizers according to the new definition
consumption of mineral fertilizers according to the new definition - in private farms - nitrogenous	Socioeconomic variable	t	January, 2010 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Consumption of mineral fertilizers according to the new definition
consumption of mineral fertilizers according to the new definition	Socioeconomic variable	t	January, 2010 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Consumption of mineral fertilizers according to the new definition

fertilizers according to the new definition - in private farms - phosphatic						
consumption of mineral fertilizers according to the new definition - in private farms - potassic	Socioeconomic variable	t	January, 2010 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Consumption of mineral fertilizers according to the new definition
consumption of mineral fertilizers including mixed fertilizers according to the new definition PRELIMINARY DATA (nitrogenous, phosphatic, potassic) in total	Socioeconomic variable	thous. t	January, 2020 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Consumption of mineral fertilizers including mixed fertilizers according to the new definition PRELIMINARY DATA
consumption of mineral fertilizers including mixed fertilizers according to the new definition PRELIMINARY DATA - in total - nitrogenous	Socioeconomic variable	thous. t	January, 2020 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Consumption of mineral fertilizers including mixed fertilizers according to the new definition PRELIMINARY DATA

consumption of mineral fertilizers including mixed fertilizers according to the new definition PRELIMINARY DATA - in total - phosphatic	Socioeconomic variable	thous. t	January, 2020 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Consumption of mineral fertilizers including mixed fertilizers according to the new definition PRELIMINARY DATA
consumption of mineral fertilizers including mixed fertilizers according to the new definition PRELIMINARY DATA - in total - potassic	Socioeconomic variable	thous. t	January, 2020 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Consumption of mineral fertilizers including mixed fertilizers according to the new definition PRELIMINARY DATA
consumption of mineral fertilizers including mixed fertilizers according to the new definition PRELIMINARY DATA - in private farms - nitrogenous	Socioeconomic variable	thous. t	January, 2020 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Consumption of mineral fertilizers including mixed fertilizers according to the new definition PRELIMINARY DATA
consumption of mineral fertilizers including mixed	Socioeconomic variable	thous. t	January, 2020 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Consumption of mineral fertilizers including mixed fertilizers according to the new definition PRELIMINARY DATA

fertilizers according to the new definition PRELIMINARY DATA - in private farms - phosphatic						
consumption of mineral fertilizers including mixed fertilizers according to the new definition PRELIMINARY DATA - in private farms - potassic	Socioeconomic variable	thous. t	January, 2020 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Consumption of mineral fertilizers including mixed fertilizers according to the new definition PRELIMINARY DATA
consumption of mineral fertilizers including mixed fertilizers according to the new definition PRELIMINARY DATA (total of nitrogenous, phosphatic, potassic) in private farms	Socioeconomic variable	thous. t	January, 2020 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Consumption of mineral fertilizers including mixed fertilizers according to the new definition PRELIMINARY DATA

Local Data Bank - Growing of crops - crop production

General information

Description: The data refer to crops production area, yield from 1 ha and harvest.

Producer: Statistics Poland

Link: <https://bdl.stat.gov.pl/BDL/metadane/cechy/1423#>

Languages: English

Catalogue:

Subjects: crop production, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Crop production

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Year

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Poland

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 7, 2022

Characterization created at: December 16, 2021

Issued: January 1, 1999

Last update: September 23, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 1999 - December, 2020

Keywords: pastures lands, cereals, triticale, wheat, barley, rye, rape, potato, sugar beet, meadows, crop production

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
CSV	CSV	Public		CSV	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLS	Public		Excel XLS	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Crop production	January, 1999 - December, 2020			

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
barley - area in thous. ha - private farms	Socioeconomic variable	thous. ha	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
oats - area in thous. ha	Socioeconomic variable	thous. ha	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
oats - area in thous. ha - private farms	Socioeconomic variable	thous. ha	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
oats - crops from 1 ha	Socioeconomic variable	dt	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
oats - crops from 1 ha - private farms	Socioeconomic variable	dt	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production

oats - harvest	Socioeconomic variable	dt	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
oats - harvest - private farms	Socioeconomic variable	dt	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
triticale - area in thous. ha	Socioeconomic variable	thous. ha	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
triticale - area in thous. ha - private farms	Socioeconomic variable	thous. ha	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
triticale - crops from 1 ha	Socioeconomic variable	dt	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
triticale - crops from 1 ha - private farms	Socioeconomic variable	dt	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
triticale - harvest	Socioeconomic variable	dt	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
triticale - harvest - private farms	Socioeconomic variable	dt	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
mixed cereals - area in thous. ha	Socioeconomic variable	thous. ha	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
mixed cereals - area in thous. ha - private farms	Socioeconomic variable	thous. ha	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
mixed cereals - crops from 1 ha	Socioeconomic variable	dt	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
mixed cereals - crops from 1 ha - private farms	Socioeconomic variable	dt	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
mixed cereals - harvest	Socioeconomic variable	dt	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production

mixed cereals - harvest - private farms	Socioeconomic variable	dt	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
potatoes - area in thous. ha	Socioeconomic variable	thous. ha	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
potatoes - area in thous. ha - private farms	Socioeconomic variable	thous. ha	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
potatoes - crops from 1 ha	Socioeconomic variable	dt	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
potatoes - crops from 1 ha - private farms	Socioeconomic variable	dt	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
potatoes - harvest	Socioeconomic variable	dt	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
potatoes - harvest - private farms	Socioeconomic variable	dt	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
sugar beets - area in thous. ha	Socioeconomic variable	thous. ha	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
sugar beets - area in thous. ha - private farms	Socioeconomic variable	thous. ha	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
sugar beets - crops from 1 ha	Socioeconomic variable	dt	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
sugar beets - crops from 1 ha - private farms	Socioeconomic variable	dt	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
sugar beets - harvest	Socioeconomic variable	dt	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production

sugar beets - harvest - private farms	Socioeconomic variable	dt	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
rape and turnip rape - area in thous. ha	Socioeconomic variable	thous. ha	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
rape and turnip rape - area in thous. ha - private farms	Socioeconomic variable	thous. ha	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
rape and turnip rape - crops from 1 ha	Socioeconomic variable	dt	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
rape and turnip rape - harvest	Socioeconomic variable	dt	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
rape and turnip rape - harvest - private farms	Socioeconomic variable	dt	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
rape and turnip rape - crops from 1 ha - private farms	Socioeconomic variable	dt	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
permanent meadows - area in thous. ha	Socioeconomic variable	thous. ha	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
permanent meadows - area in thous. ha - private farms	Socioeconomic variable	thous. ha	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
permanent meadows - crops from 1 ha	Socioeconomic variable	dt	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production

permanent meadows - crops from 1 ha - private farms	Socioeconomic variable	dt	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
permanent meadows - harvest	Socioeconomic variable	dt	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
permanent meadows - harvest - private farms	Socioeconomic variable	dt	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
permanent pastures - area in thous. ha	Socioeconomic variable	thous. ha	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
permanent pastures - area in thous. ha - private farms	Socioeconomic variable	thous. ha	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
permanent pastures - crops from 1 ha	Socioeconomic variable	dt	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
permanent pastures - crops from 1 ha - private farms	Socioeconomic variable	dt	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
permanent pastures - harvest	Socioeconomic variable	dt	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
permanent pastures - harvest - private farms	Socioeconomic variable	dt	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production

cereals, grand total - area in thous. ha	Socioeconomic variable	thous. ha	January, 1999 - December, 2020	Instant value		Crop production
cereals, grand total - crops from 1 ha	Socioeconomic variable	dt	January, 1999 - December, 2020	Instant value		Crop production
cereals, grand total - harvest	Socioeconomic variable	dt	January, 1999 - December, 2020	Instant value		Crop production
cereals, grand total - area in thous. ha - private farms	Socioeconomic variable	thous. ha	January, 1999 - December, 2020	Instant value		Crop production
cereals, grand total - crops from 1 ha - private farms	Socioeconomic variable	dt	January, 1999 - December, 2020	Instant value		Crop production
cereals, grand total - harvest - private farms	Socioeconomic variable	dt	January, 1999 - December, 2020	Instant value		Crop production
basic and mixed cereals - area in thous. ha	Socioeconomic variable	thous. ha	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
basic and mixed cereals - crops from 1 ha	Socioeconomic variable	dt	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
basic and mixed cereals - harvest	Socioeconomic variable	dt	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
basic and mixed cereals - area in thous. ha - private farms	Socioeconomic variable	thous. ha	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production

basic and mixed cereals - crops from 1 ha - private farms	Socioeconomic variable	dt	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
basic and mixed cereals - harvest - private farms	Socioeconomic variable	dt	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
basic cereals - area in thous. ha	Socioeconomic variable	thous. ha	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
basic cereals - area in thous. ha - private farms	Socioeconomic variable	thous. ha	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
basic cereals - crops from 1 ha	Socioeconomic variable	dt	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
basic cereals - crops from 1 ha - private farms	Socioeconomic variable	dt	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
basic cereals - harvest	Socioeconomic variable	dt	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
basic cereals - harvest - private farms	Socioeconomic variable	dt	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
wheat - area in thous. ha	Socioeconomic variable	thous. ha	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
wheat - area in thous. ha - private farms	Socioeconomic variable	thous. ha	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
wheat - crops from 1 ha	Socioeconomic variable	dt	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production

wheat - crops from 1 ha - private farms	Socioeconomic variable	dt	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
wheat - harvest	Socioeconomic variable	dt	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
wheat - harvest - private farms	Socioeconomic variable	dt	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
rye - area in thous. ha	Socioeconomic variable	thous. ha	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
rye - area in thous. ha - private farms	Socioeconomic variable	thous. ha	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
rye - crops from 1 ha	Socioeconomic variable	dt	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
rye - crops from 1 ha - private farms	Socioeconomic variable	dt	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
rye - harvest	Socioeconomic variable	dt	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
rye - harvest - private farms	Socioeconomic variable	dt	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
barley - area in thous. ha	Socioeconomic variable	thous. ha	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
barley - crops from 1 ha	Socioeconomic variable	dt	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
barley - crops from 1 ha - private farms	Socioeconomic variable	dt	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
barley - harvest	Socioeconomic variable	dt	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production

barley - harvest - private farms	Socioeconomic variable	dt	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Crop production
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Local Data Bank - Growing of crops - Fruits and vegetables

General information

Description: The data refer to fruits and vegetables production area, and harvest.

Producer: Statistics Poland

Link: <https://bdl.stat.gov.pl/BDL/metadane/cechy/1457#>

Languages: English

Catalogue:

Subjects: vegetable, fruit, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Crop production

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Year

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Poland

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 7, 2022

Characterization created at: December 16, 2021

Issued: January 1, 1999

Last update: September 24, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 1999 - December, 2020

Keywords: vegetable and fruit area , vegetable and fruit harvest

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
CSV	CSV	Public		CSV	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLS	Public		Excel XLS	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Fruits and vegetables	January, 1999 - December, 2020			

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
field vegetables - total area in ha	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Fruits and vegetables
field vegetables - harvest in total	Socioeconomic variable	dt	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Fruits and vegetables
field vegetables - area in ha - private farms	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Fruits and vegetables
field vegetables - harvest - private farms	Socioeconomic variable	dt	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Fruits and vegetables
tree fruits - total area in ha	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Fruits and vegetables

tree fruits - harvest in total	Socioeconomic variable	dt	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Fruits and vegetables
tree fruits - area in ha - private farms	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Fruits and vegetables
tree fruits - harvest - private farms	Socioeconomic variable	dt	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Fruits and vegetables
berry fruits - total area in ha	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Fruits and vegetables
berry fruits - harvest in total	Socioeconomic variable	dt	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Fruits and vegetables
berry fruits - area in ha - private farms	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Fruits and vegetables
berry fruits - harvest - private farms	Socioeconomic variable	dt	January, 1999 - December, 2020			Fruits and vegetables

National State of the Environment Reports

General information

Description: Regional state of the environment reports are prepared by 16 voivodship inspectors of environmental protection for area of voivodship (province) at least every three years. The detailed frequency is established individually by each voivodship inspector in voivodship environmental monitoring programme. The verified data and information obtained in the course of the state environmental monitoring in voivodship is the core of the assessment of the environment at regional level.

Producer: Chief Inspector of Environmental Protection

Link: <https://www.gios.gov.pl/en/state-of-the-environment/state-of-the-environment-reports>

Languages: Polish

Catalogue:

Subjects: environmental monitoring, environmental protection, Environment

Useful for the analysis of: Environmental policy

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution:

Resource type:

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Poland

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 7, 2022

Characterization created at: December 16, 2021

Issued: December 31, 1993

Last update: December 31, 2018

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: December, 1993 - December, 2018

Keywords: biodiversity, state of environment, resources, protected species and areas

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
State of Environment in Poland Reports	PDF	Public	https://www.gios.gov.pl/en/state-of-the-environment/state-of-the-environment-reports	PDF	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
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Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
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Agricultural Drought Monitoring System

General information

Description: The Agricultural Drought Monitoring System (ADMS) is designed to identify areas where there are crop losses caused by drought conditions, which are listed in the "Act on subsidies to insurance of agricultural crops and farm animals".

In the ADMS, meteorological conditions that are causing drought are evaluated by the climatic water balance (CWB). CWB expresses the difference between the precipitation and potential evapotranspiration.

Producer: Institute of Soil Science and Plants Cultivation State Research Institute

Link: https://susza.iung.pulawy.pl/en/mapy/2009,01,Zb_oz/

Languages: English

Catalogue:

Subjects: drought, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Atmospheric Conditions and meteorological geographical features

Useful for the analysis of: Crop production

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution:

Resource type:

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Poland

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 7, 2022

Characterization created at: December 16, 2021

Issued: April 1, 2009

Last update: September 30, 2021

Periodicity: Bimonthly

Temporal extent: April, 2009 - September, 2021

Keywords: agricultural drought, climatic water balance

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Climatic Water Balance maps	HTML	Public	https://susza.iung.pulawy.pl/en/kbw/2021,14/	HTML	False
Maps of potential zones of drought	HTML	Public	https://susza.iung.pulawy.pl/en/mapy/2021,14/	HTML	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
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Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
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Agricultural Census: Work on the exploitation: Temporary paid labour and days worked by persons not directly employed by the owner

General information

Description: Census. Collection of information regarding the agrarian structure, to serve as the basis for the directory of agricultural operations, in compliance with the legal regulations established by the European Union

Producer: Spanish National Statistics Institute

Link: https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106

Languages: Spanish | Castilian

Catalogue:

Subjects: agricultural product, agricultural region, agricultural statistics

Useful for the analysis of: Use of agricultural area

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: National Statistics Institute (Spain)

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Spain

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 18, 2022

Characterization created at: December 16, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2009

Last update: November 3, 2011

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2009

Keywords: agricultural area

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Agricultural Census	Excel XLSX	Public	https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural holding	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Labour carried out by persons not employed directly by the owner: Number of agricultural holdings	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding

Labour carried out by persons not employed directly by the owner: Number of days	Socioeconomic variable	Number of days	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Temporary paid labour: Number of agricultural holdings	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Temporary paid labour: Number of days	Socioeconomic variable	Number of days	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding

Agricultural Census: Work on the operation: Annual labour units (ALU) on the operation

General information

Description: Census. Collection of information regarding the agrarian structure, to serve as the basis for the directory of agricultural operations, in compliance with the legal regulations established by the European Union

Producer: Spanish National Statistics Institute

Link: https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106

Languages: Spanish | Castilian

Catalogue:

Subjects: agricultural product, agricultural region, agricultural statistics

Useful for the analysis of: Use of agricultural area

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: National Statistics Institute (Spain)

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Spain

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 17, 2022

Characterization created at: December 16, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2009

Last update: November 3, 2011

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2009

Keywords: agricultural area

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Agricultural Census	Excel XLSX	Public	https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural holding	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
National total employed persons (ALU)	Socioeconomic variable	ALU	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Family labour: Total	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Family labour: Total (ALU)	Socioeconomic variable	ALU	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding

Family labour: Owner (ALU)	Socioeconomic variable	ALU	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Family labour: Other members (ALU)	Socioeconomic variable	ALU	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Paid labour: Total (ALU)	Socioeconomic variable	ALU	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Paid labour: Permanent labour (ALU)	Socioeconomic variable	ALU	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Paid labour: Temporary labour (ALU)	Socioeconomic variable	ALU	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Paid labour: Temporary labour	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
National total employed persons	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Family labour: Owner	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Family labour: Other members	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Paid labour: Total	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Paid labour: Permanent labour	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding

Agricultural Census: Work on the exploitation: Agricultural manager's annual labour units (ALU)

General information

Description: Census. Collection of information regarding the agrarian structure, to serve as the basis for the directory of agricultural operations, in compliance with the legal regulations established by the European Union

Producer: Spanish National Statistics Institute

Link: https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106

Languages: Spanish | Castilian

Catalogue:

Subjects: agricultural product, agricultural region, agricultural statistics

Useful for the analysis of: Use of agricultural area

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: National Statistics Institute (Spain)

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Spain

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 17, 2022

Characterization created at: December 16, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2009

Last update: November 3, 2011

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2009

Keywords: agricultural area

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Agricultural Census	Excel XLSX	Public	https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural holding	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
National total employed persons	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
National total employed persons (ALU)	Socioeconomic variable	ALU	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Holder (ALU)	Socioeconomic variable	ALU	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding

Holder	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Other family member	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Other family member (ALU)	Socioeconomic variable	ALU	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Wage-earner (ALU)	Socioeconomic variable	ALU	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Wage-earner	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding

Agricultural Census: Work on the exploitation: Number of agricultural holdings by studies carried out by the agricultural manager

General information

Description: Census. Collection of information regarding the agrarian structure, to serve as the basis for the directory of agricultural operations, in compliance with the legal regulations established by the European Union

Producer: Spanish National Statistics Institute

Link: https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106

Languages: Spanish | Castilian

Catalogue:

Subjects: agricultural product, agricultural region, agricultural statistics

Useful for the analysis of: Use of agricultural area

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: National Statistics Institute (Spain)

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Spain

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 17, 2022

Characterization created at: December 16, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2009

Last update: November 3, 2011

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2009

Keywords: agricultural area

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Agricultural Census	Excel XLSX	Public	https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural holding	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Total agricultural holdings	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Training of the agricultural manager: exclusively	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding

practical experience						
Training of the agricultural manager: agricultural professional training	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Training of the agricultural manager: agricultural university training	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Training of the agricultural manager: other agricultural training	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding

AREA-RICA - Report management results (RISULTATI GESTIONALI)

General information

Description: This database contains data about management results in Italy from 2008 to 2019, divided into regions.

Producer: AREA-RICA

Link: https://arearica.crea.gov.it/report_c.php

Languages: Italian

Catalogue: RICA - report

Subjects: business management, Business, statistics, Economy and finance

Useful for the analysis of: Price policy

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Year

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: AREA-RICA

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Italy

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: December 16, 2021

Characterization created at: December 9, 2021

Issued:

Last update: December 31, 2019

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2008 - December, 2019

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Excel	Excel XLS	Public	https://arearica.crea.gov.it/report_c.php	Excel XLS	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Farm holding	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Geonames	37	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Represented companies (aziende rappresentate)	Socioeconomic variable	Number	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding
Total corporate revenue (ricavi totali aziendali)	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding
Gross production for sale (produzione lorda vendibile)	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding

Subsidies for CAP (first pillar) (aiuti pubblici PAC, 1° pilastro)	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding
Related activities (attività connesse)	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding
Running costs (costi correnti)	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding
Consumption factors (fattori di consumo)	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding
Third-party services (Servizio di terzi)	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding
Added value (valore aggiunto)	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding
Multi-annual costs (costi pluriennali)	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding
Net product (prodotto netto)	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding
Labor cost (costo lavoro)	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding
Operating income (Reddito operativo)	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding

Public aid (PSR and other sources) (aiuti pubblici, PSR e altre fonti)	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding
Net income (Reddito netto)	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding

AREA-RICA - Economic indices (INDICI ECONOMICI)

General information

Description: This dataset shows the report of economic indices of agricultural holdings in Italy.

Producer: AREA-RICA

Link: https://arearica.crea.gov.it/report_indx_e.php

Languages: Italian

Catalogue: RICA - report

Subjects: economy, Economy and finance

Useful for the analysis of: Farm economic size

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Year

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: AREA-RICA

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Italy

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: December 16, 2021

Characterization created at: December 9, 2021

Issued:

Last update: December 31, 2019

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2008 - December, 2019

Keywords: economy

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Excel	Excel XLS	Public	https://arearica.crea.gov.it/report_indx_e.php	Excel XLS	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Farm holding	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Geonames	37	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Impact of current costs (Incidenza dei costi correnti)	Socioeconomic variable	%	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding
Impact of multiannual costs (Incidenza dei costi pluriennali)	Socioeconomic variable	%	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding
Impact of agricultural activities (Incidenza delle attività agricole)	Socioeconomic variable	%	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding

Impact of public aid (Incidenza degli aiuti pubblici)	Socioeconomic variable	%	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding
Total productivity of labour (Produttività totale del lavoro)	Socioeconomic variable	Euro	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding
Agricultural productivity of labour (Produttività agricola del lavoro)	Socioeconomic variable	Euro	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding
Labour productivity (Produttività del lavoro)	Socioeconomic variable	Euro	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding
Net labour productivity (Produttività netta del lavoro)	Socioeconomic variable	Euro	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding
Total productivity of land (Produttività totale della terra)	Socioeconomic variable	Euro	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding
Agricultural productivity of the land (Produttività	Socioeconomic variable	Euro	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding

agricola della terra)						
Net land productivity (Produttività netta della terra)	Socioeconomic variable	Euro	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding
Companies (Aziende rappresentate)	Socioeconomic variable	nr	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding

AREA-RICA - Income indices (INDICI REDDITIVITA')

General information

Description: This dataset shows the report of income indices of agricultural holdings in Italy.

Producer: AREA-RICA

Link: https://arearica.crea.gov.it/report_indx_e.php

Languages: Italian

Catalogue: RICA - report

Subjects: economy, Economy and finance

Useful for the analysis of: Farm economic size

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Year

Resource type: Interactive resource

Was generated by: AREA-RICA

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Italy

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: December 16, 2021

Characterization created at: December 9, 2021

Issued:

Last update: December 31, 2019

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2008 - December, 2019

Keywords: economy

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Excel	Excel XLS	Public	https://arearica.crea.gov.it/report_idx_e.php	Excel XLS	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Farm holding	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Geonames	37	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Net return on labour (Redditività netta del lavoro)	Socioeconomic variable	Euro	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding
Net return on land (Redditività netta della terra)	Socioeconomic variable	Euro	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding
Gross return on land (Redditività lorda della terra)	Socioeconomic variable	Euro	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding

Extraordinary management index (Indice della gestione straordinaria)	Socioeconomic variable	Number	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding
Profitability on investments (Redditività del capitale investito)	Socioeconomic variable	Number	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding
Companies (Aziende rappresentate)	Socioeconomic variable	Number	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding
Profitability of family work (Redditività lavoro familiare)	Socioeconomic variable	Euro	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding
Gross work profitability (Redditività lorda del lavoro)	Socioeconomic variable	Euro	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding
Net labour value added (Valore aggiunto netto del lavoro)	Socioeconomic variable	Euro	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding
Net value added of land (Valore aggiunto netto della terra)	Socioeconomic variable	Euro	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding
Profitability of corporate revenues	Socioeconomic variable	%	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding

(Redditività dei ricavi aziendali)						
Return on equity (Redditività del capitale netto)	Socioeconomic variable	Number	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding

AREA-RICA - Equity Datas (DATI SITUAZIONE PATRIMONIALE)

General information

Description:

Producer: AREA-RICA

Link: https://arearica.crea.gov.it/report_indx_e.php

Languages: Italian

Catalogue: RICA - report

Subjects: economy, investment, Economy and finance

Useful for the analysis of: Farm economic size

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Year

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: AREA-RICA

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Italy

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: December 16, 2021

Characterization created at: December 9, 2021

Issued:

Last update: December 31, 2019

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2008 - December, 2019

Keywords: economy

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Excel	Excel XLS	Public	https://arearica.crea.gov.it/report_indx_e.php	Excel XLS	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Farm holding	January, 2008 - December, 2019		37	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Total uses (Totale impieghi)	Socioeconomic variable	Euro	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding
Deferred liquidity (Liquidità differite)	Socioeconomic variable	Euro	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding
Third-party capital (Capitale di terzi)	Socioeconomic variable	Euro	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding
Current liabilities (Passività correnti)	Socioeconomic variable	Euro	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding

Consolidated liabilities (Passività consolidate)	Socioeconomic variable	Euro	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding
New investments (Nuovi investimenti)	Socioeconomic variable	Euro	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding
Companies (Aziende rappresentate)	Socioeconomic variable	Number	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding
Land and buildings (Capitale fondiario)	Socioeconomic variable	Euro	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding
Fixed agricultural capital (Capitale agrario fisso)	Socioeconomic variable	Euro	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding
Circulating agricultural capital (Capitale agrario circolante)	Socioeconomic variable	Euro	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding

Fertilizer use in agriculture

General information

Description:

Producer: Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food

Link: <https://www.mapa.gob.es/es/estadistica/temas/estadisticas-agrarias/agricultura/estadisticas-medios-produccion/fertilizantes.aspx>

Languages: Spanish | Castilian

Catalogue:

Subjects: fertiliser

Useful for the analysis of: Agricultural costs, Fertilizers indicators

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Monthly

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Spain

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 13, 2022

Characterization created at: December 10, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2005

Last update: December 31, 2020

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2005 - December, 2020

Keywords: fertiliser, exports, economy, agricultural economy, imports

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Fertiliser	PDF	Public	https://www.mapa.gob.es/es/estadistica/temas/estadisticas-agrarias/agricultura/estadisticas-medios-produccion/fertilizantes.aspx	PDF	False
Fertiliser	Excel XLS	Public	https://www.mapa.gob.es/es/estadistica/temas/estadisticas-agrarias/agricultura/estadisticas-medios-produccion/fertilizantes.aspx	Excel XLS	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Total Import	January, 2005 - December, 2020	Country	100	
Agricultural sales	January, 2005 - December, 2020	Country	100	
TOTAL EXPORTS	January, 2005 - December, 2020	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
SUPERPHOSPHATES	Socioeconomic variable	Ton	January, 2005 - December, 2020	Sum	Annual	Total Import, Agricultural sales, TOTAL EXPORTS
AMMONIUM NITRATES (I)	Socioeconomic variable	Ton	January, 2005 - December, 2020	Sum	Annual	Total Import, Agricultural sales, TOTAL EXPORTS
SA+NSA	Socioeconomic variable	Ton	January, 2005 - December, 2020	Sum	Annual	Total Import, Agricultural sales, TOTAL EXPORTS
UREA+UREA WITH S	Socioeconomic variable	Ton	January, 2005 - December, 2020	Sum	Annual	Total Import, Agricultural sales, TOTAL EXPORTS
CALCIUM NITRATE	Socioeconomic variable	Ton	January, 2005 - December, 2020	Sum	Annual	Total Import, Agricultural sales, TOTAL EXPORTS
NITROGENOUS SOLUTIONS	Socioeconomic variable	Ton	January, 2005 - December, 2020	Sum	Annual	Total Import, Agricultural sales, TOTAL EXPORTS
OTHER SIMPLE NITROGENOUS	Socioeconomic variable	Ton	January, 2005 - December, 2020	Sum	Annual	Total Import, Agricultural sales, TOTAL EXPORTS
TOTAL SINGLE NITROGENOUS	Socioeconomic variable	Ton	January, 2005 - December, 2020	Sum	Annual	Total Import, Agricultural sales, TOTAL EXPORTS
PHOSPHORIC ACID AND OTHER	Socioeconomic variable	Ton	January, 2005 - December, 2020	Sum	Annual	Total Import, Agricultural sales, TOTAL EXPORTS

TOTAL SINGLE PHOSPHATES	Socioeconomic variable	Ton	January, 2005 - December, 2020	Sum	Annual	Total Import, Agricultural sales, TOTAL EXPORTS
TOTAL SINGLE POTASSIUM	Socioeconomic variable	Ton	January, 2005 - December, 2020	Sum	Annual	Total Import, Agricultural sales, TOTAL EXPORTS
TOTAL NPK LIQUID	Socioeconomic variable	Ton	January, 2005 - December, 2020	Sum	Annual	Total Import, Agricultural sales, TOTAL EXPORTS
TOTAL SUSPENSIONS	Socioeconomic variable	Ton	January, 2005 - December, 2020	Sum	Annual	Total Import, Agricultural sales, TOTAL EXPORTS
MAP	Socioeconomic variable	Ton	January, 2005 - December, 2020	Sum	Annual	Total Import, Agricultural sales, TOTAL EXPORTS
DAP	Socioeconomic variable	Ton	January, 2005 - December, 2020	Sum	Annual	Total Import, Agricultural sales, TOTAL EXPORTS
SUBTOTAL MAP+DAP	Socioeconomic variable	Ton	January, 2005 - December, 2020	Sum	Annual	Total Import, Agricultural sales, TOTAL EXPORTS
N-P COMPLEXES	Socioeconomic variable	Ton	January, 2005 - December, 2020	Sum	Annual	Total Import, Agricultural sales, TOTAL EXPORTS
N-K- COMPLEXES	Socioeconomic variable	Ton	January, 2005 - December, 2020	Sum	Annual	Total Import, Agricultural sales, TOTAL EXPORTS
P-K- COMPLEXES	Socioeconomic variable	Ton	January, 2005 - December, 2020	Sum	Annual	Total Import, Agricultural sales, TOTAL EXPORTS

SUBTOTAL NP+ NK+ PK	Socioeconomic variable	Ton	January, 2005 - December, 2020	Sum	Annual	Total Import, Agricultural sales, TOTAL EXPORTS
N-P-K COMPLEXES <10%N	Socioeconomic variable	Ton	January, 2005 - December, 2020	Sum	Annual	Total Import, Agricultural sales, TOTAL EXPORTS
N-P-K COMPLEXES 10-17%N	Socioeconomic variable	Ton	January, 2005 - December, 2020	Sum	Annual	Total Import, Agricultural sales, TOTAL EXPORTS
N-P-K COMPLEXES >17%N	Socioeconomic variable	Ton	January, 2005 - December, 2020	Sum	Annual	TOTAL EXPORTS, Total Import, Agricultural sales
SUBTOTAL NPK	Socioeconomic variable	Ton	January, 2005 - December, 2020	Sum	Annual	Total Import, Agricultural sales, TOTAL EXPORTS
TOTAL COMPLEXES	Socioeconomic variable	Ton	January, 2005 - December, 2020	Sum	Annual	Total Import, Agricultural sales, TOTAL EXPORTS
TOTAL FERTILIZERS	Socioeconomic variable	Ton	January, 2005 - December, 2020	Sum	Annual	Total Import, Agricultural sales, TOTAL EXPORTS
IN SINGLE NITROGENS	Socioeconomic variable	Ton	January, 2005 - December, 2020	Sum	Annual	Total Import, Agricultural sales, TOTAL EXPORTS
IN COMPLEXES	Socioeconomic variable	Ton	January, 2005 - December, 2020	Sum	Annual	Total Import, Agricultural sales, TOTAL EXPORTS
TOTAL N	Socioeconomic variable	Ton	January, 2005 - December, 2020	Sum	Annual	Total Import, Agricultural sales, TOTAL EXPORTS

IN SMPLES PHOSPHATES	Socioeconomic variable	Ton	January, 2005 - December, 2020	Sum	Annual	Total Import, Agricultural sales, TOTAL EXPORTS
IN COMPLEXES	Socioeconomic variable	Ton	January, 2005 - December, 2020	Sum	Annual	Total Import, Agricultural sales, TOTAL EXPORTS
TOTAL P2O5	Socioeconomic variable	Ton	January, 2005 - December, 2020	Sum	Annual	Total Import, Agricultural sales, TOTAL EXPORTS
IN SINGLE POTASSIUMS	Socioeconomic variable	Ton	January, 2005 - December, 2020	Sum	Annual	Total Import, Agricultural sales, TOTAL EXPORTS
IN COMPLEXES	Socioeconomic variable	Ton	January, 2005 - December, 2020	Sum	Annual	Total Import, Agricultural sales, TOTAL EXPORTS
TOTAL K2O	Socioeconomic variable	Ton	January, 2005 - December, 2020	Sum	Annual	Total Import, Agricultural sales, TOTAL EXPORTS

AREA-RICA - Sectoral analysis of processed products (ANALISI SETTORIALE DEI PRODOTTI TRASFORMATI)

General information

Description: This database contains data about processed products in Italy from 2008 to 2019, divided into regions.

Producer: AREA-RICA

Link: https://arearica.crea.gov.it/report_f.php

Languages: Italian

Catalogue: RICA - report

Subjects: wine, olive oil, Economy and finance

Useful for the analysis of: Wine production, Agricultural costs

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Year

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: AREA-RICA

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Italy

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: December 17, 2021

Characterization created at: December 9, 2021

Issued:

Last update: December 31, 2019

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2008 - December, 2019

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Excel	Excel XLS	Public	https://arearica.crea.gov.it/report_f.php	Excel XLS	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Quality wine	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Geonames	95	
Oil	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Geonames	95	
Common wine	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Geonames	95	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Observations (osservazioni)	Socioeconomic variable	nr	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Oil, Common wine, Quality wine
Crop area (superficie coltura)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Oil, Common wine, Quality wine
Raw material production	Socioeconomic variable	q.li/ha	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Oil, Common wine, Quality wine

(produzione materia prima)						
Raw transformed material production (valore produzione materia prima trasformata)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Oil, Common wine, Quality wine
Value of raw material purchased (valore materia prima acquistata)	Socioeconomic variable	€/q.le	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Oil, Common wine, Quality wine
Quantity of raw material purchased (quantità materia prima acquistata)	Socioeconomic variable	q.li/ha	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Oil, Common wine, Quality wine
Value of raw material transformed (valor materia prima trasformata)	Socioeconomic variable	€/q.le	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Oil, Common wine, Quality wine
Main product production (produzione prodotto principale)	Socioeconomic variable	q.li/ha	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Oil, Common wine, Quality wine

Main product purchased (prodotto principale acquistato)	Socioeconomic variable	q.li/ha	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Oil, Common wine, Quality wine
Purchased product value (valore prodotto acquistato)	Socioeconomic variable	€/q.le	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Oil, Common wine, Quality wine
Gross margin (Margine lordo)	Socioeconomic variable	€/q.le	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Oil, Common wine, Quality wine
PLT Main company product (PLT prodotto principale aziendale)	Socioeconomic variable	€/q.le	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Oil, Common wine, Quality wine
Expenditure on processing into main product (Spese trasformazione su prodotto principale)	Socioeconomic variable	€/q.le	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Oil, Common wine, Quality wine
Average selling price (Prezzo medio vendita)	Socioeconomic variable	€/q.le	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Oil, Common wine, Quality wine

Information System on Organic Production in Andalusia (SIPEA)

General information

Description: Web tool for partial queries to the Information System of organic production in Andalusia, SIPEA, making available to any user the list of certified organic operators for this scope, in Andalusia.

Producer: Regional government of Andalusia

Link: <https://ws142.juntadeandalucia.es/agriculturaypesca/roae/>

Languages: Spanish | Castilian

Catalogue:

Subjects: organic farming, organic product, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Organic Crop, Farm size, land use, Olives production, Use of agricultural area, Permanent crops

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Daily

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: Control of Organic Producers by the Regional Government of Andalusia

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: ES61

Dataset type: GEOREFERENCED

Characterization last update: January 14, 2022

Characterization created at: December 2, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2010

Last update:

Periodicity: Daily

Temporal extent: January, 1985 - December, 2021

Keywords: organic production, plots , organic farmer, organic certificate

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Information System on Organic Production in Andalusia	PDF	Public	https://ws142.juntadeandalucia.es/agricultoraypesca/roae/index.jsp	PDF	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Area size	Area size unit
Agricultural plot	January, 1985 - December, 2021	NUTS2	0	hectare

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Province	Georeferenced variable		January, 1985 - December, 2021			Agricultural plot
Inscription date	Georeferenced variable		January, 1985 - December, 2021	Instant value		Agricultural plot
Inscription Calification	Georeferenced variable		January, 2010 - December, 2021	Instant value	Daily	Agricultural plot
Agricultural area under organic farming	Georeferenced variable	hectare	January, 1985 - December, 2021	Instant value	Daily	Agricultural plot
Organic Product	Georeferenced variable		January, 1985 - December, 2021	Instant value	Daily	Agricultural plot

AREA-RICA - Crop sectoral analysis (RISULTATI SETTORIALI COLTURE)

General information

Description: This database contains data about crops in Italy from 2008 to 2019, divided into regions.

Producer: AREA-RICA

Link: https://arearica.crea.gov.it/report_d.php

Languages: Italian

Catalogue: RICA - report

Subjects: crop production, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Crop production, Use of agricultural area

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Year

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: AREA-RICA

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Italy

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: December 17, 2021

Characterization created at: December 7, 2021

Issued:

Last update: December 31, 2019

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2008 - December, 2019

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Excel	Excel XLS	Public	https://arearica.crea.gov.it/report_d.php	Excel XLS	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Nursery, cultivated mushrooms and other areas, (open field-greenhouse)	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Geonames	95	
Cereals and legumes (in open field)	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Geonames	95	
Flowers and vegetables (industrial garden-open field-greenhouse)	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Geonames	95	
Fruit and agrumes (open field-greenhouse)	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Geonames	95	
Fodder (in open field)	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Geonames	95	
Industrial plants (in open field)	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Geonames	95	
Viticulture and olive growing (open field-greenhouse)	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Geonames	95	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Observations (Osservazioni)	Socioeconomic variable	nr	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Nursery, cultivated mushrooms and other areas, (open field-greenhouse), Cereals and legumes (in open field), Flowers and vegetables (industrial garden-open field-greenhouse), Fruit and agrumes (open field-greenhouse), Fodder (in open field), Industrial plants (in open field), Viticulture and olive growing (open field-greenhouse)
Crop area (Superficie coltura)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Nursery, cultivated mushrooms and other areas, (open field-greenhouse), Cereals and legumes (in open field), Flowers and vegetables (industrial garden-open field-greenhouse), Fruit and agrumes (open field-greenhouse), Fodder (in open field), Industrial plants (in open field), Viticulture and olive growing (open field-greenhouse)
Irrigated area (Incidenza superficie irrigata)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Nursery, cultivated mushrooms and other areas, (open field-greenhouse), Cereals and legumes (in open field), Flowers and vegetables (industrial garden-open field-greenhouse), Fruit and agrumes (open field-greenhouse), Fodder (in open field), Industrial plants (in open field), Viticulture

						and olive growing (open field-greenhouse)
Main product yield (Resa prodotto principale)	Socioeconomic variable	q.li/ha	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Nursery, cultivated mushrooms and other areas, (open field-greenhouse), Cereals and legumes (in open field), Flowers and vegetables (industrial garden-open field-greenhouse), Fruit and agrumes (open field-greenhouse), Fodder (in open field), Industrial plants (in open field), Viticulture and olive growing (open field-greenhouse)
Main product price (Prezzo prodotto principale)	Socioeconomic variable	€/q.le	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Nursery, cultivated mushrooms and other areas, (open field-greenhouse), Cereals and legumes (in open field), Flowers and vegetables (industrial garden-open field-greenhouse), Fruit and agrumes (open field-greenhouse), Fodder (in open field), Industrial plants (in open field), Viticulture and olive growing (open field-greenhouse)
Total gross production (Produzione lorda totale)	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Nursery, cultivated mushrooms and other areas, (open field-greenhouse), Cereals and legumes (in open field), Flowers and vegetables (industrial garden-open field-greenhouse), Fruit and agrumes (open field-greenhouse), Fodder (in open field), Industrial plants (in open field), Viticulture and olive growing (open field-greenhouse)

Specific costs (Costi specifici)	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Nursery, cultivated mushrooms and other areas, (open field-greenhouse), Cereals and legumes (in open field), Fruit and agrumes (open field-greenhouse), Fodder (in open field), Industrial plants (in open field), Flowers and vegetables (industrial garden-open field-greenhouse), Viticulture and olive growing (open field-greenhouse)
Gross saleable production (Produzione lorda vendibile)	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Nursery, cultivated mushrooms and other areas, (open field-greenhouse), Cereals and legumes (in open field), Flowers and vegetables (industrial garden-open field-greenhouse), Fruit and agrumes (open field-greenhouse), Fodder (in open field), Industrial plants (in open field), Viticulture and olive growing (open field-greenhouse)
Reused/transformed production (Produzione reimpiegata/trasformata)	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Nursery, cultivated mushrooms and other areas, (open field-greenhouse), Cereals and legumes (in open field), Fruit and agrumes (open field-greenhouse), Fodder (in open field), Industrial plants (in open field), Flowers and vegetables (industrial garden-open field-greenhouse), Viticulture and olive growing (open field-greenhouse)
Gross margin (Margine lordo)	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Nursery, cultivated mushrooms and other areas, (open field-greenhouse), Cereals and legumes (in open field), Fruit and agrumes

						(open field-greenhouse), Fodder (in open field), Industrial plants (in open field), Flowers and vegetables (industrial garden-open field-greenhouse), Viticulture and olive growing (open field-greenhouse)
Operating margin (Margine operativo)	Socioeconomic variable	€/ha	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Nursery, cultivated mushrooms and other areas, (open field-greenhouse), Cereals and legumes (in open field), Fruit and agrumes (open field-greenhouse), Fodder (in open field), Industrial plants (in open field), Flowers and vegetables (industrial garden-open field-greenhouse), Viticulture and olive growing (open field-greenhouse)

BDSICE. Costs and prices. Agricultural price index

General information

Description: The BDSICE database contains different databases classified in different areas that correspond to the main sectors of the economy.

Producer: Ministry of Economic Affairs and Digital Transformation

Link: http://serviciosede.mineco.gob.es/Indeco/BDSICE/Busquedas/busquedas_new.aspx

Languages: Spanish | Castilian

Catalogue:

Subjects: price of agricultural produce, cost analysis, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Agricultural costs

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Monthly

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Spain

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 14, 2022

Characterization created at: December 9, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2015

Last update: July 31, 2021

Periodicity: Monthly

Temporal extent: January, 2015 - July, 2021

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Cost and Prices. Agricultural price Index	Excel XLSX	Public	http://serviciosedemineco.gob.es/Indeco/BDSICE/Busquedas/busquedas_new.aspx	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural Price Perceived	January, 2015 - July, 2021	Country		
Agricultural Price paid	January, 2015 - July, 2021	Country		

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Industrial crops	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2015 - July, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Agricultural Price Perceived
Forage crops	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2015 - July, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Agricultural Price Perceived
Vegetables	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2015 - July, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Agricultural Price Perceived
Citruses	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2015 - July, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Agricultural Price Perceived
Fresh fruits in general	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2015 - July, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Agricultural Price Perceived

Wine and must	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2015 - July, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Agricultural Price Perceived
Olive oil	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2015 - July, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Agricultural Price Perceived
Forestry products	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2015 - July, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Agricultural Price Perceived
Animal products	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2015 - July, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Agricultural Price Perceived
Livestock for supply	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2015 - July, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Agricultural Price Perceived
Beef for supply	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2015 - July, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Agricultural Price Perceived
Ovine for supply	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2015 - July, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Agricultural Price Perceived
Goat for supply	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2015 - July, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Agricultural Price Perceived
Porcine for supply	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2015 - July, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Agricultural Price Perceived
Fowl for supply	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2015 - July, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Agricultural Price Perceived
General Index	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2015 - July, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Agricultural Price Perceived, Agricultural Price paid
Agricultural Products	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2015 - July, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Agricultural Price Perceived
Cereals	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2015 - July, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Agricultural Price Perceived
Legumes	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2015 - July, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Agricultural Price Perceived
Tubercles	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2015 - July, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Agricultural Price Perceived

Rabbits for supply	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2015 - July, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Agricultural Price Perceived
Livestock products	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2015 - July, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Agricultural Price Perceived
Milk	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2015 - July, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Agricultural Price Perceived
Eggs	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2015 - July, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Agricultural Price Perceived
Wool	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2015 - July, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Agricultural Price Perceived
Fertilizers	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2015 - July, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Agricultural Price paid
Seeds and seedlings	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2015 - July, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Agricultural Price paid
Livestock feed	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2015 - July, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Agricultural Price paid
Costruction and repair of machinery	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2015 - July, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Agricultural Price paid
Energy and lubricants	Socioeconomic variable	€	January, 2015 - July, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Agricultural Price paid

Agrifood Foreign Trade Statistics (Table 3 & Table 4)

General information

Description: This statistical activity offers the main data and reports of the Andalusian Agrifood Trade Balance. Mains counties of origin and destination thereof.

Producer: Regional ministry of agriculture, livestock, fisheries and sustainable development

Link: <https://www.juntadeandalucia.es/organismos/agriculturaganaderiapescaydesarrollosostenible/servicios/estadistica-cartografia/actividad/detalle/175076/175464.html>

Languages: Spanish | Castilian

Catalogue:

Subjects: Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Agricultural value added, Agricultural costs

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: Regional Ministry of Agriculture, Livestock, Fisheries and Sustainable Development

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Europe, America, Asia

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 17, 2022

Characterization created at: December 7, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2005

Last update: June 7, 2017

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2005 - March, 2017

Keywords: agricultural economy, agricultural sector, foreign trade, balance

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Imports and exports of agri-food products and beverages from Andalusia	PDF	Public	https://www.juntadeandalucia.es/organismos/agriculturaganaderiapescaydesarrollosostenible/servicios/estadistica-cartografia/actividad/detalle/175076/175464.html	PDF	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Main origins of imports	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Country	100	
Main Destination of Exports	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Percentage Value Imported	Socioeconomic variable	% Value	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Main origins of imports
Value Imported	Socioeconomic variable	Thousands of Euros	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Main origins of imports

Percentage Value Exported	Socioeconomic variable	% Value	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Main Destination of Exports
Value Exported	Socioeconomic variable	Thousands of Euros	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Main Destination of Exports
Percentage Variation between 2 annuities	Socioeconomic variable	%	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Instant value	Annual	Main origins of imports , Main Destination of Exports

BDSICE. National production and demand indicators. Agriculture (Olive grove)

General information

Description: The BDSICE database also contains different databases classified in different areas that correspond to the main sectors of the economy.

Producer: Ministry of Economic Affairs and Digital Transformation

Link: http://serviciosede.mineco.gob.es/Indeco/BDSICE/Busquedas/Busquedas_new.aspx

Languages: Spanish | Castilian

Catalogue:

Subjects: cost analysis, economic indicator, production statistics, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Economy and finance

Useful for the analysis of: Agricultural costs, agro-industry value added, production indices

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Spain

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 14, 2022

Characterization created at: December 10, 2021

Issued: January 25, 2016

Last update: June 14, 2021

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 1983 - December, 2010

Keywords: economy, agricultural sector, statistical advances, olive grove production

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Olive Grove	Excel XLSX	Public	http://serviciosede.mineco.gob.es/Indeco/BDSICE/Visualizacion/visualizacionTabular.aspx	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Olive Production	January, 1983 - December, 2010			

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Statistical advances in olive grove production	Socioeconomic variable	Thousand Tons	January, 1983 - December, 2010	Instant value	Annual	Olive Production

Local Data Bank - Land surface and soil protection

General information

Description: The data refer to soil type, landscape cover, fire damages of different areas, devastated and degraded land, reclaimed and brought into cultivation.

Producer: Statistics Poland

Link: <https://bdl.stat.gov.pl/BDL/metadane/podgrupy/304#>

Languages: English

Catalogue:

Subjects: soil protection, Environment, Land cover, Soil, Regional statistics

Useful for the analysis of: land use

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Year

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Poland

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 7, 2022

Characterization created at: December 10, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2003

Last update: June 28, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2003 - December, 2020

Keywords: landscape cover, fire damages of different areas, devastated and degraded land, reclaimed and brought into cultivation

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
CSV	CSV	Public		CSV	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLS	Public		Excel XLS	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural area and forest land excluded from agricultural and forest production	January, 2003 - December, 2020	NUTS2	95	
Agricultural land designated for non-agricultural purposes by type of land	January, 2003 - December, 2020	NUTS2	95	
Agricultural area and forest land excluded from agricultural and forest production by exclusion type	January, 2003 - December, 2020	NUTS2	95	1
Devastated and degraded land requiring reclamation	January, 2002 - December, 2020	NUTS2	95	
Devastated and degraded land, reclaimed and brought into cultivation	January, 2003 - December, 2020	NUTS2	95	

Fire of agricultural crops, meadows, stubbles and wasteland	January, 2003 - December, 2020	NUTS2	95	
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Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
transport grounds	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2003 - December, 2003	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural area and forest land excluded from agricultural and forest production by exclusion type
residential lands	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2003 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural area and forest land excluded from agricultural and forest production by exclusion type
industrial lands	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2003 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural area and forest land excluded from agricultural and forest production by exclusion type
mining grounds water reservoirs other	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2003 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural area and forest land excluded from agricultural and forest production by exclusion type
water reservoirs	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2003 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural area and forest land excluded from agricultural and forest production by exclusion type
other of agricultural area and forest land excluded from agricultural and forest production by exclusion type	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2003 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural area and forest land excluded from agricultural and forest production by exclusion type

total agricultural area and forest land excluded from agricultural and forest production	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2003 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural area and forest land excluded from agricultural and forest production
arable lands	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2003 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural area and forest land excluded from agricultural and forest production
forest land	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2003 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural area and forest land excluded from agricultural and forest production
agricultural area designated in total	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2003 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural land designated for non-agricultural purposes by type of land
utilised agricultural total	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2003 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural land designated for non-agricultural purposes by type of land
utilised agricultural - quality class I-II, mineral	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2003 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural land designated for non-agricultural purposes by type of land
utilised agricultural - quality class III, mineral	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2003 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural land designated for non-agricultural purposes by type of land
utilised agricultural - quality class IV, mineral	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2003 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural land designated for non-agricultural purposes by type of land
utilised agricultural -	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2003 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural land designated for non-agricultural purposes by type of land

quality class IV, organic						
utilised agricultural - quality class V-VI, organic	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2003 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural land designated for non-agricultural purposes by type of land
miscellaneous land	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2003 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural land designated for non-agricultural purposes by type of land
total of devastated and degraded land requiring reclamation	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2003 - October, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Devastated and degraded land requiring reclamation
devastated land	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2003 - October, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Devastated and degraded land requiring reclamation
degraded land	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2003 - October, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Devastated and degraded land requiring reclamation
share of devastated and degraded land requiring reclamation in total area	Socioeconomic variable	%	January, 2003 - October, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Devastated and degraded land requiring reclamation
share of degraded land in total area	Socioeconomic variable	%	January, 2003 - October, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Devastated and degraded land requiring reclamation
total of land reclaimed and managed during the year	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2003 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Devastated and degraded land, reclaimed and brought into cultivation
land reclaimed and managed	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2003 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Devastated and degraded land, reclaimed and brought into cultivation

during the year for agricultural purposes						
total of land reclaimed during the year	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2003 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Devastated and degraded land, reclaimed and brought into cultivation
land reclaimed during the year for agricultural purposes	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2003 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Devastated and degraded land, reclaimed and brought into cultivation
land reclaimed during the year for forestry purposes	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2003 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Devastated and degraded land, reclaimed and brought into cultivation
total of land managed during the year	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2003 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Devastated and degraded land, reclaimed and brought into cultivation
land managed during the year for agricultural purposes	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2003 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Devastated and degraded land, reclaimed and brought into cultivation
land managed during the year forestry purposes	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2003 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Devastated and degraded land, reclaimed and brought into cultivation
total of fires	Socioeconomic variable	pcs	January, 2003 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Fire of agricultural crops, meadows, stubbles and wasteland
fires of croplands, meadows and stubbles	Socioeconomic variable	pcs	January, 2003 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Fire of agricultural crops, meadows, stubbles and wasteland

fires of wasteland	Socioeconomic variable	pcs	January, 2003 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Fire of agricultural crops, meadows, stubbles and wasteland
Total area of fires	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2003 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Fire of agricultural crops, meadows, stubbles and wasteland
fire area of croplands, meadows and stubbles	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2003 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Fire of agricultural crops, meadows, stubbles and wasteland
fire area of wasteland	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2003 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Fire of agricultural crops, meadows, stubbles and wasteland
land reclaimed and managed during the year for forestry purposes	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2003 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Devastated and degraded land, reclaimed and brought into cultivation

Local Data Bank - Usable underground water resources

General information

Description: The data refer to underground water resources, abstraction water from quaternary, tertiary, Cretaceous and older geological formations, its increase or decrease as compared to the previous year.

Producer: Statistics Poland

Link: <https://bdl.stat.gov.pl/BDL/metadane/podgrupy/311#>

Languages: English

Catalogue:

Subjects: drinking water, water protection, water policy, Environment, Hydrography

Useful for the analysis of: Environmental policy, Freshwater abstractions

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Year

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Poland

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 7, 2022

Characterization created at: December 10, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2003

Last update: October 28, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2003 - December, 2020

Keywords: underground water resources

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
CSV	CSV	Public		CSV	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLS	Public		Excel XLS	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Usable underground water resources	January, 2003 - December, 2020	NUTS2	95	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
increase or decrease as compared to the previous year	Socioeconomic variable	hm3	January, 2003 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	
total of usable underground water resources	Socioeconomic variable	hm3	January, 2003 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	
from quaternary geological formations	Socioeconomic variable	hm3	January, 2003 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	
from tertiary geological formations	Socioeconomic variable	hm3	January, 2003 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	

from Cretaceous geological formations	Socioeconomic variable	hm3	January, 2003 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	
from older geological formations	Socioeconomic variable	hm3	January, 2003 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	

Agricultural Census: General Distribution of area

General information

Description: Census. Collection of information regarding the agrarian structure, to serve as the basis for the directory of agricultural operations, in compliance with the legal regulations established by the European Union

Producer: Spanish National Statistics Institute

Link: https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106

Languages: Spanish | Castilian

Catalogue:

Subjects: agricultural product, agricultural region, agricultural statistics, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Agricultural and aquaculture facilities, Land use

Useful for the analysis of: Use of agricultural area, Permanent crops, Organic Crop, Farm size

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: Regular updating of the national census of agricultural holdings

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Spain

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 17, 2022

Characterization created at: December 13, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2009

Last update: December 31, 2012

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 2011 - December, 2012

Keywords: agricultural area

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Agricultural Census	Excel XLSX	Public	https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural Holdings	January, 2011 - December, 2012	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
All lands (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2011 - December, 2012	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
Cultivated lands (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2011 - December, 2012	Instant value	Annual	
Land for permanent pastures (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2011 - December, 2012	Instant value	Annual	
Other Land (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2011 - December, 2012	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings

All lands (Number of Holdings)	Socioeconomic variable	Number of Holdings	January, 2011 - December, 2012	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
Cultivated lands (Number of Holdings)	Socioeconomic variable	Number of Holdings	January, 2011 - December, 2012	Instant value	Annual	
Land for permanent pastures (Number of Holdings)	Socioeconomic variable	Number of Holdings	January, 2011 - December, 2012	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
Other land (Number of Holdings)	Socioeconomic variable	Number of Holdings	January, 2011 - December, 2012	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
Number of Agricultural Holdings with UAA	Socioeconomic variable	Number of Holdings	January, 2011 - December, 2012	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
Area of Agricultural Holdings with UAA	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2011 - December, 2012	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings

Agricultural Census GENERAL DISTRIBUTION OF AREA: Exploitation of cultivated lands

General information

Description: Census. Collection of information regarding the agrarian structure, to serve as the basis for the directory of agricultural operations, in compliance with the legal regulations established by the European Union

Producer: Spanish National Statistics Institute

Link: https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106

Languages: Spanish | Castilian

Catalogue:

Subjects: agricultural product, agricultural region, agricultural statistics

Useful for the analysis of: Use of agricultural area

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: National Statistics Institute (Spain)

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Spain

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 18, 2022

Characterization created at: December 13, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2009

Last update: December 31, 2012

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2009

Keywords: agricultural area

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Agricultural Census	Excel XLSX	Public	https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural holding with UAA	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
All cultivated lands (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
All cultivated lands	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Combined arable	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA

Fruit trees	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Combined arable (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Fruit trees (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Olive groves (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Vineyards (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Other cultivated lands (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Olive groves	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Vineyards	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Other cultivated lands	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA

Agrifood Foreign Trade Statistics (Table 1 & Table 2 - Agri-food and beverages imports and exports)

General information

Description: This statistical activity offers the main data and reports of the Andalusian Agrifood Trade Balance. Imports and exports of agri-food products and beverages from Andalusia.

Producer: Regional ministry of agriculture, livestock, fisheries and sustainable development

Link: <https://www.juntadeandalucia.es/organismos/agriculturaganaderiapescaydesarrollosostenible/servicios/estadistica-cartografia/estadisticas-agricolas/paginas/comercio-exterior-agricola.html>

Languages: Spanish | Castilian

Catalogue:

Subjects: Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Agricultural value added, Agricultural costs

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: ES613, ES616, ES615, ES618, ES614, ES611, ES617, ES612

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 14, 2022

Characterization created at: December 3, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2005

Last update: December 23, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2005 - March, 2017

Keywords: agricultural economy, agricultural sector, foreign trade, balance

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Imports and exports of agri-food products and beverages from Andalusia	Excel XLS	Public	https://www.juntadeandalucia.es/organismos/agriculturaganaderiapescaydesarrollosostenible/servicios/estadistic-cartografia/estadisticas-agricolas/paginas/comercio-exterior-agricola.html	Excel XLS	False
Imports and exports of agri-food products and beverages from Andalusia	PDF	Public	https://www.juntadeandalucia.es/organismos/agriculturaganaderiapescaydesarrollosostenible/servicios/estadistic-cartografia/estadisticas-agricolas/paginas/comercio-exterior-agricola.html	PDF	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
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Region	January, 2005 - December, 2021			
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Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Quantity Imported	Socioeconomic variable	Tons	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Sum	Monthly	Region
Quantity exported	Socioeconomic variable	Tons	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Sum	Monthly	Region
Value Imported	Socioeconomic variable	Thousands of Euros	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Sum	Monthly	Region
Value Exported	Socioeconomic variable	Thousands of Euros	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Sum	Monthly	Region

Agrifood Foreign Trade Statistics (Table 5 - Exported and Imported Tariff Chapters)

General information

Description: This statistical activity offers the main data and reports of the Andalusian Agrifood Trade Balance. Trade balance of the main exported and imported tariff chapters

Producer: Regional ministry of agriculture, livestock, fisheries and sustainable development

Link: <https://www.juntadeandalucia.es/organismos/agriculturaganaderiapescaydesarrollosostenible/servicios/estadistica-cartografia/actividad/detalle/175076/175464.html>

Languages: Spanish | Castilian

Catalogue:

Subjects: Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Agricultural value added, Agricultural costs

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: ES61

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 14, 2022

Characterization created at: December 7, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2005

Last update: December 23, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2005 - March, 2017

Keywords: agricultural economy, agricultural sector, foreign trade, balance

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Trade balance of the main exported and imported tariff chapters	Excel XLS	Public	https://www.juntadeandalucia.es/organismos/agriculturaganaderiapescaydesarrollosostenible/servicios/estadisticas-cartografia/estadisticas-agricolas/paginas/comercio-exterior-agricola.html	Excel XLS	False
Trade balance of the main exported and imported tariff chapters	PDF	Public	https://www.juntadeandalucia.es/organismos/agriculturaganaderiapescaydesarrollosostenible/servicios/estadisticas-cartografia/estadisticas-agricolas/paginas/comercio-exterior-agricola.html	PDF	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
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Product	January, 2005 - December, 2021			
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Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Value Imported	Socioeconomic variable	Thousands of Euros	January, 2005 - March, 2017	Instant value	Annual	Product
Value Exported	Socioeconomic variable	Thousands of Euros	January, 2005 - March, 2017	Instant value	Annual	Product
Balance	Socioeconomic variable	Thousands of Euros	January, 2005 - March, 2017	Instant value	Annual	Product

Local Data Bank - Economic exploitation of forest

General information

Description: The data refer to forest fruit and mushrooms quantity and value.

Producer: Statistics Poland

Link: <https://bdl.stat.gov.pl/BDL/metadane/podgrupy/443>

Languages: English

Catalogue:

Subjects: forestry policy, Environment, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Environmental policy, Forestry output

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Year

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Poland

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 7, 2022

Characterization created at: December 10, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2009

Last update: May 20, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2020

Keywords: forest fruit, forest mushrooms

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
CSV	CSV	Public		CSV	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLS	Public		Excel XLS	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Procurement of forest fruits and mushrooms	January, 2009 - December, 2020	NUTS2	95	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
forest fruit quantity	Socioeconomic variable	t	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Procurement of forest fruits and mushrooms
forest fruit value	Socioeconomic variable	thous. zl	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Procurement of forest fruits and mushrooms
mushrooms quantity	Socioeconomic variable	t	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Procurement of forest fruits and mushrooms
mushrooms value	Socioeconomic variable	thous. zl	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Procurement of forest fruits and mushrooms

Spanish Statistics on Means of Production: Registration of New machinery

General information

Description: This survey provides information about the incorporation of new machinery in the agrarian production process in Spain. It provides information at a provincial level on new machinery by type of machine, brand or purpose.

Producer: Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food

Link: <https://www.mapa.gob.es/es/estadistica/temas/estadisticas-agrarias/agricultura/estadisticas-medios-produccion/maquinaria-agricola.aspx>

Languages: Spanish | Castilian

Catalogue:

Subjects: machinery, production statistics

Useful for the analysis of: Agricultural costs

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Monthly

Resource type:

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Spain

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 13, 2022

Characterization created at: December 10, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2006

Last update: December 31, 2019

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2006 - December, 2019

Keywords: agricultural economy, agricultural machinery

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Registration of New Machinery (Excel spreadsheet)	Excel XLSX	Public	https://www.mapa.gob.es/es/estadistica/temas/estadisticas-agrarias/agricultura/estadisticas-medios-produccion/maquinaria-agricola.aspx	Excel XLSX	False
Registration of New Machinery (PDF)	PDF	Public	https://www.mapa.gob.es/es/estadistica/temas/estadisticas-agrarias/agricultura/estadisticas-medios-produccion/maquinaria-agricola.aspx	PDF	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Machinery units	January, 2006 - December, 2019	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis

Tractors	Socioeconomic variable	Units	January, 2006 - December, 2019	Instant value	Monthly	Machinery units
Tractor wheels	Socioeconomic variable	Units	January, 2006 - December, 2019	Instant value	Monthly	Machinery units
Self-propelled grain harvesting machinery	Socioeconomic variable	Units	January, 2006 - December, 2019	Instant value	Monthly	Machinery units
Other self-propelled machinery	Socioeconomic variable	Units	January, 2006 - December, 2019	Instant value	Monthly	Machinery units
Loading equipment	Socioeconomic variable	Units	January, 2006 - December, 2019	Instant value	Monthly	Machinery units
Tractor-trailers	Socioeconomic variable	Units	January, 2006 - December, 2019	Instant value	Monthly	Machinery units
Trailers	Socioeconomic variable	Units	January, 2006 - December, 2019	Instant value	Monthly	Machinery units
Other	Socioeconomic variable	Units	January, 2006 - December, 2019	Instant value	Monthly	Machinery units

Local Data Bank - Land Use

General information

Description: Data by official residence of the land user.

Producer: Statistics Poland

Link: <https://bdl.stat.gov.pl/BDL/metadane/podgrupy/422>

Languages: English

Catalogue:

Subjects: land use, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Land use

Useful for the analysis of: Use of agricultural area

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: year

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Poland

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 5, 2022

Characterization created at: December 7, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2004

Last update: October 20, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2004 - December, 2020

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
CSV	CSV	Public		CSV	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLS	Public		Excel XLS	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural land as percentage of total area (P2399)	January, 2004 - December, 2020	NUTS2	95	
Land use (P2608)	January, 2004 - December, 2020	NUTS2	95	
Utilised agricultural land - agricultural land area per 1 tractor according to the new definition (P3409)	January, 2010 - December, 2016	NUTS2	93	
Utilised agricultural land - agricultural land area per 1 tractor according to the new definition PRELIMINARY DATA (P4012)	January, 2020 - December, 2020	NUTS2	95	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
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agricultural land according to the new definition	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2011 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Land use (P2608)
Data coverage - in agricultural holdings according to the new definition	Socioeconomic variable	%	January, 2004 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural land as percentage of total area (P2399)
Data coverage - in farms exceeding 30 hectares in the agricultural land area in farms conducting agricultural activity in total - new definition	Socioeconomic variable	%	January, 2004 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural land as percentage of total area (P2399)
Forms of ownership - total	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2010 - December, 2020	Instant value	Irregular	Utilised agricultural land - agricultural land area per 1 tractor according to the new definition (P3409), Utilised agricultural land - agricultural land area per 1 tractor according to the new definition PRELIMINARY DATA (P4012)
Forms of ownership - private farms	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2010 - December, 2020	Instant value	Irregular	Utilised agricultural land - agricultural land area per 1 tractor according to the new definition (P3409), Utilised agricultural land - agricultural land area per 1 tractor according to the new definition PRELIMINARY DATA (P4012)
total area in agricultural	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2010 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Land use (P2608)

holdings according to the new definition						
afforested area in agricultural holdings according to the new definition	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2011 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Land use (P2608)
agricultural land in good agriarian culture according to the new definition	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2011 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Land use (P2608)
kitchen gardens according to the new definition	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2011 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Land use (P2608)
meadows and permanent pastures according to the new definition	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2011 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Land use (P2608)
permanent crops according to the new definition	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2011 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Land use (P2608)
arable land according to the new definition	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2011 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Land use (P2608)
grassland according to the new definition	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2011 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Land use (P2608)

fallows areas (with green fertilizer) according to the new definition	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2011 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Land use (P2608)
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Local Data Bank - Forest environment: threats and protection

General information

Description: The data refer to data from the National Forest Fire Information System.

Producer: Statistics Poland

Link: <https://bdl.stat.gov.pl/BDL/metadane/podgrupy/444>

Languages: English

Catalogue:

Subjects: forestry policy, forestry statistics, Environment, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Environmental policy

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Year

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Poland

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 7, 2022

Characterization created at: December 10, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2009

Last update: July 1, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2020

Keywords: forest fires

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Spreadsheet	Excel XLS	Public		Excel XLS	False
CSV	CSV	Public		CSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Forest fires by causes	January, 2009 - December, 2020	NUTS2	95	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
area of forest fires in total	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Forest fires by causes
area of forest fires by arson	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Forest fires by causes
area of forest fires by negligence adults	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Forest fires by causes
area of forest fires by defects technical devices and their incorrect exploitation	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Forest fires by causes

area of forest fires by transport equipment defects and incorrect exploitation	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Forest fires by causes
area of forest fires by negligence juveniles	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Forest fires by causes
area of forest fires by lightning	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Forest fires by causes
area of forest fires unknown	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Forest fires by causes

Agrifood Foreign Trade Statistics (Table 6 & 7 - Main Agri-Food Products Exported by Andalusia)

General information

Description: This statistical activity offers the main data and reports of the Andalusian Agrifood Trade Balance. Main agri-food products exported by Andalusia

Producer: Regional ministry of agriculture, livestock, fisheries and sustainable development

Link: <https://www.juntadeandalucia.es/organismos/agriculturaganaderiapescaydesarrollosostenible/servicios/estadistica-cartografia/actividad/detalle/175076/175464.html>

Languages: Spanish | Castilian

Catalogue:

Subjects: Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Agricultural value added, Agricultural costs

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Monthly

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: ES61

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 14, 2022

Characterization created at: December 7, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2005

Last update: December 23, 2021

Periodicity: Monthly

Temporal extent: January, 2005 - March, 2017

Keywords: agricultural economy, agricultural sector, foreign trade, balance

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Main agri-food products exported by Andalusia	PDF	Public	https://www.juntadeandalucia.es/organismos/agriculturaganaderiapescaydesarrollosostenible/servicios/estadistica-cartografia/actividad/detalle/175076/175464.html	PDF	False
Main agri-food products exported by Andalusia	Excel XLS	Public	https://www.juntadeandalucia.es/organismos/agriculturaganaderiapescaydesarrollosostenible/servicios/estadistica-cartografia/estadisticas-agricolas/paginas/comercio-exterior-agricola.html	Excel XLS	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
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Agri-food product	January, 2005 - December, 2021	NUTS2		
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Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Value Exported	Socioeconomic variable	Thousands of Euros	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Agri-food product
Quantity Exported	Socioeconomic variable	Tons	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Agri-food product
Percentage Quantity Exported	Socioeconomic variable	% total Tons	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Agri-food product
Percentage Value Exported	Socioeconomic variable	% total value exported	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Agri-food product
Value Exported (1 year ago)	Socioeconomic variable	Thousands of Euros	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Agri-food product
Quantity Exported (1 year ago)	Socioeconomic variable	Tons	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Agri-food product
Variation of Quantity Exported (regarding 1 year ago)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage (%)	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Agri-food product
Variation of Value Exported (regarding 1 year ago)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage (%)	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Agri-food product

Training of farm managers

General information

Description: of training of farm managers

Producer: Eurostat

Link: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/ef_mp_training/default/table?lang=en

Languages: English

Catalogue: Eurostat - Agriculture, forestry and fishery

Subjects: vocational training, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Agriculture policy

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution:

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Malta, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 7, 2022

Characterization created at: December 9, 2021

Issued: February 9, 2021

Last update: February 9, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2013 - January, 2016

Keywords: training, farm managers

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Training of farm managers	SDMX	Public	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/ef_mp_training/default/table?lang=en	SDMX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
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Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Basic training	Socioeconomic variable	hours	January, 2013 - January, 2016	Instant value	Annual	
Practical experience	Socioeconomic variable	Hours	January, 2013 - January, 2016	Instant value	Annual	
Full agricultural training	Socioeconomic variable	Hours	January, 2013 - January, 2016	Instant value	Annual	

AREA-RICA - Technical indices (INDICI CARATTERISTICHE STRUTTURALI)

General information

Description: This dataset shows the report of technical indices about structural characteristics of agricultural holdings in Italy.

Producer: AREA-RICA

Link: https://arearica.crea.gov.it/report_indx_t.php

Languages: Italian

Catalogue: RICA - report

Subjects: agricultural holdings, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Farm Structure

Useful for the analysis of: Technical index

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Year

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: AREA-RICA

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Italy

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 10, 2022

Characterization created at: December 9, 2021

Issued:

Last update: December 31, 2019

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2008 - December, 2019

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Excel	Excel XLS	Public	https://arearica.crea.gov.it/report_indx_t.php	Excel XLS	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
is	January, 2000 - March, 2000			
Farm holding	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Geonames	37	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Labour intensity (intensità del lavoro)	Socioeconomic variable	hectares	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding
Holdings (aziende rappresentate)	Socioeconomic variable	number	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding
Incidence of irrigated land use (incidenza della SAU irrigata)	Socioeconomic variable	%	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding

Incidence of land use in property (incidenza della SAU in proprietà)	Socioeconomic variable	%	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding
zootechnical intensity's level (grado intensità zootecnica)	Socioeconomic variable		January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding
Livestock load (carico bestiame)	Socioeconomic variable		January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding
Incidence of family labour (incidenza manodopera familiare)	Socioeconomic variable	%	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding
mechanisation of land's level (grado di meccanizzazione dei terreni)	Socioeconomic variable	kw	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding
Mechanisation intensity (intensità della meccanizzazione)	Socioeconomic variable	kw	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding
Holdings work's intensity (intensità del lavoro aziendale)	Socioeconomic variable	days	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding
Incidence of seasonal work (incidenza del lavoro stagionale)	Socioeconomic variable	%	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding

Incidence of agricultural contractors (incidenza del controterzismo)	Socioeconomic variable	%	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding
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Local Data Bank - Forestry of all forms of ownership

General information

Description: The data refer to the forestry data, presented according to the division on public forests: forests owned by the State Treasury, including forests managed by the State Forests and private forests. Forest land include the forests area as well as land connected with silviculture.

Producer: Statistics Poland

Link: <https://bdل.stat.gov.pl/BDL/metadane/podgrupy/171>

Languages: English

Catalogue:

Subjects: forestry policy, forestry statistics, Environment, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Environmental policy, Forestry output

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Year

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Poland

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 7, 2022

Characterization created at: December 10, 2021

Issued: January 1, 1999

Last update: July 1, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 1999 - December, 2020

Keywords: forest land, afforestation, removals (timber), public forests, private forests

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Spreadsheet	Excel XLS	Public		Excel XLS	False
CSV	CSV	Public		CSV	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Area of non-forest land, already wooded and designed for afforestation	January, 1999 - December, 2020	NUTS2	95	
Forest area	January, 1999 - December, 2020	NUTS2	95	
Forest land	January, 1999 - December, 2020	NUTS2	95	
Afforestation of non-forest land	January, 2001 - December, 2020	NUTS2	95	
Removals (timber) per 100 ha of forest area	January, 2002 - December, 2020	NUTS2	95	
Renewals, afforestations and other silviculture operations	January, 1999 - December, 2020	NUTS2	95	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
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Forest land in total	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 1999 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Forest land
public forest land, grand total	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 1999 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Forest land
public forest land owned by State Treasury	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 1999 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Forest land
public forest land owned by State Treasury, managed by State Forests	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 1999 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Forest land
private forest land	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 1999 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Forest land
lands connected to forest economy, grand total	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 1999 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Forest land
lands connected to forest economy managed by State Forests	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 1999 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Forest land
forest cover in percent	Socioeconomic variable	%	January, 1999 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Forest land
afforestation of non-forest land in total	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2001 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Afforestation of non-forest land
public forests, total	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2017 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Afforestation of non-forest land

public forests of State Treasury	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2017 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Afforestation of non-forest land
public forests owned of the State Treasury managed by the State Forests	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2001 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Afforestation of non-forest land
private forests	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2001 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Afforestation of non-forest land
afforestations in public forests of State Treasury managed by State Forests	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 1999 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Area of non-forest land, already wooded and designed for afforestation
afforestations, grand total	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 1999 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Area of non-forest land, already wooded and designed for afforestation
forests, grand total	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 1999 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Forest area
public forests, grand total	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 1999 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Forest area
public forests of State Treasury	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 1999 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Forest area
public forests owned of the State Treasury managed by the State Forests	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 1999 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Forest area
Removals (timber) per 100 ha of forest area, total	Socioeconomic variable	m3	January, 2002 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Removals (timber) per 100 ha of forest area

Removals (timber) per 100 ha of forest area, public forests, grand total	Socioeconomic variable	m3	January, 2002 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Removals (timber) per 100 ha of forest area
Removals (timber) per 100 ha of forest area, public forests of State Treasury	Socioeconomic variable	m3	January, 2002 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Removals (timber) per 100 ha of forest area
Removals (timber) per 100 ha of forest area, public forests owned of the State Treasury managed by the State Forests	Socioeconomic variable	m3	January, 2002 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Removals (timber) per 100 ha of forest area
Removals (timber) per 100 ha of forest area, public forests, gmina	Socioeconomic variable	m3	January, 2002 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Removals (timber) per 100 ha of forest area
Removals (timber) per 100 ha of forest area, private forests	Socioeconomic variable	m3	January, 2002 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Removals (timber) per 100 ha of forest area
regeneration and afforestations in	Socioeconomic variable	%	January, 2005 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Renewals, afforestations and other silviculture operations

relation to forest area total						
renewals and afforestations, total	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 1999 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Renewals, afforestations and other silviculture operations
renewals and afforestations, public forests, total	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2017 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Renewals, afforestations and other silviculture operations
renewals and afforestations, public forests of State Treasury	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2017 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Renewals, afforestations and other silviculture operations
renewals and afforestations, public forests owned of the State Treasury managed by the State Forests	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 1999 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Renewals, afforestations and other silviculture operations
renewals and afforestations, private forests	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2017 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Renewals, afforestations and other silviculture operations

Agricultural Census: Livestock

General information

Description: Census. Collection of information regarding the agrarian structure, to serve as the basis for the directory of agricultural operations, in compliance with the legal regulations established by the European Union

Producer: Spanish National Statistics Institute

Link: https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106

Languages: Spanish | Castilian

Catalogue:

Subjects: agricultural product, agricultural region, agricultural statistics, livestock, livestock farming, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Agricultural and aquaculture facilities, Land use

Useful for the analysis of: Use of agricultural area, Livestock farming

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: Regular updating of the national census of agricultural holdings

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Spain

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 17, 2022

Characterization created at: December 13, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2009

Last update: December 31, 2012

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2009

Keywords: agricultural area, livestock, livestock animal units

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Agricultural Census	Excel XLSX	Public	https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural Holdings without UAA	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Country	100	
Agricultural Holdings with UAA	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Country	100	
Agricultural Holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Country	100	
Agricultural Holdings without lands	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Number of Agricultural	Socioeconomic variable	Number of Agricultural Holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings without UAA, Agricultural Holdings with UAA,

Holdings with Cattle						Agricultural Holdings, Agricultural Holdings without lands
Total Livestock (Livestock units)	Socioeconomic variable	Livestock units	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings without UAA, Agricultural Holdings with UAA, Agricultural Holdings, Agricultural Holdings without lands
Cattle (Livestock units)	Socioeconomic variable	Livestock units	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings without UAA, Agricultural Holdings with UAA, Agricultural Holdings, Agricultural Holdings without lands
Sheep (Livestock units)	Socioeconomic variable	Livestock units	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings without UAA, Agricultural Holdings with UAA, Agricultural Holdings, Agricultural Holdings without lands
Goats (Livestock units)	Socioeconomic variable	Livestock units	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings without UAA, Agricultural Holdings with UAA, Agricultural Holdings, Agricultural Holdings without lands
Pigs (Livestock units)	Socioeconomic variable	Livestock units	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings without UAA, Agricultural Holdings with UAA, Agricultural Holdings, Agricultural Holdings without lands
Horses (Livestock units)	Socioeconomic variable	Livestock units	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings without UAA, Agricultural Holdings with UAA, Agricultural Holdings, Agricultural Holdings without lands
Poultry (except ostriches) (Livestock units)	Socioeconomic variable	Livestock units	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings without UAA, Agricultural Holdings with UAA, Agricultural Holdings, Agricultural Holdings without lands

Number of Agricultural Holdings with Livestock	Socioeconomic variable	Number of Agricultural Holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings without UAA, Agricultural Holdings with UAA, Agricultural Holdings, Agricultural Holdings without lands
Number of Agricultural Holdings with Sheeps	Socioeconomic variable	Number of Agricultural Holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings without UAA, Agricultural Holdings with UAA, Agricultural Holdings, Agricultural Holdings without lands
Number of Agricultural Holdings with Goats	Socioeconomic variable	Number of Agricultural Holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings without UAA, Agricultural Holdings with UAA, Agricultural Holdings, Agricultural Holdings without lands
Number of Agricultural Holdings with Pigs	Socioeconomic variable	Number of Agricultural Holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings without UAA, Agricultural Holdings with UAA, Agricultural Holdings, Agricultural Holdings without lands
Number of Agricultural Holdings with Horses	Socioeconomic variable	Number of Agricultural Holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings without UAA, Agricultural Holdings with UAA, Agricultural Holdings, Agricultural Holdings without lands
Number of Agricultural Holdings with Poultry (except ostriches)	Socioeconomic variable	Number of Agricultural Holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings without UAA, Agricultural Holdings with UAA, Agricultural Holdings, Agricultural Holdings without lands
Does (except ostriches) (Livestock Units)	Socioeconomic variable	Livestock Units	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings without UAA, Agricultural Holdings with UAA, Agricultural Holdings, Agricultural Holdings without lands
Number of Agricultural Holdings with Does	Socioeconomic variable	Number of Agricultural Holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings without UAA, Agricultural Holdings with UAA, Agricultural Holdings, Agricultural Holdings without lands

Agricultural Census: Municipal results

General information

Description: Census. Collection of information regarding the agrarian structure, to serve as the basis for the directory of agricultural operations, in compliance with the legal regulations established by the European Union

Producer: Nationa Statistics Institute

Link: https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106

Languages: Spanish | Castilian

Catalogue:

Subjects: agricultural product, agricultural region, agricultural statistics

Useful for the analysis of: Use of agricultural area

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: Nationa Statistics Institute (Spain)

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Spain

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: December 22, 2021

Characterization created at: December 13, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2009

Last update: December 31, 2012

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2009

Keywords: agricultural area

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Agricultural Census	Excel XLSX	Public	https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Municipalities	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Total Livestock	Socioeconomic variable	Number of livestock	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Municipalities
UAA	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	
Holding	Socioeconomic variable	Number of holding	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Municipalities

Local Data Bank - Nature and biodiversity protection

General information

Description: The data refer to Natura 2000, protected animals, nature reserves, legal protected area.

Producer: Statistics Poland

Link: <https://bdl.stat.gov.pl/BDL/metadane/podgrupy/218?back=True#>

Languages: English

Catalogue:

Subjects: biodiversity, Environment, Regional statistics, Habitats and biotopes

Useful for the analysis of: Environmental policy

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Year

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Poland

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 7, 2022

Characterization created at: December 10, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2003

Last update: July 15, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2003 - December, 2020

Keywords: protected animals, nature reserves, legal protected area

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
CSV	CSV	Public		CSV	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLS	Public		Excel XLS	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Natura 2000 areas	January, 2003 - December, 2020	NUTS2	95	
Nature reserves	January, 2017 - December, 2020	NUTS2	95	
Important protected animals	January, 2003 - December, 2020	NUTS2	95	
Legal protected area	January, 2003 - December, 2020	NUTS2	95	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
northern chamois	Socioeconomic variable	head	January, 2003 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Important protected animals
brown bear	Socioeconomic variable	head	January, 2003 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Important protected animals
eurasian beaver	Socioeconomic variable	head	January, 2003 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Important protected animals

eurasian lynx	Socioeconomic variable	head	January, 2003 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Important protected animals
gray wolf	Socioeconomic variable	head	January, 2003 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Important protected animals
european bison	Socioeconomic variable	head	January, 2003 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Important protected animals
Legal protected area in total	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2003 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Legal protected area
national parks	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2003 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Legal protected area
nature reserves	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2003 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Legal protected area
landscape parks, total	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2003 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Legal protected area
reserves and other forms of nature conservation on the landscape parks	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2003 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Legal protected area
protected landscape areas total	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2003 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Legal protected area
reserves and other forms of nature conservation on protected landscape areas	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2003 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Legal protected area
ecological areas	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2003 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Legal protected area

documentation sites	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2003 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Legal protected area
landscape-nature complexes	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2003 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Legal protected area
Special Protection Areas of birds (SPAs) in total	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2005 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Natura 2000 areas
Special Protection Areas of birds (SPAs) - % of total area	Socioeconomic variable	%	January, 2005 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Natura 2000 areas
Special Areas of Conservation of habitats (SACs) in total	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2005 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Natura 2000 areas
Special Areas of Conservation of habitats (SACs) - % of total area	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2005 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Natura 2000 areas
number of Nature reserves in total	Socioeconomic variable	pcs	January, 2017 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Nature reserves
number reserves of fauna	Socioeconomic variable	pcs	January, 2017 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Nature reserves
number reserves of landscape	Socioeconomic variable	pcs	January, 2017 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Nature reserves

number reserves of peatbog	Socioeconomic variable	pcs	January, 2017 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Nature reserves
number reserves of flora	Socioeconomic variable	pcs	January, 2017 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Nature reserves
number reserves of water	Socioeconomic variable	pcs	January, 2017 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Nature reserves
number inanimate nature	Socioeconomic variable	pcs	January, 2017 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Nature reserves
number reserves of steppe	Socioeconomic variable	pcs	January, 2017 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Nature reserves
number reserves of halophyte	Socioeconomic variable	pcs	January, 2017 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Nature reserves
number reserves of forest	Socioeconomic variable	pcs	January, 2017 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Nature reserves
area of Nature reserves in total	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2017 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Nature reserves
area under strict protection in total	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2017 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Nature reserves
average area of 1 establishment in total	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2017 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Nature reserves
area of reserves of fauna	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2017 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Nature reserves

area under strict protection of fauna	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2017 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Nature reserves
average area of 1 establishment of fauna	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2017 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Nature reserves
area under strict protection of Nature reserves in total	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2017 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Nature reserves
average area of 1 establishment of Nature reserves in total	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2017 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Nature reserves
area of landscape	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2017 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Nature reserves
area under strict protection of landscape	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2017 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Nature reserves
average area of 1 establishment of landscape	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2017 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Nature reserves
area of peatbog	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2017 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Nature reserves
area under strict protection of peatbog	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2017 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Nature reserves
average area of 1 establishment of peatbog	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2017 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Nature reserves

area of flora	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2017 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Nature reserves
area under strict protection of flora	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2017 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Nature reserves
average area of 1 establishment of flora	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2017 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Nature reserves
area of water	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2017 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Nature reserves
area under strict protection of water	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2017 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Nature reserves
average area of 1 establishment of water	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2017 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Nature reserves
area of inanimate nature	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2017 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Nature reserves
area under strict protection of inanimate nature	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2017 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Nature reserves
average area of 1 establishment of inanimate nature	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2017 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Nature reserves
area of steppe	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2017 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Nature reserves

area under strict protection of steppe	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2017 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Nature reserves
average area of 1 establishment of steppe	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2017 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Nature reserves
area of halophyte	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2017 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Nature reserves
area of forest	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2017 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Nature reserves
area under strict protection of halophyte	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2017 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Nature reserves
average area of 1 establishment of halophyte	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2017 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Nature reserves
area under strict protection of forest	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2017 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Nature reserves
average area of 1 establishment of forest	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2017 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Nature reserves

Agrifood Foreign Trade Statistics (Table 8 - Main agri-food products exported by Andalusia and Spain)

General information

Description: This statistical activity offers the main data and reports of the Andalusian Agrifood Trade Balance. Main agri-food products exported by Andalusia and Spain

Producer: Regional ministry of agriculture, livestock, fisheries and sustainable development

Link: <https://www.juntadeandalucia.es/organismos/agriculturaganaderiapescaydesarrollosostenible/servicios/estadistica-cartografia/actividad/detalle/175076/175464.html>

Languages: Spanish | Castilian

Catalogue:

Subjects: Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Agricultural value added, Agricultural costs

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Monthly

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: ES6

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 14, 2022

Characterization created at: December 7, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2005

Last update: December 23, 2021

Periodicity: Monthly

Temporal extent: January, 2005 - December, 2021

Keywords: agricultural economy, agricultural sector, foreign trade, balance

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Main agri-food products exported by Andalusia & Spain	Excel XLS	Public	https://www.juntadeandalucia.es/organismos/agriculturaganaderiapescaydesarrollosostenible/servicios/estadisticas-cartografia/estadisticas-agricolas/paginas/comercio-exterior-agricola.html	Excel XLS	False
Main agri-food products exported by Andalusia & Spain	PDF	Public	https://www.juntadeandalucia.es/organismos/agriculturaganaderiapescaydesarrollosostenible/servicios/estadisticas-cartografia/actividad/detalle/175076/175464.html	PDF	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
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Agri-food product	January, 2005 - December, 2021	NUTS2		
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Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Value Exported by Spain	Socioeconomic variable	Thousands of Euros	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Sum	Monthly	Agri-food product
Value Exported by Andalusia	Socioeconomic variable	Thousands of Euros	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Sum	Monthly	Agri-food product
Percentage Value Exported Andalusia/Spain	Socioeconomic variable	% value exported	January, 2005 - December, 2021	Instant value	Monthly	Agri-food product

Agricultural Census GENERAL DISTRIBUTION OF AREA: Exploitation of cultivated Dry lands

General information

Description: Census. Collection of information regarding the agrarian structure, to serve as the basis for the directory of agricultural operations, in compliance with the legal regulations established by the European Union

Producer: Spanish National Statistics Institute

Link: https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106

Languages: Spanish | Castilian

Catalogue:

Subjects: agricultural product, agricultural region, agricultural statistics

Useful for the analysis of: Use of agricultural area

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: National Statistics Institute (Spain)

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Spain

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 18, 2022

Characterization created at: December 13, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2009

Last update: December 31, 2012

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2009

Keywords: agricultural area

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Agricultural Census	Excel XLSX	Public	https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural holding with UAA	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
All cultivated lands	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Combined arable	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
All cultivated lands (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA

Combined arable (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Fruit trees (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Olive groves (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Vineyards (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Other cultivated lands (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Fruit trees	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Olive groves	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Vineyards	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Other cultivated lands	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA

BDSICE. Price and costs. Agricultural wage index

General information

Description:

The dataset collects the evolution of gross daily income corresponding to a worker within the following categories: fixed and eventual workers, tractorists, reapers and collectors, shepherds, cowboys and porkers and foremans mandated. Series linked since January 1985 in function of the antique base series 1976.

Producer: Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food

Link: <https://www.mapa.gob.es/es/estadistica/temas/estadisticas-agrarias/economia/precios-percibidos-pagados-salarios/salarios-agrarios/default.aspx>

Languages: Spanish | Castilian

Catalogue:

Subjects: cost analysis, wage earner, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Agricultural costs

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Monthly

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Spain

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 14, 2022

Characterization created at: December 9, 2021

Issued: January 1, 1976

Last update: July 31, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 1976 - July, 2021

Keywords: agricultural holdings, agricultural economy, agricultural sector, agricultural cost , wage

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Agricultural wages (PDF)	PDF	Public	https://www.mapa.gob.es/es/estadistica/temas/estadisticas-agrarias/economia/precios-percibidos-pagados-salarios/salarios-agrarios/default.aspx	PDF	False
Agricultural wages (Excel spreadsheet)	Excel XLSX	Public	https://www.mapa.gob.es/es/estadistica/temas/estadisticas-agrarias/economia/precios-percibidos-pagados-salarios/salarios-agrarios/default.aspx	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural wage indices (CASUAL LABOURERS)	January, 1985 - July, 2021	Country		

National average daily wages	January, 1985 - July, 2021	Country		
Agricultural wage indices (FIXED LABOUR FORCE)	January, 1985 - July, 2021	Country		

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Foremen	Socioeconomic variable	Euros	January, 1985 - July, 2021	Average	Monthly	National average daily wages , Agricultural wage indices (FIXED LABOUR FORCE)
Tractor and engine drivers	Socioeconomic variable	Euros	January, 1985 - July, 2021	Average	Monthly	National average daily wages , Agricultural wage indices (FIXED LABOUR FORCE)
Shepherds	Socioeconomic variable	Euros	January, 1985 - July, 2021	Average	Monthly	National average daily wages , Agricultural wage indices (FIXED LABOUR FORCE)
Cowherds and herdsmen	Socioeconomic variable	Euros	January, 1985 - July, 2021	Average	Monthly	National average daily wages , Agricultural wage indices (FIXED LABOUR FORCE)
Horticulturalists	Socioeconomic variable	Euros	January, 1985 - July, 2021	Average	Monthly	National average daily wages , Agricultural wage indices (FIXED LABOUR FORCE)
Guardsmen and farm labourers	Socioeconomic variable	Euros	January, 1985 - July, 2021	Average	Monthly	National average daily wages , Agricultural wage indices (FIXED LABOUR FORCE)
Permanent labourer	Socioeconomic variable	Euros	January, 1985 - July, 2021	Average	Monthly	National average daily wages , Agricultural wage indices (FIXED LABOUR FORCE)
Land preparation	Socioeconomic variable	Euros	January, 1985 - July, 2021	Average	Monthly	National average daily wages , Agricultural wage indices (CASUAL LABOURERS)
Sowing and fertilising	Socioeconomic variable	Euros	January, 1985 - July, 2021	Average	Monthly	National average daily wages , Agricultural wage indices (CASUAL LABOURERS)
Complementary work	Socioeconomic variable	Euros	January, 1985 - July, 2021	Average	Monthly	National average daily wages , Agricultural wage indices (CASUAL LABOURERS)
Irrigation	Socioeconomic variable	Euros	January, 1985 - July, 2021	Average	Monthly	National average daily wages , Agricultural wage indices (CASUAL LABOURERS)

Pest treatments	Socioeconomic variable	Euros	January, 1985 - July, 2021	Average	Monthly	National average daily wages , Agricultural wage indices (CASUAL LABOURERS)
Harvesting herbaceous products	Socioeconomic variable	Euros	January, 1985 - July, 2021	Average	Monthly	National average daily wages , Agricultural wage indices (CASUAL LABOURERS)
Harvesting fruit and citrus trees	Socioeconomic variable	Euros	January, 1985 - July, 2021	Average	Monthly	National average daily wages , Agricultural wage indices (CASUAL LABOURERS)
Olive harvesting	Socioeconomic variable	Euros	January, 1985 - July, 2021	Average	Monthly	National average daily wages , Agricultural wage indices (CASUAL LABOURERS)
Harvesting	Socioeconomic variable	Euros	January, 1985 - July, 2021	Average	Monthly	National average daily wages , Agricultural wage indices (CASUAL LABOURERS)
Pruning	Socioeconomic variable	Euros	January, 1985 - July, 2021	Average	Monthly	National average daily wages , Agricultural wage indices (CASUAL LABOURERS)
Planting and felling of trees	Socioeconomic variable	Euros	January, 1985 - July, 2021	Average	Monthly	National average daily wages , Agricultural wage indices (CASUAL LABOURERS)
Livestock management	Socioeconomic variable	Euros	January, 1985 - July, 2021	Average	Monthly	National average daily wages , Agricultural wage indices (CASUAL LABOURERS)
Fixed labour force index	Socioeconomic variable	Euros	January, 1985 - July, 2021	Average	Monthly	Agricultural wage indices (FIXED LABOUR FORCE)
Casual labour force index	Socioeconomic variable	Euros	January, 1985 - July, 2021	Average	Monthly	Agricultural wage indices (CASUAL LABOURERS)
General labour force index	Socioeconomic variable	Euros	January, 1985 - July, 2021	Average	Monthly	

Agricultural Census: Number, total area and used agricultural area (UAA) of Agricultural Holdings

General information

Description: Census. Collection of information regarding the agrarian structure, to serve as the basis for the directory of agricultural operations, in compliance with the legal regulations established by the European Union

Producer: Spanish National Statistics Institute

Link: https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106

Languages: Spanish | Castilian

Catalogue:

Subjects: agricultural product, agricultural region, agricultural statistics

Useful for the analysis of: Use of agricultural area

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: National Statistics Institute (Spain)

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Spain

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 17, 2022

Characterization created at: December 13, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2009

Last update: December 31, 2012

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2009

Keywords: agricultural area

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Agricultural Census	Excel XLSX	Public	https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural Holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Percentage of agricultural holdings of a given type in relation to the total number of holdings	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings

Total land area per type of Agricultural Holding	Socioeconomic variable	Hectares (ha)	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
Percentage of land associated with holdings of a given type in relation to the total area for all holdings.	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
Percentage of UAA associated with holdings of a given type in relation to the total UAA for all holdings.	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
Total Utilised Agricultural Area per type of Agricultural Holding	Socioeconomic variable	Hectares (ha)	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings
Number of Agricultural Holdings of each type	Socioeconomic variable	Number of Agricultural Holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings

AREA-RICA - Report structural characteristics of agricultural holdings (CARATTERISTICHE STRUTTURALI)

General information

Description: This dataset shows the structural characteristics of agricultural holdings in Italy.

Producer: AREA-RICA

Link: https://arearica.crea.gov.it/report_a.php

Languages: Italian

Catalogue: RICA - report

Subjects: agricultural holdings, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Farm Structure

Useful for the analysis of: Farm economic size, Farm structure

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Year

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: AREA-RICA

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Italy

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 11, 2022

Characterization created at: December 9, 2021

Issued:

Last update: December 31, 2019

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2008 - December, 2019

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Excel	Excel XLS	Public	https://arearica.crea.gov.it/report_a.php	Excel XLS	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Farm holding	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Geonames	37	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Irrigable area (Superficie irrigabile)	Socioeconomic variable	number	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding
Power of holding machines (Potenza motrice)	Socioeconomic variable	kw	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding
Holdings (Aziende rappresentate)	Socioeconomic variable	number	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding

Total area (Superficie totale)	Socioeconomic variable	hectares	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding
Land use (Superficie agricola utilizzata)	Socioeconomic variable	hectares	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding
Land use in property (superficie agricola utilizzata in proprietà)	Socioeconomic variable	hectares	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding
Annual work unit (Unità di lavoro annue)	Socioeconomic variable	awu	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding
Family Work Unit (Unità di lavoro familiari)	Socioeconomic variable	awu	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding
Bovine Adult Unit (Unità bovine adulte)	Socioeconomic variable	bau	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding
Average age of tractors (Età media delle trattrici)	Socioeconomic variable	years	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm holding

Agricultural Census CROPS: Arable crops and fallow lands: cereals for grain

General information

Description: Census. Collection of information regarding the agrarian structure, to serve as the basis for the directory of agricultural operations, in compliance with the legal regulations established by the European Union

Producer: Spanish National Statistics Institute

Link: https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106

Languages: Spanish | Castilian

Catalogue:

Subjects: agricultural product, agricultural region, agricultural statistics, Agricultural and aquaculture facilities, Land use

Useful for the analysis of: Use of agricultural area

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: Regular updating of the national census of agricultural holdings

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Spain

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 17, 2022

Characterization created at: December 13, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2009

Last update: December 31, 2012

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2009

Keywords: agricultural area

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Agricultural Census	Excel XLSX	Public	https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural Holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Country	100	
Agricultural Holdings with UAA (20 to <30)	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Country	100	
Agricultural Holdings with UAA (2 to <5)	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Country	100	
Agricultural Holdings with UAA (5 to <10)	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Country	100	
Agricultural Holdings with UAA (10 to <20)	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Country	100	
Agricultural Holdings with UAA (30 to <50)	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Country	100	

Agricultural Holdings with UAA (<1)	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Country	100	
Agricultural Holdings with UAA (50 to <100)	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Country	100	
Agricultural Holdings with UAA (1 to <2)	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Country	100	
Agricultural Holdings with UAA (>= 100)	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Number of Agricultural Holdings cropping Grain Cereals	Socioeconomic variable	Number of Agricultural Holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings with UAA (<1), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (1 to <2), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (2 to <5), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (5 to <10), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (10 to <20), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (20 to <30), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (30 to <50), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (50 to <100), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (>= 100), Agricultural Holdings
Area of Agricultural Holdings cropping Wheat with Irrigation	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings with UAA (<1), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (1 to <2), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (2 to <5), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (5 to <10), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (10 to <20), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (20 to <30), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (30 to <50), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (50 to <100), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (>= 100)

Area of Agricultural Holdings cropping Cereals	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings with UAA (<1), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (1 to <2), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (2 to <5), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (5 to <10), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (10 to <20), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (20 to <30), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (30 to <50), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (50 to <100), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (>= 100), Agricultural Holdings
Number of Agricultural Holdings cropping Dry Grain Cereals	Socioeconomic variable	Number of Agricultural Holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings with UAA (<1), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (1 to <2), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (2 to <5), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (5 to <10), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (10 to <20), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (20 to <30), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (30 to <50), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (50 to <100), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (>= 100), Agricultural Holdings
Area of Agricultural Holdings cropping Dry Wheat	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings with UAA (50 to <100), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (>= 100), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (<1), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (1 to <2), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (2 to <5), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (5 to <10), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (10 to <20), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (20 to <30), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (30 to <50)
Area of Agricultural Holdings cropping dry Rye	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings with UAA (50 to <100), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (>= 100), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (<1), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (1 to <2), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (2 to <5),

						Agricultural Holdings with UAA (5 to <10), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (10 to <20), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (20 to <30), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (30 to <50), Agricultural Holdings
Area of Agricultural Holdings cropping dry common Wheat	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings with UAA (50 to <100), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (>= 100), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (<1), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (1 to <2), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (2 to <5), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (5 to <10), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (10 to <20), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (20 to <30), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (30 to <50), Agricultural Holdings
Number of Agricultural Holdings cropping Common Wheat with Irrigation	Socioeconomic variable	Number of Agricultural Holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings with UAA (<1), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (1 to <2), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (2 to <5), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (5 to <10), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (10 to <20), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (20 to <30), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (30 to <50), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (50 to <100), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (>= 100), Agricultural Holdings
Area of Agricultural Holdings cropping common Wheat with Irrigation	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings with UAA (<1), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (1 to <2), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (2 to <5), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (5 to <10), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (10 to <20), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (20 to <30), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (30 to <50), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (50 to <100), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (>= 100), Agricultural Holdings

Number of Agricultural Holdings cropping Durum Wheat (any kind)	Socioeconomic variable	Number of Agricultural Holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings with UAA (<1), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (1 to <2), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (2 to <5), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (5 to <10), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (10 to <20), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (20 to <30), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (30 to <50), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (50 to <100), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (>= 100), Agricultural Holdings
Area of Agricultural Holdings cropping Durum Wheat	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings with UAA (<1), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (1 to <2), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (2 to <5), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (5 to <10), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (10 to <20), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (20 to <30), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (30 to <50), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (50 to <100), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (>= 100), Agricultural Holdings
Other (including other mixes of cereals): Irrigation (operations)	Socioeconomic variable	Operations number	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings with UAA (<1), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (1 to <2), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (2 to <5), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (5 to <10), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (10 to <20), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (20 to <30), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (30 to <50), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (50 to <100), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (>= 100)
Area of Agricultural Holdings cropping dry Grain Cereals	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings with UAA (<1), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (1 to <2), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (2 to <5), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (5 to <10), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (10 to

						<20), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (20 to <30), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (30 to <50), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (50 to <100), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (>= 100), Agricultural Holdings
Area of Agricultural Holdings cropping Wheat (any kind)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings with UAA (<1), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (1 to <2), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (2 to <5), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (5 to <10), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (10 to <20), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (20 to <30), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (30 to <50), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (50 to <100), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (>= 100), Agricultural Holdings
Number of Agricultural Holdings cropping common Wheat (any kind)	Socioeconomic variable	Number of Agricultural Holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings with UAA (<1), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (1 to <2), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (2 to <5), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (5 to <10), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (10 to <20), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (20 to <30), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (30 to <50), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (50 to <100), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (>= 100), Agricultural Holdings
Area of Agricultural Holdings cropping Common Wheat	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings with UAA (5 to <10), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (10 to <20), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (20 to <30), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (30 to <50), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (50 to <100), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (>= 100), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (<1), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (1 to <2), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (2 to <5), Agricultural Holdings

Number of Agricultural Holdings cropping Dry Common Wheat	Socioeconomic variable	Number of Agricultural Holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings with UAA (<1), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (1 to <2), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (2 to <5), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (5 to <10), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (10 to <20), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (20 to <30), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (30 to <50), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (50 to <100), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (>= 100), Agricultural Holdings
Number of Agricultural Holdings cropping Dry Durum Wheat	Socioeconomic variable	Number of Agricultural Holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings with UAA (<1), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (1 to <2), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (2 to <5), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (5 to <10), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (10 to <20), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (20 to <30), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (30 to <50), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (50 to <100), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (>= 100), Agricultural Holdings
Area of Agricultural Holdings cropping Dry Durum Common Wheat: Dry (area	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings with UAA (50 to <100), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (>= 100), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (<1), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (1 to <2), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (2 to <5), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (5 to <10), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (10 to <20), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (20 to <30), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (30 to <50), Agricultural Holdings
Number of Agricultural Holdings cropping Durum	Socioeconomic variable	Number of Agricultural Holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings with UAA (<1), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (1 to <2), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (2 to <5), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (5 to <10), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (10 to

Wheat with Irrigation						<20), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (20 to <30), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (30 to <50), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (50 to <100), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (>= 100), Agricultural Holdings
Area of Agricultural Holdings cropping Durum Wheat with Irrigation (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings with UAA (<1), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (1 to <2), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (2 to <5), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (5 to <10), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (10 to <20), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (20 to <30), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (30 to <50), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (50 to <100), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (>= 100), Agricultural Holdings
Number of Agricultural Holdings cropping Barley (any kind)	Socioeconomic variable	Number of Agricultural Holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings with UAA (<1), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (1 to <2), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (2 to <5), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (5 to <10), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (10 to <20), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (20 to <30), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (30 to <50), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (50 to <100), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (>= 100), Agricultural Holdings
Area of Agricultural Holdings cropping Barley (any kind)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings with UAA (<1), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (1 to <2), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (2 to <5), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (5 to <10), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (10 to <20), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (20 to <30), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (30 to <50), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (50 to <100), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (>= 100), Agricultural Holdings

Number of Agricultural Holdings cropping Dry Barley	Socioeconomic variable	Number of Agricultural Holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings with UAA (<1), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (1 to <2), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (2 to <5), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (5 to <10), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (10 to <20), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (20 to <30), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (30 to <50), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (50 to <100), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (>= 100), Agricultural Holdings
Area of Agricultural Holdings cropping Dry Barley	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings with UAA (50 to <100), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (>= 100), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (<1), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (1 to <2), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (2 to <5), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (5 to <10), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (10 to <20), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (20 to <30), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (30 to <50), Agricultural Holdings
Number of Agricultural Holdings cropping Barley with Irrigation	Socioeconomic variable	Number of Agricultural Holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings with UAA (<1), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (1 to <2), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (2 to <5), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (5 to <10), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (10 to <20), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (20 to <30), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (30 to <50), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (50 to <100), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (>= 100), Agricultural Holdings
Area of Agricultural Holdings cropping Barley with Irrigation	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings with UAA (<1), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (1 to <2), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (2 to <5), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (5 to <10), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (10 to

						<20), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (20 to <30), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (30 to <50), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (50 to <100), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (>= 100), Agricultural Holdings
Number of Agricultural Holdings Oats (any kind)	Socioeconomic variable	Number of Agricultural Holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings with UAA (<1), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (1 to <2), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (2 to <5), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (5 to <10), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (10 to <20), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (20 to <30), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (30 to <50), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (50 to <100), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (>= 100), Agricultural Holdings
Area of Agricultural Holdings cropping Oats (any kind)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings with UAA (<1), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (1 to <2), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (2 to <5), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (5 to <10), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (10 to <20), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (20 to <30), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (30 to <50), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (50 to <100), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (>= 100), Agricultural Holdings
Number of Agricultural Holdings cropping Dry Oats	Socioeconomic variable	Number of Agricultural Holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings with UAA (<1), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (1 to <2), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (2 to <5), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (5 to <10), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (10 to <20), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (20 to <30), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (30 to <50), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (50 to <100), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (>= 100), Agricultural Holdings

Area of Agricultural Holdings cropping Dry Oats	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings with UAA (50 to <100), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (>= 100), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (<1), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (1 to <2), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (2 to <5), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (5 to <10), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (10 to <20), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (20 to <30), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (30 to <50), Agricultural Holdings
Number of Agricultural Holdings cropping Oats with Irrigation	Socioeconomic variable	Number of Agricultural Holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings with UAA (<1), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (1 to <2), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (2 to <5), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (5 to <10), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (10 to <20), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (20 to <30), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (30 to <50), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (50 to <100), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (>= 100), Agricultural Holdings
Area of Agricultural Holdings cropping Oats with Irrigation	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings with UAA (<1), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (1 to <2), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (2 to <5), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (5 to <10), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (10 to <20), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (20 to <30), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (30 to <50), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (50 to <100), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (>= 100), Agricultural Holdings
Number of Agricultural Holdings cropping Rye	Socioeconomic variable	Number of Agricultural Holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings with UAA (<1), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (1 to <2), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (2 to <5), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (5 to <10), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (10 to

						<20), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (20 to <30), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (30 to <50), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (50 to <100), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (>= 100), Agricultural Holdings
Area of Agricultural Holdings cropping Rye (any kind)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings with UAA (<1), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (1 to <2), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (2 to <5), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (5 to <10), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (10 to <20), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (20 to <30), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (30 to <50), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (50 to <100), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (>= 100), Agricultural Holdings
Number of Agricultural Holdings cropping Dry Rye	Socioeconomic variable	Number of Agricultural Holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings with UAA (<1), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (1 to <2), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (2 to <5), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (5 to <10), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (10 to <20), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (20 to <30), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (30 to <50), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (50 to <100), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (>= 100), Agricultural Holdings
Number of Agricultural Holdings cropping Rye with Irrigation	Socioeconomic variable	Number of Agricultural Holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings with UAA (<1), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (1 to <2), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (2 to <5), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (5 to <10), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (10 to <20), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (20 to <30), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (30 to <50), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (50 to <100), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (>= 100), Agricultural Holdings

Area of Agricultural Holdings cropping Rye with Irrigation	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings with UAA (<1), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (1 to <2), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (2 to <5), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (5 to <10), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (10 to <20), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (20 to <30), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (30 to <50), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (50 to <100), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (>= 100), Agricultural Holdings
Number of Agricultural Holdings cropping Corn (any kind)	Socioeconomic variable	Number of Agricultural Holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings with UAA (<1), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (1 to <2), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (2 to <5), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (5 to <10), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (10 to <20), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (20 to <30), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (30 to <50), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (50 to <100), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (>= 100), Agricultural Holdings
Area of Agricultural Holdings cropping Corn (any kind)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings with UAA (<1), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (1 to <2), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (2 to <5), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (5 to <10), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (10 to <20), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (20 to <30), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (30 to <50), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (50 to <100), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (>= 100), Agricultural Holdings
Number of Agricultural Holdings cropping Dry Corn	Socioeconomic variable	Number of Agricultural Holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings with UAA (<1), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (1 to <2), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (2 to <5), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (5 to <10), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (10 to

						<20), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (20 to <30), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (30 to <50), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (50 to <100), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (>= 100), Agricultural Holdings
Area of Agricultural Holdings cropping Dry Corn	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings with UAA (50 to <100), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (>= 100), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (<1), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (1 to <2), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (2 to <5), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (5 to <10), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (10 to <20), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (20 to <30), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (30 to <50), Agricultural Holdings
Number of Agricultural Holdings cropping Corn with Irrigation	Socioeconomic variable	Number of Agricultural Holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings with UAA (<1), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (1 to <2), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (2 to <5), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (5 to <10), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (10 to <20), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (20 to <30), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (30 to <50), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (50 to <100), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (>= 100), Agricultural Holdings
Area of Agricultural Holdings cropping Corn with Irrigation	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings with UAA (<1), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (1 to <2), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (2 to <5), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (5 to <10), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (10 to <20), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (20 to <30), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (30 to <50), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (50 to <100), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (>= 100)

Number of Agricultural Holdings cropping Other Cereals (including other mixes of cereals)	Socioeconomic variable	Number of Agricultural Holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings with UAA (<1), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (1 to <2), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (2 to <5), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (5 to <10), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (10 to <20), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (20 to <30), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (30 to <50), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (50 to <100), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (>= 100), Agricultural Holdings
Area of Agricultural Holdings cropping Other Cereals (including other mixes of cereals)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings with UAA (<1), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (1 to <2), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (2 to <5), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (5 to <10), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (10 to <20), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (20 to <30), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (30 to <50), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (50 to <100), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (>= 100), Agricultural Holdings
Number of Agricultural Holdings cropping Other Dry Cereals (including other mixes of cereals)	Socioeconomic variable	Number of Agricultural Holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings with UAA (<1), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (1 to <2), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (2 to <5), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (5 to <10), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (10 to <20), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (20 to <30), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (30 to <50), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (50 to <100), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (>= 100), Agricultural Holdings
Area of Agricultural Holdings cropping Other Cereals	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings with UAA (50 to <100), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (>= 100), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (<1), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (1 to <2), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (2 to <5),

(including other mixes of cereals)						Agricultural Holdings with UAA (5 to <10), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (10 to <20), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (20 to <30), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (30 to <50), Agricultural Holdings
Area of Agricultural Holdings cropping Other Cereals (including other mixes of cereals) with Irrigation	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings with UAA (<1), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (1 to <2), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (2 to <5), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (5 to <10), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (10 to <20), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (20 to <30), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (30 to <50), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (50 to <100), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (>= 100), Agricultural Holdings
Number of Agricultural Holdings cropping Rice with Irrigation	Socioeconomic variable	Number of Agricultural Holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings with UAA (<1), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (1 to <2), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (2 to <5), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (5 to <10), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (10 to <20), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (20 to <30), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (30 to <50), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (50 to <100), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (>= 100), Agricultural Holdings
Area of Agricultural Holdings cropping Rice with Irrigation	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings with UAA (<1), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (1 to <2), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (2 to <5), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (5 to <10), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (10 to <20), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (20 to <30), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (30 to <50), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (50 to <100), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (>= 100), Agricultural Holdings

Number of Agricultural Holdings cropping cereals for grain with Irrigation	Socioeconomic variable	Number of Agricultural Holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings with UAA (<1), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (1 to <2), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (2 to <5), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (5 to <10), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (10 to <20), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (20 to <30), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (30 to <50), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (50 to <100), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (>= 100), Agricultural Holdings
Area of Agricultural Holdings cropping cereals for grain with Irrigation	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings with UAA (<1), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (1 to <2), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (2 to <5), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (5 to <10), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (10 to <20), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (20 to <30), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (30 to <50), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (50 to <100), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (>= 100), Agricultural Holdings
Number of Agricultural Holdings cropping Wheat (any kind)	Socioeconomic variable	Number of Agricultural Holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings with UAA (<1), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (1 to <2), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (2 to <5), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (5 to <10), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (10 to <20), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (20 to <30), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (30 to <50), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (50 to <100), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (>= 100), Agricultural Holdings
Number of Agricultural Holdings cropping Dry Wheat	Socioeconomic variable	Number of Agricultural Holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings with UAA (<1), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (1 to <2), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (2 to <5), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (5 to <10), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (10 to

						<20), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (20 to <30), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (30 to <50), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (50 to <100), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (>= 100), Agricultural Holdings
Number of Agricultural Holdings cropping irrigated Wheat	Socioeconomic variable	Number of Agricultural Holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural Holdings with UAA (<1), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (1 to <2), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (2 to <5), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (5 to <10), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (10 to <20), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (20 to <30), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (30 to <50), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (50 to <100), Agricultural Holdings with UAA (>= 100), Agricultural Holdings

Agricultural Census: LEGAL PERSONALITY OF THE TITLE HOLDER AND LAND TENURE REGIME: Number and UAA of agricultural holdings with land under more than one tenancy regimee

General information

Description: Census. Collection of information regarding the agrarian structure, to serve as the basis for the directory of agricultural operations, in compliance with the legal regulations established by the European Union

Producer: Spanish National Statistics Institute

Link: https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106

Languages: Spanish | Castilian

Catalogue:

Subjects: agricultural product, agricultural region, agricultural statistics

Useful for the analysis of: Use of agricultural area

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: Nationa Statistics Institute (Spain)

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Spain

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 18, 2022

Characterization created at: December 13, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2009

Last update: March 21, 2012

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2009

Keywords: agricultural area

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Agricultural Census	Excel XLSX	Public	https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural holding with UAA	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
No tenancy regime greater than 50% of UAA (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
No tenancy regime greater	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA

than 50% of UAA						
More than 50% of UAA in ownership (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
More than 50% of UAA in crop-share and other regimes (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
More than 50% of UAA in ownership	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
More than 50% of UAA under lease (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
More than 50% of UAA under lease	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
More than 50% of UAA in crop-share and other regimes	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA

Commercialization of Phytosanitary Products

General information

Description: Determinate the quantities of active substances, by category of products and chemical classification, expressed in kilograms of substance, contained in the phytosanitary products marketed by the holders of authorization of these products, whose destination is agricultural use

Producer: MINISTRY OF AGRICULTURE, FISHERIES AND FOOD

Link: <https://www.mapa.gob.es/es/estadistica/temas/estadisticas-agrarias/agricultura/estadisticas-medios-produccion/fitosanitarios.aspx>

Languages: Spanish | Castilian

Catalogue:

Subjects: agricultural product, agricultural market, pesticide, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Economy and finance

Useful for the analysis of: Agricultural costs, Pesticides use

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Spain

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 13, 2022

Characterization created at: December 13, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2011

Last update: December 31, 2019

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2011 - December, 2019

Keywords: marketing of plant protection products;, agricultural product; , pesticides use

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Commercialization of Phytosanitary Products	PDF	Public	https://www.mapa.gob.es/es/estadistica/temas/estadisticas-agrarias/agricultura/estadisticas-medios-produccion/fitosanitarios.aspx	PDF	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Change in quantities traded between year n and year n-1 at constant population and contribution to total growth rate.	January, 2011 - December, 2019	Country		
Quantity of active substances placed on the market in the year (by category of substances and expressed in tonnes).	January, 2011 - December, 2019	Country		
Quantities placed on the market by the authorised holders of the main groups of active substances	January, 2011 - December, 2019	Country		

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Insecticides (percentages)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentages	January, 2011 - December, 2019	Average	Annual	Quantities placed on the market by the authorised holders of the main groups of active substances
Insecticides and Acaricides (Change in pp)	Socioeconomic variable	Change in pp	January, 2011 - December, 2019	Average	Annual	Quantities placed on the market by the authorised holders of the main groups of active substances, Change in quantities traded between year n and year n-1 at constant population and contribution to total growth rate.
Growth regulators (Tons)	Socioeconomic variable	Tons	January, 2011 - December, 2019	Average	Annual	Quantities placed on the market by the authorised holders of the main groups of active substances
Growth regulators (percentages)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentages	January, 2011 - December, 2019	Average	Annual	Quantities placed on the market by the authorised holders of the main groups of active substances
Growth regulators (Change in pp)	Socioeconomic variable	Change in pp	January, 2011 - December, 2019	Average	Annual	Quantities placed on the market by the authorised holders of the main groups of active substances, Change in quantities traded between year n and year n-1 at constant population and contribution to total growth rate.
Triazine- and triazinone-based herbicides	Socioeconomic variable	Ton	January, 2011 - December, 2019	Average	Annual	Quantity of active substances placed on the market in the year (by category of substances and expressed in tonnes).
Amide- and anilide-based herbicides	Socioeconomic variable	Ton	January, 2011 - December, 2019	Average	Annual	Quantity of active substances placed on the market in the year (by category of substances and expressed in tonnes).
Herbicides based on cabamates bicarmamates	Socioeconomic variable	Ton	January, 2011 - December, 2019	Average	Annual	Quantity of active substances placed on the market in the year (by category of substances and expressed in tonnes).

Herbicides based on Dinitroanilides derivatives	Socioeconomic variable	Ton	January, 2011 - December, 2019	Average	Annual	Quantity of active substances placed on the market in the year (by category of substances and expressed in tonnes).
Herbicides based on urea, uracil or sulphonylurea derivatives	Socioeconomic variable	Ton	January, 2011 - December, 2019	Average	Annual	Quantity of active substances placed on the market in the year (by category of substances and expressed in tonnes).
Other insecticides	Socioeconomic variable	Ton	January, 2011 - December, 2019	Average	Annual	Quantity of active substances placed on the market in the year (by category of substances and expressed in tonnes).
Fungicides and Bactericides (Change in pp)	Socioeconomic variable	Change in pp	January, 2011 - December, 2019	Average	Annual	Quantities placed on the market by the authorised holders of the main groups of active substances, Change in quantities traded between year n and year n-1 at constant population and contribution to total growth rate.
Herbicides (Tons)	Socioeconomic variable	Tons	January, 2011 - December, 2019	Average	Annual	Quantities placed on the market by the authorised holders of the main groups of active substances
Molluscicides and other plant protection products (Tons)	Socioeconomic variable	Tons	January, 2011 - December, 2019	Average	Annual	Quantities placed on the market by the authorised holders of the main groups of active substances
Molluscicides and other plant protection products (percentages)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentages	January, 2011 - December, 2019	Average	Annual	Quantities placed on the market by the authorised holders of the main groups of active substances
Molluscicides and other plant protection products(Change in pp)	Socioeconomic variable	Change in pp	January, 2011 - December, 2019	Average	Annual	Quantities placed on the market by the authorised holders of the main groups of active substances, Change in quantities traded between year n and year n-1 at

						constant population and contribution to total growth rate.
Insecticides and acaracides(Tons)	Socioeconomic variable	Tons	January, 2011 - December, 2019	Average	Annual	Quantity of active substances placed on the market in the year (by category of substances and expressed in tonnes).
Fungicides and Bactericides(Tons)	Socioeconomic variable	Tons	January, 2011 - December, 2019	Average	Annual	Quantity of active substances placed on the market in the year (by category of substances and expressed in tonnes).
Herbicides(Tons)	Socioeconomic variable	Tons	January, 2011 - December, 2019	Average	Annual	Quantity of active substances placed on the market in the year (by category of substances and expressed in tonnes).
Growth Regulators (Tons)	Socioeconomic variable	Tons	January, 2011 - December, 2019	Average	Annual	Quantity of active substances placed on the market in the year (by category of substances and expressed in tonnes).
Benzimidazole-based fungicides	Socioeconomic variable	Ton	January, 2011 - December, 2019	Average	Annual	Quantity of active substances placed on the market in the year (by category of substances and expressed in tonnes).
Imidazole and Triazole-based fungicides	Socioeconomic variable	Ton	January, 2011 - December, 2019	Average	Annual	Quantity of active substances placed on the market in the year (by category of substances and expressed in tonnes).
Other Herbicides	Socioeconomic variable	Ton	January, 2011 - December, 2019	Average	Annual	Quantity of active substances placed on the market in the year (by category of substances and expressed in tonnes).
Pyrethroid-based insecticides	Socioeconomic variable	Ton	January, 2011 - December, 2019	Average	Annual	Quantity of active substances placed on the market in the year (by category of substances and expressed in tonnes).
Insecticides Carbamates Oxime-Carbamates	Socioeconomic variable	Ton	January, 2011 - December, 2019	Average	Annual	Quantity of active substances placed on the market in the year (by category of substances and expressed in tonnes).

Insecticide-based biological-botanical products	Socioeconomic variable	Ton	January, 2011 - December, 2019	Average	Annual	Quantity of active substances placed on the market in the year (by category of substances and expressed in tonnes).
Inorganic fungicides	Socioeconomic variable	Ton	January, 2011 - December, 2019	Average	Annual	Quantity of active substances placed on the market in the year (by category of substances and expressed in tonnes).
Carbamate and dithiocarbamate fungicides	Socioeconomic variable	Ton	January, 2011 - December, 2019	Average	Annual	Quantity of active substances placed on the market in the year (by category of substances and expressed in tonnes).
Fungicides and Bactericides (Tons)	Socioeconomic variable	Tons	January, 2011 - December, 2019	Average	Annual	Quantities placed on the market by the authorised holders of the main groups of active substances
Fungicides and Bactericides (percentages)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentages	January, 2011 - December, 2019	Average	Annual	Quantities placed on the market by the authorised holders of the main groups of active substances
Growth regulators	Socioeconomic variable	Tons	January, 2011 - December, 2019	Average	Annual	Quantity of active substances placed on the market in the year (by category of substances and expressed in tonnes).
Molluscicides and other plant protection products	Socioeconomic variable	Tons	January, 2011 - December, 2019	Average	Annual	Quantity of active substances placed on the market in the year (by category of substances and expressed in tonnes).
Herbicides (Change in pp)	Socioeconomic variable	Change in pp	January, 2011 - December, 2019	Average	Annual	Quantities placed on the market by the authorised holders of the main groups of active substances, Change in quantities traded between year n and year n-1 at constant population and contribution to total growth rate.
Herbicides (percentages)	Socioeconomic variable	Percentages	January, 2011 - December, 2019	Average	Annual	Quantities placed on the market by the authorised holders of the main groups of active substances

Insecticides (Tons)	Socioeconomic variable	Tons	January, 2011 - December, 2019	Average	Annual	Quantities placed on the market by the authorised holders of the main groups of active substances
Morpholine-based fungicides	Socioeconomic variable	Ton	January, 2011 - December, 2019	Average	Annual	Quantity of active substances placed on the market in the year (by category of substances and expressed in tonnes).
Microbiological or Botanical Fungicides	Socioeconomic variable	Ton	January, 2011 - December, 2019	Average	Annual	Quantity of active substances placed on the market in the year (by category of substances and expressed in tonnes).
Other fungicides	Socioeconomic variable	Ton	January, 2011 - December, 2019	Average	Annual	Quantity of active substances placed on the market in the year (by category of substances and expressed in tonnes).
Phenoxy-phytohormone herbicides	Socioeconomic variable	Ton	January, 2011 - December, 2019	Average	Annual	Quantity of active substances placed on the market in the year (by category of substances and expressed in tonnes).

Agricultural Census CROPS: Arable crops and fallow lands: Fodder crops

General information

Description: Census. Collection of information regarding the agrarian structure, to serve as the basis for the directory of agricultural operations, in compliance with the legal regulations established by the European Union

Producer: Spanish National Statistics Institute

Link: https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106

Languages: Spanish | Castilian

Catalogue:

Subjects: agricultural product, agricultural region, agricultural statistics

Useful for the analysis of: Use of agricultural area

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: National Statistics Institute (Spain)

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Spain

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 18, 2022

Characterization created at: December 13, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2009

Last update: November 3, 2011

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2009

Keywords: agricultural area

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Agricultural Census	Excel XLSX	Public	https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural holding with UAA	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Fodder crops: Total	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Fodder crops: Total (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Fodder crops: Dry farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA

Fodder crops: Dry farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Fodder crops: Irrigation farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Fodder crops: Irrigation farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Leguminous fodder plants: Irrigation farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Roots, tubers, etc.: Total	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Roots, tubers, etc.: Total (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Roots, tubers, etc.: Dry farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Roots, tubers, etc.: Dry farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Roots, tubers, etc.: Irrigation farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Roots, tubers, etc.: Irrigation farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA

Green, multiannual fodder plant: Total	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Green, multiannual fodder plant: Total (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Green, multiannual fodder plant: Dry farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Green, multiannual fodder plant: Dry farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Green, multiannual fodder plant: Irrigation farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Green, multiannual fodder plant: Irrigation farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Other green, multiannual fodder plant: Total	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Other green, multiannual	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA

fodder plant: Total (area)						
Other green, multiannual fodder plant: Dry farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Other green, multiannual fodder plant: Dry farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Other green, multiannual fodder plant: Irrigation farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Other green, multiannual fodder plant: Irrigation farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Green maize: Total	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Green maize: Total (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Green maize: Dry farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Green maize: Dry farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA

Green maize: Irrigation farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Green maize: Irrigation farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Leguminous fodder plants: Total	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Leguminous fodder plants: Total (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Leguminous fodder plants: Dry farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Leguminous fodder plants: Dry farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Leguminous fodder plants: Irrigation farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA

Agricultural Census CROPS: Arable crops and fallow lands: potato

General information

Description: Census. Collection of information regarding the agrarian structure, to serve as the basis for the directory of agricultural operations, in compliance with the legal regulations established by the European Union

Producer: Spanish National Statistics Institute

Link: https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106

Languages: Spanish | Castilian

Catalogue:

Subjects: agricultural product, agricultural region, agricultural statistics

Useful for the analysis of: Use of agricultural area

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: National Statistics Institute (Spain)

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Spain

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 18, 2022

Characterization created at: December 13, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2009

Last update: November 3, 2011

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2009

Keywords: agricultural area

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Agricultural Census	Excel XLSX	Public	https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural holding with UAA	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Total	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Dry farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Irrigation farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Total (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA

Dry farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Irrigation farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA

Agricultural Census CROPS: Arable crops and fallow lands: leguminous plants for grain

General information

Description: Census. Collection of information regarding the agrarian structure, to serve as the basis for the directory of agricultural operations, in compliance with the legal regulations established by the European Union

Producer: Spanish National Statistics Institute

Link: https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106

Languages: Spanish | Castilian

Catalogue:

Subjects: agricultural product, agricultural region, agricultural statistics

Useful for the analysis of: Use of agricultural area

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: National Statistics Institute (Spain)

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Spain

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 18, 2022

Characterization created at: December 13, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2009

Last update: March 4, 2016

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2009

Keywords: agricultural area

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Agricultural Census	Excel XLSX	Public	https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural holding with UAA	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Pulses for grain: Total	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Pulses for grain: Total (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Pulses for grain: Dry farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA

Pulses for grain: Dry farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Pulses for grain: Irrigation farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Pulses for grain: Irrigation farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Peas, beans, horse beans and sweet lupins: Irrigation farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Other leguminous plants (including mixes even though they are with cereals): Total	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Other leguminous plants (including mixes even though they are with cereals): Total (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Other leguminous plants (including	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA

mixes even though they are with cereals): Dry farming						
Other leguminous plants (including mixes even though they are with cereals): Dry farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Cickpeas, dried beans and lentils: Total	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Cickpeas, dried beans and lentils: Total (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Cickpeas, dried beans and lentils: Dry farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Cickpeas, dried beans and lentils: Dry farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Cickpeas, dried beans and lentils: Irrigation farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA

Cickpeas, dried beans and lentils: Irrigation farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Peas, beans, horse beans and sweet lupins: Total	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Peas, beans, horse beans and sweet lupins: Total (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Peas, beans, horse beans and sweet lupins: Dry farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Peas, beans, horse beans and sweet lupins: Dry farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Peas, beans, horse beans and sweet lupins: Irrigation farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Other leguminous plants (including mixes even though they are with cereals):	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA

Irrigation farming						
Other leguminous plants (including mixes even though they are with cereals): Irrigation farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA

Agricultural Census: LEGAL PERSONALITY OF THE TITLE HOLDER AND LAND TENURE REGIME: Number of UAA of agricultural holdings with all the land under just one tenancy regime

General information

Description: Census. Collection of information regarding the agrarian structure, to serve as the basis for the directory of agricultural operations, in compliance with the legal regulations established by the European Union

Producer: Spanish National Statistics Institute

Link: https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106

Languages: Spanish | Castilian

Catalogue:

Subjects: agricultural product, agricultural region, agricultural statistics

Useful for the analysis of: Use of agricultural area

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: National Statistics Institute (Spain)

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Spain

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 18, 2022

Characterization created at: December 13, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2009

Last update: November 3, 2011

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2009

Keywords: agricultural area

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Agricultural Census	Excel XLSX	Public	https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural holding with UAA	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
UAA owned	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
UAA rented	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA

UAA in sharecropping and other modes (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
UAA in sharecropping and other modes	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
UAA owned (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
UAA rented (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA

Agricultural Census: LEGAL PERSONALITY OF THE TITLE HOLDER AND LAND TENURE REGIME: Number and UAA of agricultural holdings according to tenancy regime

General information

Description: Census. Collection of information regarding the agrarian structure, to serve as the basis for the directory of agricultural operations, in compliance with the legal regulations established by the European Union

Producer: Spanish National Statistics Institute

Link: https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106

Languages: Spanish | Castilian

Catalogue:

Subjects: agricultural product, agricultural region, agricultural statistics

Useful for the analysis of: Use of agricultural area

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: National Statistics Institute (Spain)

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Spain

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 18, 2022

Characterization created at: December 13, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2009

Last update: November 3, 2011

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2009

Keywords: agricultural area

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Agricultural Census	Excel XLSX	Public	https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural holding with UAA	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
UAA in all regimes (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
UAA in all regimes	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA

UAA owned	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
UAA rented	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
UAA in sharecropping and other modes (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
UAA in sharecropping and other modes	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
UAA owned (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
UAA rented (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA

Agricultural Census GENERAL DISTRIBUTION OF AREA: Other Land

General information

Description: Census. Collection of information regarding the agrarian structure, to serve as the basis for the directory of agricultural operations, in compliance with the legal regulations established by the European Union

Producer: Spanish National Statistics Institute

Link: https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106

Languages: Spanish | Castilian

Catalogue:

Subjects: agricultural product, agricultural region, agricultural statistics

Useful for the analysis of: Use of agricultural area

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: National Statistics Institute (Spain)

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Spain

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 18, 2022

Characterization created at: December 13, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2009

Last update: November 3, 2011

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2009

Keywords: agricultural area, land cover, pastures lands

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Agricultural Census	Excel XLSX	Public	https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural holding	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Land with spontaneous vegetation and not used for agricultural purposes	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Land with spontaneous vegetation and	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding

not used for agricultural purposes (area)						
Forest tree species	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Other land	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Forest tree species (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding
Other land (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding

Agricultural Census GENERAL DISTRIBUTION OF AREA: Land for Permanent pastures

General information

Description: Census. Collection of information regarding the agrarian structure, to serve as the basis for the directory of agricultural operations, in compliance with the legal regulations established by the European Union

Producer: Spanish National Statistics Institute

Link: https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106

Languages: Spanish | Castilian

Catalogue:

Subjects: agricultural product, agricultural region, agricultural statistics

Useful for the analysis of: Use of agricultural area

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: National Statistics Institute (Spain)

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Spain

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 18, 2022

Characterization created at: December 13, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2009

Last update: November 3, 2011

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2009

Keywords: agricultural area, land cover, pastures lands

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Agricultural Census	Excel XLSX	Public	https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural holding with UAA	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Lands for permanent pastures: Total (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Lands for permanent pastures: Dry farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA

Lands for permanent pastures: Dry farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Lands for permanent pastures: Irrigated farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Lands for permanent pastures: Total	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Lands for permanent pastures: Irrigated farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Permanent fields and pasture lands: Total (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Permanent fields and pasture lands: Total	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Permanent fields and pasture lands: Dry farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Permanent fields and pasture lands:	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA

Irrigated farming						
Other areas for pastures	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Area of pastures no longer used for production purposes and which are admitted to a fosterage system	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Area of pastures no longer used for production purposes and which are admitted to a fosterage system (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Other areas for pastures (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Permanent fields and pasture lands: Dry farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Permanent fields and pasture lands: Irrigated farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA

Agricultural Census GENERAL DISTRIBUTION OF AREA: Exploitation of cultivated Irrigated lands

General information

Description: Census. Collection of information regarding the agrarian structure, to serve as the basis for the directory of agricultural operations, in compliance with the legal regulations established by the European Union

Producer: Spanish National Statistics Institute

Link: https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106

Languages: Spanish | Castilian

Catalogue:

Subjects: agricultural product, agricultural region, agricultural statistics

Useful for the analysis of: Use of agricultural area

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: National Statistics Institute (Spain)

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Spain

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 18, 2022

Characterization created at: December 13, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2009

Last update: December 31, 2012

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2009

Keywords: agricultural area

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Agricultural Census	Excel XLSX	Public	https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural holding with UAA	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
All cultivated lands	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Combined arable	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA

Fruit trees	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Olive groves	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Vineyards	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Other cultivated lands (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
All cultivated lands (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Combined arable (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Fruit trees (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Olive groves (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Vineyards (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Other cultivated lands	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA

Local Data Bank - Agricultural holdings

General information

Description: Data by official residence of the land user.

Producer: Statistics Poland

Link: <https://bdl.stat.gov.pl/BDL/metadane/podgrupy/333>

Languages: English

Catalogue:

Subjects: agricultural holdings, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food

Useful for the analysis of: Farm size

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: year

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Poland

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 6, 2022

Characterization created at: December 8, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2010

Last update: October 11, 2017

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 2010 - December, 2016

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
CSV	CSV	Public		CSV	False
Spreadsheet	Excel XLS	Public		Excel XLS	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Organic farms (P3179)	January, 2006 - December, 2020	NUTS2	95	
The share of large holdings in total - new definition of agricultural holding (P3401)	January, 2010 - December, 2016	NUTS2	95	
Agricultural holdings by area groups of agricultural land - new definition of agricultural holding (P3399)	January, 2010 - December, 2016	NUTS2	95	
Organic certified farms - the share of agricultural area in agricultural area total (P3180)	January, 2006 - December, 2020	NUTS2	95	
The average size of private farms with an area exceeding 1 ha of arable land (in ha arable land)- new definition of	January, 2010 - December, 2016	NUTS2	95	

agricultural holding (P3404)				
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Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Area groups - total	Socioeconomic variable	number of farms	January, 2010 - December, 2016	Instant value	Irregular	Agricultural holdings by area groups of agricultural land - new definition of agricultural holding (P3399)
Area groups - up to 1 ha	Socioeconomic variable	number of farms	January, 2010 - December, 2016	Instant value	Irregular	Agricultural holdings by area groups of agricultural land - new definition of agricultural holding (P3399)
Area groups - over 1 ha and less than 2 ha	Socioeconomic variable	number of farms	January, 2010 - December, 2016	Instant value	Irregular	Agricultural holdings by area groups of agricultural land - new definition of agricultural holding (P3399)
Area groups - from 2 to less than 5 ha	Socioeconomic variable	number of farms	January, 2010 - December, 2016	Instant value	Irregular	Agricultural holdings by area groups of agricultural land - new definition of agricultural holding (P3399)
Area groups - over 5 and less than 10 ha	Socioeconomic variable	number of farms	January, 2010 - December, 2016	Instant value	Irregular	Agricultural holdings by area groups of agricultural land - new definition of agricultural holding (P3399)
Area groups - from 10 to less than 15 ha	Socioeconomic variable	number of farms	January, 2010 - December, 2016	Instant value	Irregular	Agricultural holdings by area groups of agricultural land - new definition of agricultural holding (P3399)
Area groups - from 15 to less than 20 ha	Socioeconomic variable	number of farms	January, 2010 - December, 2016	Instant value	Irregular	Agricultural holdings by area groups of agricultural land - new definition of agricultural holding (P3399)
Area groups - to 20 ha	Socioeconomic variable	number of farms	January, 2010 - December, 2016	Instant value	Irregular	Agricultural holdings by area groups of agricultural land - new definition of agricultural holding (P3399)

Area groups - over 20 and less than 30 ha	Socioeconomic variable	number of farms	January, 2010 - December, 2016	Instant value	Irregular	Agricultural holdings by area groups of agricultural land - new definition of agricultural holding (P3399)
Area groups - over 30 and less than 50 ha	Socioeconomic variable	number of farms	January, 2010 - December, 2016	Instant value	Irregular	Agricultural holdings by area groups of agricultural land - new definition of agricultural holding (P3399)
Area groups - from 20 to less than 50 ha	Socioeconomic variable	number of farms	January, 2010 - December, 2016	Instant value	Irregular	Agricultural holdings by area groups of agricultural land - new definition of agricultural holding (P3399)
Area groups - 50 ha and more	Socioeconomic variable	number of farms	January, 2010 - December, 2016	Instant value	Irregular	Agricultural holdings by area groups of agricultural land - new definition of agricultural holding (P3399)
Area groups - from 50 to less than 100 ha	Socioeconomic variable	number of farms	January, 2010 - December, 2016	Instant value	Irregular	Agricultural holdings by area groups of agricultural land - new definition of agricultural holding (P3399)
Area groups - 100 ha and more	Socioeconomic variable	number of farms	January, 2010 - December, 2016	Instant value	Irregular	Agricultural holdings by area groups of agricultural land - new definition of agricultural holding (P3399)
Forms of ownership - total	Socioeconomic variable	number of farms	January, 2010 - December, 2016	Instant value	Irregular	Agricultural holdings by area groups of agricultural land - new definition of agricultural holding (P3399)
Forms of ownership - private farms	Socioeconomic variable	number of farms	January, 2010 - December, 2016	Instant value	Irregular	Agricultural holdings by area groups of agricultural land - new definition of agricultural holding (P3399)
total by a new definition	Socioeconomic variable	%	January, 2006 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Organic certified farms - the share of agricultural area in agricultural area total (P3180)
agricultural holdings, total - agricultural area	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2006 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Organic farms (P3179)

agricultural holdings, total - farms	Socioeconomic variable	number of farms	January, 2006 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Organic farms (P3179)
certified - farms	Socioeconomic variable	number of farms	January, 2006 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Organic farms (P3179)
certified - agricultural area	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2006 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Organic farms (P3179)
under conversion - agricultural area	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2006 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Organic farms (P3179)
under conversion - farms	Socioeconomic variable	number of farms	January, 2006 - December, 2020	Instant value	Annual	Organic farms (P3179)
average size of private farms with an area exceeding 1 ha of arable land	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2010 - December, 2016	Instant value	Irregular	The average size of private farms with an area exceeding 1 ha of arable land (in ha arable land)- new definition of agricultural holding (P3404)
Forms of ownership - total	Socioeconomic variable	%	January, 2010 - December, 2016	Instant value	Irregular	The share of large holdings in total - new definition of agricultural holding (P3401)
Forms of ownership - private farms	Socioeconomic variable	%	January, 2010 - December, 2016	Instant value	Irregular	The share of large holdings in total - new definition of agricultural holding (P3401)

AREA-RICA - Equity indices (INDICI PATRIMONIALI)

General information

Description:

Producer: AREA-RICA

Link: https://arearica.crea.gov.it/report_indx_e.php

Languages: Italian

Catalogue: RICA - report

Subjects: economy, Economy and finance

Useful for the analysis of: Farm economic size

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Year

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: AREA-RICA

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Italy

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: December 16, 2021

Characterization created at: December 9, 2021

Issued:

Last update: December 31, 2019

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2008 - December, 2019

Keywords: economy

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Excel	Excel XLS	Public	https://arearica.crea.gov.it/report_indx_e.php	Excel XLS	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Farm Holding	January, 2008 - December, 2019		37	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Capitalisation of landed property (Capitalizzazione fondiaria)	Socioeconomic variable	Euro	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
Agricultural capitalisation (Capitalizzazione agraria)	Socioeconomic variable	Euro	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
Intensity of land (Intensità fondiaria)	Socioeconomic variable	Euro	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
Agricultural intensity	Socioeconomic variable	Euro	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	

(Intensità agraria)						
Business dynamism (Dinamicità aziendale)	Socioeconomic variable	Euro	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
Companies (Aziende rappresentate)	Socioeconomic variable	Number	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding
Efficiency index of agricultural capital (Indice efficienza del capitale agrario)	Socioeconomic variable	Number	January, 2008 - December, 2019	Instant value	Annual	Farm Holding

Agricultural Census CROPS: Woody crops: Woody non-forest nurseries, woody greenhouse and other permanent crops

General information

Description: Census. Collection of information regarding the agrarian structure, to serve as the basis for the directory of agricultural operations, in compliance with the legal regulations established by the European Union

Producer: Spanish National Statistics Institute

Link: https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106

Languages: Spanish | Castilian

Catalogue:

Subjects: agricultural product, agricultural region, agricultural statistics

Useful for the analysis of: Use of agricultural area

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: National Statistics Institute (Spain)

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Spain

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 17, 2022

Characterization created at: December 13, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2009

Last update: November 3, 2011

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2009

Keywords: agricultural area

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Agricultural Census	Excel XLSX	Public	https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural holding with UAA	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Other permanent crops: Total	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Other permanent crops: Total (area)	Socioeconomic variable	hectare	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA

Other permanent crops: non-irrigated land	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Other permanent crops: non-irrigated land (area)	Socioeconomic variable	hectare	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Other permanent crops: irrigated land	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Other permanent crops: irrigated land (area)	Socioeconomic variable	hectare	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Nursery woody crops: Total	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Nursery woody crops: Total (area)	Socioeconomic variable	hectare	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Nursery woody crops: non-irrigated land	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Nursery woody crops: non-irrigated land (area)	Socioeconomic variable	hectare	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA

Nursery woody crop: irrigated land	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Nursery woody crops: irrigated land (area)	Socioeconomic variable	hectare	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Woody crops in greenhouses: irrigated land	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Woody crops in greenhouses: irrigated land (area)	Socioeconomic variable	hectare	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA

National Soil Erosion Inventory (INES) (for Spain) LAMINAR EROSION AND EROSION IN REGUEROS: Areas and soil losses according to erosion levels

General information

Description: Provide homogeneous and comparable statistical information on soil erosion processes in the national territory

To serve as coordination instrument for the forestal policies and the soil conservation of the autonomous communities, national territory and EU.

To provide information to delimit the priority actuation areas in the fight against erosion

Producer: Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food

Link: <https://www.mapa.gob.es/es/estadistica/temas/publicaciones/anuario-de-estadistica/2017/default.aspx?parte=2&capitulo=12&grupo=7>

Languages: Spanish | Castilian

Catalogue:

Subjects: soil resources, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Land use, Soil

Useful for the analysis of: land use

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type:

Was generated by:

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: ES213, ES212, ES220, ES413, ES211, ES414, ES241, ES513, ES114, ES412, ES243, ES230, ES113, ES512, ES511, ES418, ES419, ES417, ES416, ES514, ES242, ES424, ES415, ES300, ES411, ES522, ES423, ES432, ES425, ES533, ES523, ES532, ES422, ES431, ES421, ES531, ES521,

ES620, ES613, ES616, ES615, ES618, ES614, ES611, ES617, ES612, ES630, ES640, ES708, ES707, ES704, ES709, ES706, ES705, ES703, ES112, ES120, ES130

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 13, 2022

Characterization created at: December 13, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2016

Last update: December 31, 2016

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2016 - December, 2016

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
National soil erosion inventory (INES)LAMINAR EROSION AND EROSION IN REGUEROS: Surface areas and soil losses according to erosion levels	PDF	Public	https://confluence.agricore-project.eu/pages/view/page.action?pageId=8946440	PDF	False
National soil erosion inventory (INES)LAMINAR EROSION AND EROSION IN REGUEROS: Surface areas and soil losses	Excel XLS	Public		Excel XLS	False

according to erosion levels					
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Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Erosion Level 0-5 (t.ha-1 year n-1)	January, 2016 - December, 2016	NUTS3	100	
Erosion Level 5 to 10 (t.ha-1 year n-1)	January, 2016 - December, 2016	NUTS3		
Erosion Level 25 to 50 (t.ha-1 year n-1)	January, 2016 - December, 2016	NUTS3	100	
Erosion Level 10 to 25 (t.ha-1 year n-1)	January, 2016 - December, 2016	NUTS3		
Erosion Level 50 to100 (t.ha-1 year n-1)	January, 2016 - December, 2016	NUTS3	100	
Erosion Level >200 (t.ha-1 year n-1)	January, 2016 - December, 2016	NUTS3	100	
Erosion Level 100 to200 (t.ha-1 year n-1)	January, 2016 - December, 2016	NUTS3	100	
Erodible surface (t.ha-1.year-1)	January, 2016 - December, 2016	NUTS3	100	
Surface water bodies and wetlands (t.ha-1.year-1)	January, 2016 - December, 2016	NUTS3	100	
Artificial surfaces (t.ha-1.year-1)	January, 2016 - December, 2016	NUTS3	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
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Geographical area (hectares)	Socioeconomic variable	(hectares)	January, 2016 - December, 2016	Instant value	Annual	Erosion Level 0-5 (t.ha-1 year n-1), Erosion Level 5 to 10 (t.ha-1 year n-1), Erosion Level 25 to 50 (t.ha-1 year n-1), Erosion Level 10 to 25 (t.ha-1 year n-1), Erosion Level 50 to100 (t.ha-1 year n-1), Erosion Level 100 to200 (t.ha-1 year n-1), Erodible surface (t.ha-1.year-1), Surface water bodies and wetlands (t.ha-1.year-1, Artificial surfaces (t.ha-1.year-1
Geographical area (percentage)	Socioeconomic variable	percentage	January, 2016 - December, 2016	Instant value	Annual	Erosion Level 0-5 (t.ha-1 year n-1), Erosion Level 5 to 10 (t.ha-1 year n-1), Erosion Level 25 to 50 (t.ha-1 year n-1), Erosion Level 10 to 25 (t.ha-1 year n-1), Erosion Level 50 to100 (t.ha-1 year n-1), Erosion Level 100 to200 (t.ha-1 year n-1), Erodible surface (t.ha-1.year-1), Surface water bodies and wetlands (t.ha-1.year-1, Artificial surfaces (t.ha-1.year-1
loss of soil (t. year-1)	Socioeconomic variable	t. year-1	January, 2016 - December, 2016	Instant value	Annual	Erosion Level 0-5 (t.ha-1 year n-1), Erosion Level 5 to 10 (t.ha-1 year n-1), Erosion Level 25 to 50 (t.ha-1 year n-1), Erosion Level 10 to 25 (t.ha-1 year n-1), Erosion Level 50 to100 (t.ha-1 year n-1), Erosion Level 100 to200 (t.ha-1 year n-1), Erodible surface (t.ha-1.year-1)
loss of soil percentage)	Socioeconomic variable	percentage	January, 2016 - December, 2016	Instant value	Annual	Erosion Level 0-5 (t.ha-1 year n-1), Erosion Level 5 to 10 (t.ha-1 year n-1), Erosion Level 25 to 50 (t.ha-1 year n-1), Erosion Level 10 to 25 (t.ha-1 year n-1), Erosion Level 50 to100 (t.ha-1 year n-1), Erosion Level 100 to200 (t.ha-1 year n-1), Erodible surface (t.ha-1.year-1)

average loss(t.ha-1. year-1)	Socioeconomic variable	t.ha-1. year-1	January, 2016 - December, 2016	Instant value	Annual	Erosion Level 0-5 (t.ha-1 year n-1), Erosion Level 5 to 10 (t.ha-1 year n-1), Erosion Level 25 to 50 (t.ha-1 year n-1), Erosion Level 10 to 25 (t.ha-1 year n-1), Erosion Level 50 to100 (t.ha-1 year n-1), Erosion Level 100 to200 (t.ha-1 year n-1), Erodible surface (t.ha-1.year-1)
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Agricultural Census CROPS: Woody crops: Vineyards

General information

Description: Census. Collection of information regarding the agrarian structure, to serve as the basis for the directory of agricultural operations, in compliance with the legal regulations established by the European Union

Producer: Spanish National Statistics Institute

Link: https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106

Languages: Spanish | Castilian

Catalogue:

Subjects: agricultural product, agricultural region, agricultural statistics

Useful for the analysis of: Use of agricultural area

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: National Statistics Institute (Spain)

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Spain

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 17, 2022

Characterization created at: December 13, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2009

Last update: November 3, 2011

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2009

Keywords: agricultural area

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Agricultural Census	Excel XLSX	Public	https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural holding with UAA	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Vineyards. Dry farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Vineyards. Irrigation farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Table grapes. Dry farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Table grapes. Irrigation farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA

Grapes for raisins. Dry farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Grapes for raisins. Irrigation farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Vinification grapes. Dry farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Vinification grapes. Irrigation farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
For quality wines. Dry farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
For quality wines. Irrigation farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
For other wines. Dry farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
For other wines. Irrigation farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Vinification grapes. Total (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Vinification grapes. Dry farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA

Vinification grapes. Irrigation farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Vinification grapes. Total	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
For quality wines. Total (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
For other wines. Total (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Vineyards. Total	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Vineyards. Total (area)	Socioeconomic variable	hectare	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Vineyards. Dry farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Vineyards. Irrigation farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Table grapes. Total	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Table grapes. Total (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Table grapes. Dry farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA

Table grapes. Irrigation farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Grapes for raisins. Total (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Grapes for raisins. Dry farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Grapes for raisins. Irrigation farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Grapes for raisins. Total	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
For quality wines. Dry farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
For quality wines. Irrigation farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
For quality wines. Total	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
For other wines. Dry farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
For other wines. Irrigation farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA

For other wines. Total	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
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Agricultural Census CROPS: Woody crops: Olive grove

General information

Description: Census. Collection of information regarding the agrarian structure, to serve as the basis for the directory of agricultural operations, in compliance with the legal regulations established by the European Union

Producer: Spanish National Statistics Institute

Link: https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106

Languages: Spanish | Castilian

Catalogue:

Subjects: agricultural product, agricultural region, agricultural statistics

Useful for the analysis of: Use of agricultural area

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: National Statistics Institute (Spain)

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Spain

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 17, 2022

Characterization created at: December 13, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2009

Last update: November 3, 2011

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2009

Keywords: agricultural area

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Agricultural Census	Excel XLSX	Public	https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural holding with UAA	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Olive groves. Irrigation farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Table olives. Irrigation farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Oil-press olives. Irrigation farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA

Olive groves. Irrigation farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Table olives. Total	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Olive groves. Total	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Olive groves. Total (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Olive groves. Dry farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Olive groves. Dry farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Table olives. Total (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Table olives. Dry farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Table olives. Dry farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Table olives. Irrigation farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Oil-press olives. Total (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA

Oil-press olives. Dry farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Oil-press olives. Dry farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Oil-press olives. Irrigation farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Oil-press olives. Total	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA

Agricultural Census CROPS: Woody crops: Fruit trees

General information

Description: Census. Collection of information regarding the agrarian structure, to serve as the basis for the directory of agricultural operations, in compliance with the legal regulations established by the European Union

Producer: Spanish National Statistics Institute

Link: https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106

Languages: Spanish | Castilian

Catalogue:

Subjects: agricultural product, agricultural region, agricultural statistics

Useful for the analysis of: Use of agricultural area

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: National Statistics Institute (Spain)

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Spain

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 17, 2022

Characterization created at: December 13, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2009

Last update: November 3, 2011

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2009

Keywords: agricultural area

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Agricultural Census	Excel XLSX	Public	https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural holding with UAA	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Berries. Total	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Fruit trees. Dry farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Fruit trees. Irrigation farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Citrus fruit trees. Irrigation farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA

Berries. Dry farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Berries. Irrigation farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Berries. Dry farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Berries. Irrigation farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Fruit trees native to subtropical climates. Dry farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Fruit trees native to subtropical climates. Irrigation farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Nut trees. Dry farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Nut trees. Irrigation farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Berries. Total (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Fruit trees. Total	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA

Fruit trees. Total (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Fruit trees. Dry farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Fruit trees. Irrigation farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Citrus fruit trees. Total	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Citrus fruit trees. Total (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Citrus fruit trees. Dry farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Citrus fruit trees. Dry farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Citrus fruit trees. Irrigation farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Fruit trees native to subtropical climates. Total	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Fruit trees native to subtropical climates. Total (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA

Fruit trees native to subtropical climates. Dry farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Fruit trees native to subtropical climates. Irrigation farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Nut trees. Total (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Nut trees. Dry farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Nut trees. Irrigation farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Nut trees. Total	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA

Standard Results of the Spanish FADN (Red Contable Agraria Nacional - RECAN)

General information

Description: The National Farm Accountancy Network is a tool for assessing farm income and the impact of agricultural policy on farms. It is governed by a Community Regulation, which means that the same accounting principles apply in all countries. It is therefore the only complete source of microdata in Spain and harmonised with the rest of the EU countries.

Producer: Spanish Ministry for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food

Link: <https://www.mapa.gob.es/es/estadistica/temas/estadisticas-agrarias/economia/red-contable-recan/>

Languages: Spanish | Castilian

Catalogue:

Subjects: agricultural economics, agricultural holdings, agricultural research, agricultural statistics, accounting, Agriculture, fisheries, forestry and food, Farm Structure

Useful for the analysis of: Agricultural costs, Agricultural value added, Agriculture policy, Crop production, Farm economic size, land use, Use of agricultural area

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: Annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: Regular operation of the FADN in Spain

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: ES423, ES432, ES425, ES533, ES523, ES532, ES422, ES431, ES421, ES531, ES521, ES620, ES613, ES616, ES615, ES618, ES614, ES611, ES617, ES612, ES708, ES707, ES704, ES709, ES706, ES705, ES703, ES111, ES112, ES120, ES130, ES213, ES212, ES220, ES413, ES211, ES414, ES241, ES513, ES114, ES412, ES243, ES230, ES113, ES512, ES511, ES418, ES419, ES417, ES416, ES514, ES242, ES424, ES415, ES300, ES411, ES522

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 13, 2022

Characterization created at: November 25, 2021

Issued: September 5, 2013

Last update: July 15, 2021

Periodicity: Annual

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2019

Keywords:

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
PDF Files	PDF	Public	https://www.mapa.gob.es/es/estadistica/temas/estadisticas-agrarias/economia/re-d-contable-recan/#ancla5	PDF	False
Excel Workbooks	Excel XLS	Public	https://www.mapa.gob.es/es/estadistica/temas/estadisticas-agrarias/economia/re-d-contable-recan/	Excel XLS	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural Holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2019	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
(SE025) Total Utilised Agricultural Area / Superficie Agraria Útil	Socioeconomic variable	Hectares (ha)	January, 2009 - December, 2019	Average		Agricultural Holdings
(SE030) Rented Utilised Agricultural Area / Superficie Agraria Útil en arrendamiento	Socioeconomic variable	Hectares (ha)	January, 2009 - December, 2019	Average		Agricultural Holdings
(SE080) Total Livestock Units / Unidades de Ganado	Socioeconomic variable	Livestock Units (LSU) (LU)	January, 2009 - December, 2019	Average		Agricultural Holdings
(SE206) Total output livestock & livestock products / Producción Bruta Animal	Socioeconomic variable	Euros (€)	January, 2009 - December, 2019	Average		Agricultural Holdings
(SE256) Other output / Otra producción bruta	Socioeconomic variable	Euros (€)	January, 2009 - December, 2019	Average		Agricultural Holdings
(SE270) Total Inputs / Costes Totales	Socioeconomic variable	Euros (€)	January, 2009 - December, 2019	Average		Agricultural Holdings

(SE283) Total Livestock Specific Costs / Costes específicos de ganados	Socioeconomic variable	Euros (€)	January, 2009 - December, 2019	Average		Agricultural Holdings
(SE750) Total Specific Costs from Other Activities / Costes específicos de otras actividades lucrativas	Socioeconomic variable	Euros (€)	January, 2009 - December, 2019	Average		Agricultural Holdings
(SE336) Total Farming Overheads / Costes generales	Socioeconomic variable	Euros (€)	January, 2009 - December, 2019	Average		Agricultural Holdings
(SE010) Total Labour Input / Mano de Obra Total	Socioeconomic variable	Annual Working Unit (AWU)	January, 2009 - December, 2019	Average		Agricultural Holdings
(SE015) Unpaid Labour Input / Mano de obra no asalariada	Socioeconomic variable	Annual Working Unit (AWU)	January, 2009 - December, 2019	Average		Agricultural Holdings
(SE020) Paid Labour Input / Mano de obra asalariada	Socioeconomic variable	Annual Working Unit (AWU)	January, 2009 - December, 2019	Average		Agricultural Holdings
(SE131) Total Output /	Socioeconomic variable	Euros (€)	January, 2009 - December, 2019	Average		Agricultural Holdings

Producción Bruta Total						
(SE135) Total output crops & crop production / Producción Bruta Vegetal	Socioeconomic variable	Euros (€)	January, 2009 - December, 2019	Average		Agricultural Holdings
(SE275) Total Intermediate Consumption / Consumos intermedios	Socioeconomic variable	Euros (€)	January, 2009 - December, 2019	Average		Agricultural Holdings
(SE281) Total Specific Costs / Costes específicos	Socioeconomic variable	Euros (€)	January, 2009 - December, 2019	Average		Agricultural Holdings
(SE282) Total Crop Specific Costs / Costes específicos de cultivos	Socioeconomic variable	Euros (€)	January, 2009 - December, 2019	Average		Agricultural Holdings
(SE350) Contract work / Costes generales por trabajos de terceros y arrendamiento de maquinaria	Socioeconomic variable	Euros (€)	January, 2009 - December, 2019	Average		Agricultural Holdings
(SE340) Machinery & building current costs / Costes generales por mantenimiento	Socioeconomic variable	Euros (€)	January, 2009 - December, 2019	Average		Agricultural Holdings

corriente de maquinaria y edificios						
(SE345) Energy costs / Costes generales por energía	Socioeconomic variable	Euros (€)	January, 2009 - December, 2019	Average		Agricultural Holdings
(SE356) Other direct inputs / Otros costes generales	Socioeconomic variable	Euros (€)	January, 2009 - December, 2019	Average		Agricultural Holdings
(SE360) Depreciation / Amortizaciones	Socioeconomic variable	Euros (€)	January, 2009 - December, 2019	Average		Agricultural Holdings
(SE365) Total External Factors / Costes de Factores Externos	Socioeconomic variable	Euros (€)	January, 2009 - December, 2019	Average		Agricultural Holdings
(SE370) Wages paid / Salarios y cargas sociales	Socioeconomic variable	Euros (€)	January, 2009 - December, 2019	Average		Agricultural Holdings
(SE375) Rent paid / Arrendamientos pagados	Socioeconomic variable	Euros (€)	January, 2009 - December, 2019	Average		Agricultural Holdings
(SE380) Interest paid / Intereses pagados	Socioeconomic variable	Euros (€)	January, 2009 - December, 2019	Average		Agricultural Holdings
(SE605) Total subsidies excluding on investments /	Socioeconomic variable	Euros (€)	January, 2009 - December, 2019	Average		Agricultural Holdings

Subvenciones corrientes totales						
(SE610) Total subsidies on crops / Subvenciones corrientes totales por cultivos	Socioeconomic variable	Euros (€)	January, 2009 - December, 2019	Average		Agricultural Holdings
(SE615) Total subsidies on livestock / Subvenciones corrientes totales por ganado	Socioeconomic variable	Euros (€)	January, 2009 - December, 2019	Average		Agricultural Holdings
(SE630) Decoupled payments / Pagos desacoplados	Socioeconomic variable	Euros (€)	January, 2009 - December, 2019	Average		Agricultural Holdings
(SE624) Rural development payments / Subvenciones corrientes por desarrollo rural	Socioeconomic variable	Euros (€)	January, 2009 - December, 2019	Average		Agricultural Holdings
(SE699) Other subsidies / Otras subvenciones	Socioeconomic variable	Euros (€)	January, 2009 - December, 2019	Average		Agricultural Holdings

(SE436) Total Assets / Activos totales	Socioeconomic variable	Euros (€)	January, 2009 - December, 2019	Average		Agricultural Holdings
(SE441) Total Fixed Assets / Capital fijo	Socioeconomic variable	Euros (€)	January, 2009 - December, 2019	Average		Agricultural Holdings
(SE446) Land, permanent crops & quotas / Tierras, cultivos permanentes y cuotas	Socioeconomic variable	Euros (€)	January, 2009 - December, 2019	Average		Agricultural Holdings
(SE450) Buildings / Edificios y mejoras	Socioeconomic variable	Euros (€)	January, 2009 - December, 2019	Average		Agricultural Holdings
(SE455) Machinery / Maquinaria y equipo	Socioeconomic variable	Euros (€)	January, 2009 - December, 2019	Average		Agricultural Holdings
(SE460) Breeding livestock / Ganado reproductor	Socioeconomic variable	Euros (€)	January, 2009 - December, 2019	Average		Agricultural Holdings
(SE465) Total Current Assets / Capital circulante	Socioeconomic variable	Euros (€)	January, 2009 - December, 2019	Average		Agricultural Holdings
(SE485) Total Liabilities / Pasivos totales	Socioeconomic variable	Euros (€)	January, 2009 - December, 2019	Average		Agricultural Holdings

(SE490) Long & medium term loans / Préstamos a medio y Largo Plazo	Socioeconomic variable	Euros (€)	January, 2009 - December, 2019	Average		Agricultural Holdings
(SE495) Short term loans / Préstamos a corto Plazo	Socioeconomic variable	Euros (€)	January, 2009 - December, 2019	Average		Agricultural Holdings
(SE600) Balance current subsidies & taxes / Subvenciones corrientes netas	Socioeconomic variable	Euros (€)	January, 2009 - December, 2019	Average		Agricultural Holdings
(SE410) Gross Farm Income / Valor Añadido Bruto de Explotación	Socioeconomic variable	Euros (€)	January, 2009 - December, 2019	Average		Agricultural Holdings
(SE415) Farm Net Added Value / Valor Añadido Neto de Explotación	Socioeconomic variable	Euros (€)	January, 2009 - December, 2019	Average		Agricultural Holdings
(SE415M) Median Farm Net Added Value / Valor Añadido Neto de Explotación (Mediana)	Socioeconomic variable	Euros (€)	January, 2009 - December, 2019	Median		Agricultural Holdings

(SE420) Farm Net Income / Renta Neta de Explotación	Socioeconomic variable	Euros (€)	January, 2009 - December, 2019	Average		Agricultural Holdings
(SE136) Total crops output per hectare / Producción Bruta Vegetal por SAU	Socioeconomic variable	Euros (€)/ha	January, 2009 - December, 2019	Average		Agricultural Holdings
(SE207) Total livestock output per livestock unit / Producción Bruta Animal por UG	Socioeconomic variable	Euros (€)/Livestock Unit (LU)	January, 2009 - December, 2019	Average		Agricultural Holdings
(SE284) Specific Crop Costs per hectare / Costes específicos de cultivos por SAU	Socioeconomic variable	Euros (€) / Hectare (ha)	January, 2009 - December, 2019	Average		Agricultural Holdings
(SE309) Specific Livestock Costs per Livestock Unit / Costes específicos de ganados por Unidad Ganadera	Socioeconomic variable	Euros (€) / Livestock Unit (LU)	January, 2009 - December, 2019	Average		Agricultural Holdings
(SE425) Farm Net Value Added per Agricultural	Socioeconomic variable	Euros (€) / Agricultural	January, 2009 - December, 2019	Average		Agricultural Holdings

Working Units / Valor Añadido Neto de Explotación por Unidades de Trabajo Agrícola		Working Units (AWU)				
(SE425M) Median Farm Net Value Added per Agricultural Working Units / Valor Añadido Neto de Explotación por Unidades de Trabajo Agrícola (Mediana)	Socioeconomic variable	Euros (€) / Agricultural Working Units (AWU)	January, 2009 - December, 2019	Median		Agricultural Holdings
Weight of Net Subsidies regarding Net Value Added / Peso de las Subvenciones corrientes Netas con respecto al Valor añadido Neto	Socioeconomic variable	Percentage %	January, 2009 - December, 2019	Average		Agricultural Holdings

Agricultural Census CROPS: Arable crops and fallow lands: Seeds and seedlings for sale

General information

Description: Census. Collection of information regarding the agrarian structure, to serve as the basis for the directory of agricultural operations, in compliance with the legal regulations established by the European Union

Producer: Spanish National Statistics Institute

Link: https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106

Languages: Spanish | Castilian

Catalogue:

Subjects: agricultural product, agricultural region, agricultural statistics

Useful for the analysis of: Use of agricultural area

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: National Statistics Institute (Spain)

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Spain

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 17, 2022

Characterization created at: December 13, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2009

Last update: November 3, 2011

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2009

Keywords: agricultural area

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Agricultural Census	Excel XLSX	Public	https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural holding with UAA	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Seeds and seedlings for sale: Dry farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Seeds and seedlings for sale. Total	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA

Seeds and seedlings for sale. Total (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Seeds and seedlings for sale: Dry farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Seeds and seedlings for sale: Irrigation farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Seeds and seedlings for sale: Irrigation farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA

Agricultural Census CROPS: Arable crops and fallow lands: Seeds, fallow lands, other arable crops and kitchen gardens

General information

Description: Census. Collection of information regarding the agrarian structure, to serve as the basis for the directory of agricultural operations, in compliance with the legal regulations established by the European Union

Producer: Spanish National Statistics Institute

Link: https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106

Languages: Spanish | Castilian

Catalogue:

Subjects: agricultural product, agricultural region, agricultural statistics

Useful for the analysis of: Use of agricultural area

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: National Statistics Institute (Spain)

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Spain

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 17, 2022

Characterization created at: December 13, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2009

Last update: November 3, 2011

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2009

Keywords: agricultural area

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Agricultural Census	Excel XLSX	Public	https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural holding with UAA	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Fallow land: Total (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Fallow land: Total	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Fallow land: Subsidised (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA

Kitchen garden (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Fallow land: Subsidised	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Fallow land: Non-subsidised (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Fallow land: Non-subsidised	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Kitchen garden	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA

Agricultural Census CROPS: Arable crops and fallow lands: Ornamental flowers and plants

General information

Description: Census. Collection of information regarding the agrarian structure, to serve as the basis for the directory of agricultural operations, in compliance with the legal regulations established by the European Union

Producer: Spanish National Statistics Institute

Link: https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106

Languages: Spanish | Castilian

Catalogue:

Subjects: agricultural product, agricultural region, agricultural statistics

Useful for the analysis of: Use of agricultural area

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: National Statistics Institute (Spain)

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Spain

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 17, 2022

Characterization created at: December 13, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2009

Last update: November 3, 2011

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2009

Keywords: agricultural area

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Agricultural Census	Excel XLSX	Public	https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural holding with UAA	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Ornamental flowers and plants: Dry farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Ornamental flowers and plants. Total	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA

Ornamental flowers and plants: Total (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Ornamental flowers and plants: Dry farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Open air and/or sheltered: Irrigation farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Ornamental flowers and plants: Irrigation farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Ornamental flowers and plants: Irrigation farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Open air and/or sheltered: Dry farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Open air and/or sheltered: Total	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Open air and/or sheltered: Total (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA

Open air and/or sheltered: Dry farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Open air and/or sheltered: Irrigation farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
In greenhouse (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
In greenhouse	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA

Agricultural Census CROPS: Arable crops and fallow lands: Vegetables

General information

Description: Census. Collection of information regarding the agrarian structure, to serve as the basis for the directory of agricultural operations, in compliance with the legal regulations established by the European Union

Producer: Spanish National Statistics Institute

Link: https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106

Languages: Spanish | Castilian

Catalogue:

Subjects: agricultural product, agricultural region, agricultural statistics

Useful for the analysis of: Use of agricultural area

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: National Statistics Institute (Spain)

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Spain

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 18, 2022

Characterization created at: December 13, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2009

Last update: November 3, 2011

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2009

Keywords: agricultural area

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Agricultural Census	Excel XLSX	Public	https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural holdings with UAA	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
In field work: Total (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holdings with UAA
In field work: Dry farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holdings with UAA
In field work: Total	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holdings with UAA

In field work: Dry farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holdings with UAA
Vegetable crops: Irrigation farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holdings with UAA
Vegetable crops: Irrigation farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holdings with UAA
Vegetables: Total	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holdings with UAA
Vegetables: Total (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holdings with UAA
Vegetables: Dry farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holdings with UAA
Vegetables: Dry farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holdings with UAA
Vegetables: Irrigation farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holdings with UAA
Vegetables: Irrigation farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holdings with UAA
In field work: Irrigation farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holdings with UAA
In field work: Irrigation farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holdings with UAA

In horticultural crop: Total	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holdings with UAA
In horticultural crop: Total (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holdings with UAA
In horticultural crop: Dry farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holdings with UAA
In horticultural crop: Dry farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holdings with UAA
In greenhouse: Total	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holdings with UAA
In greenhouse: Total (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holdings with UAA

Agricultural Census CROPS: Arable crops and fallow lands: Industrial crops

General information

Description: Census. Collection of information regarding the agrarian structure, to serve as the basis for the directory of agricultural operations, in compliance with the legal regulations established by the European Union

Producer: Spanish National Statistics Institute

Link: https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106

Languages: Spanish | Castilian

Catalogue:

Subjects: agricultural product, agricultural region, agricultural statistics

Useful for the analysis of: Use of agricultural area

Themes covered:

Spatial resolution (in meters):

Temporal resolution: annual

Resource type: Dataset

Was generated by: National Statistics Institute (Spain)

Is referenced by:

Geographical coverage: Spain

Dataset type: SOCIOECONOMIC

Characterization last update: January 18, 2022

Characterization created at: December 13, 2021

Issued: January 1, 2009

Last update: November 3, 2011

Periodicity: Irregular

Temporal extent: January, 2009 - December, 2009

Keywords: agricultural area

Distributions

Title	Format	Access rights	Access URL	Compress format	Data service
Agricultural Census	Excel XLSX	Public	https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176851&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735727106	Excel XLSX	False

Units of analysis

Name	Temporal extent	Aggregation level unit	Population coverage	Unit of analysis number
Agricultural holding with UAA	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Country	100	

Variables included

Name	Type	Unit of measurement	Temporal extent	Mathematical representation	Data frequency	Unit of analysis
Aromatic and medicinal plants and spices: Dry farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Aromatic and medicinal plants and spices: Irrigation farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Aromatic and medicinal plants	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA

and spices: Irrigation farming (area)						
Aromatic and medicinal plants and spices: Total	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Hops: Total (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Aromatic and medicinal plants and spices: Total (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Aromatic and medicinal plants and spices: Dry farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Soybeans: Total	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Soybeans: Total (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Soybeans: Dry farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Soybeans: Dry farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Soybeans: Irrigation farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Soybeans: Irrigation farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA

Other industrial crops: Total	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Other oleaginous crops: Dry farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Other oleaginous crops: Irrigation farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Other oleaginous crops: Irrigation farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Tobacco: Total	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Tobacco: Total (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Sunflowers: Total	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Sunflowers: Total (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Sunflowers: Dry farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Cotton: Irrigation farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA

Cotton: Irrigation farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Other textile crops: Total	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Other industrial crops: Total (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Other industrial crops: Dry farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Other industrial crops: Dry farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Other industrial crops: Irrigation farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Other industrial crops: Irrigation farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Tobacco: Dry farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Tobacco: Dry farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Tobacco: Irrigation farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Tobacco: Irrigation farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA

Sunflowers: Dry farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Sunflowers: Irrigation farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Sunflowers: Irrigation farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Linseed (oil flax): Total	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Linseed (oil flax): Total (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Linseed (oil flax): Dry farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Linseed (oil flax): Dry farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Linseed (oil flax): Irrigation farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Linseed (oil flax): Irrigation farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Hops: Total	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Hops: Dry farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA

Hops: Dry farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Hops: Irrigation farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Hops: Irrigation farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Industrial crops: Total	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Industrial crops: Total (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Industrial crops: Dry farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Industrial crops: Dry farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Industrial crops: Irrigation farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Industrial crops: Irrigation farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Sugar beet: Total	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Sugar beet: Total (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Sugar beet: Dry farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA

Sugar beet: Dry farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Sugar beet: Irrigation farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Sugar beet: Irrigation farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Cotton: Total	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Cotton: Total (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Cotton: Dry farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Cotton: Dry farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Other textile crops: Total (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Other textile crops: Dry farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Other textile crops: Dry farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Other textile crops: Irrigation farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA

Other textile crops: Irrigation farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Rapessed an turnip rapessed: Total	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Rapessed an turnip rapessed: Total (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Rapessed an turnip rapessed: Dry farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Rapessed an turnip rapessed: Dry farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Rapessed an turnip rapessed: Irrigation farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Rapessed an turnip rapessed: Irrigation farming (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Other oleaginous crops: Total	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
Other oleaginous crops: Total (area)	Socioeconomic variable	ha	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA

Other oleaginous crops: Dry farming	Socioeconomic variable	Number of agricultural holdings	January, 2009 - December, 2009	Instant value	Annual	Agricultural holding with UAA
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